

Taico

Teacher-AI Complementarity

INITIAL MODEL OF TEACHER-AI COMPLEMENTARITY

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Authors	Ann-Christin Falhs (RUB), Nikol Rummel (RUB), Anne-Wil Kramer (RU), Inge Molenaar (RU), Paraskevi Topali (RU), Tobias Ley (UWK)
Reviewers	Tobias Ley (UWK), Qi Zhou (UCL), Wannapon Suraworachet (UCL)
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Executive summary

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly entering educational practice. Yet there is still limited understanding of how AI systems and teachers interact within concrete pedagogical work. Rather than asking whether AI improves performance and outcomes, the TAICo project investigates how AI reshapes teaching tasks, required skills, and professional practice in authentic educational settings.

This deliverable presents the first version of the TAICo Workpackage 1 (WP1) teacher-AI complementarity model, grounded in the idea that complementarity becomes observable only when we describe teacher work at sufficient granularity: actions within pedagogical tasks, who performs them, how information flows between teacher and AI, and which skills and knowledge are required to perform those actions.

Complementarity is therefore not treated as a general property of a tool or as a performance comparison between humans and AI. Instead, it is conceptualised as a configuration of distributed actions, skills, and knowledge within shared pedagogical tasks. It emerges from how teachers and AI systems interact within a shared pedagogical task to achieve instructional goals.

To analyse these configurations systematically, the deliverable pursues a three-component methodological approach:

1. Hierarchical Task Analysis (HTA) models pedagogical tasks in both teacher-only and AI-supported conditions. It identifies pedagogical tasks, their subtasks, actions, and conditions, and specifies whether actions are existing or newly introduced through AI, which actor performs them, and how information flows between teacher and AI.
2. Skill and Knowledge Analysis (SKA) links coded actions to cognitive and metacognitive skills (e.g., perceiving, interpreting, deciding, planning, monitoring, evaluating), respective AI capabilities (e.g., detect, diagnose, inform) required to perform those actions, alongside professional and AI-related knowledge requirements and identifies whether these demands are existing or new.
3. Complementarity Analysis (CA) integrates task-level and skill-level indicators at the level of subtasks and assigns formal complementarity labels based on observable configurations (e.g., teacher-led complementarity).

Together, these components open the “black box” of teacher-AI interaction, revealing how complementarity is derived from systematically coded task structures and skill distributions.

We demonstrate the feasibility of our modeling approach through an initial application to one of the TAICo cases, more specifically, Radboud University’s case (RU case). In this setting, primary school teachers use Snappet Copilot (an educational AI) to plan differentiated math lessons. The AI primarily reconfigures work by generating suggestions that teachers can interpret and evaluate. This creates a form of teacher-led complementarity: teachers remain central decision-makers, while the AI supports them with input. As a result, new tasks emerge, along with new skill and knowledge requirements for teachers.

Overall, the analysis of this case indicates that full teacher replacement at task level is unlikely. Instead, teacher-AI interaction emerges in specific, context-dependent ways that depend on how the tool is implemented and used. In this setting, AI does not replace teacher judgment. Rather, in this case, it restructures the informational basis of decision-making. The resulting skill requirements concern the ability to interpret AI generated outputs, appropriately calibrate trust and decide when to accept, adapt, or override suggestions, and integrate AI-informed decisions with curricular and ethical considerations.

Moving forward, WP1 will (1) pool HTAs and skill codings across all TAICo cases to refine the complementarity model, (2) evaluate in Task 1.4 how AI-supported task level action patterns affect teachers' tasks and work processes, and (3) evaluate in T1.5 how AI affects teachers' skills and knowledge demands, including potential risks of erosion and new competence requirements.

With this deliverable, WP1 will provide systematic inputs to subsequent Workpackages: WP2 validates the complementarity model through the TAICo case studies and synthesizes findings across cases to build a robust knowledge base. WP3 analyzes existing AI tools and develops future-oriented, human-centered design scenarios to formulate evidence-informed guidelines for AI development and deployment. WP4 investigates teacher professional learning and the impact of AI on the teaching profession to derive policy recommendations and best practices for teacher training. Against this background, WP1 provides input to all three WPs. It develops operationalised constructs and validation in WP2. It also identifies links between complementarity patterns and specific AI interaction features and affordances, thereby informing the analytical and design-oriented work in WP3. In addition, WP1 highlights emerging skill demands and changing task configurations, which serve as professional development anchors for WP4.

Structure of this deliverable

The remainder of this deliverable is structured as follows. Chapter 1 provides an introduction to the background, aims and scope of this deliverable and situates the complementarity model within the broader TAICo framework. Chapter 2 presents the theoretical background, drawing on an economic lens on task-level change and an educational lens on teachers' professional skills and knowledge. Chapter 3 describes the method, detailing the three analytical components: Hierarchical Task Analysis, Skill and Knowledge Analysis, and Complementarity Analysis. Chapter 4 presents the results of applying this method to the RU curriculum adaptivity case. Chapter 5 discusses the findings and reflects on the strengths and limitations of the analytical approach. Chapter 6 concludes and outlines next steps for the model development.

1. Introduction

TAICo, as part of the Horizon Europe framework program, aims to develop and validate a model explaining how teachers and AI systems complement each other in real pedagogical settings, across educational sectors and contexts.

Rather than focusing on isolated AI applications or performance outcomes, TAICo investigates how AI technologies reshape pedagogical work, teacher competences, and professional practice within authentic educational settings.

Within the project, **Work Package 1 (WP1)** is responsible for developing and refining a comprehensive model that shapes our understanding of complementarity. Deliverable D1.1 constitutes the first formal report on the development cycle. It presents an initial version of the Teacher-AI Complementarity model (TAICo model), developed through conceptual synthesis and iterative engagement with TAICo cases.

D1.1 builds directly on Tasks T1.1 and T1.2.

- T1.1 focuses on task level changes in AI deployment in education.
- T1.2 examines the changing knowledge and skill dimensions involved in performing these tasks.

Together, T1.1 and T1.2 provide the basis for modelling complementarity. In prior work on human-AI complementarity (e.g. Vaccaro, Almaatouq, & Malone, 2024), successful complementarity was primarily defined in terms of performance or outcomes, whether human and AI together perform better than either could alone. While valuable, this perspective tends to treat the interaction itself as a “black box.” TAICo instead, takes teacher-AI interaction within pedagogical tasks as the primary unit of analysis. Complementarity becomes observable when we describe how tasks, skills and knowledge are distributed and coordinated between teachers and AI at a fine-grained level (i.e., what each actor does, how information flows, and what skills are required).

With this deliverable, **WP1 introduces the initial conceptual model and the methodological approach that together form the foundation for analysing Teacher-AI complementarity** within the broader TAICo framework.

1.1. The TAICo Framework

While WP1 develops the conceptual model of Teacher-AI complementarity, this model is embedded within the broader **TAICo framework**, which conceptualises complementarity as part of a **sociotechnical ecosystem**. The TAICo framework specifies the conditions under which teacher-AI interaction unfolds and through which complementarity configurations emerge (see Figure 1).

Teacher-AI complementarity can be observed when teachers interact with AI systems in the implementation of pedagogical tasks in concrete educational settings. The interaction between teachers and AI is embedded into a broader **socio-technical context**. This context is

defined by three types of conditions: the characteristics of the teacher interacting with AI, the characteristics of the AI System, and the way the AI system is deployed in the educational setting.

These conditions are important for at least two reasons. First, conditions in the sociotechnical system will determine the complementarity configuration at task as well as skill and knowledge level that will emerge. Different teachers will interact differently with the system. For example, we have observed that situation-specific skills of the teacher (e.g., perceive, interpret, decide) determine to some extent how meaningful teachers interact with the AI (see Ley et al., 2025). Similarly, expectations towards and knowledge of AI influences the interaction. The way AI systems are designed also plays an important role in influencing the interaction. Systems that are not transparent or communicate in ways not understood by teachers disrupt the flow when a pedagogical task is performed. Finally, deployment is an important factor. For example, time constraints under which teachers work in a particular situation influence how they process information provided by the AI tool.

The second reason why a focus on the sociotechnical conditions is important is that these conditions can be altered to influence the complementarity configuration that emerges. While complementarity is an emergent property of the interaction and can not easily be changed directly, it can be influenced through the design of the conditions that shape it. Teachers can be prepared, AI tools can be designed, and deployment conditions altered. In the TAICo project, we therefore do not only examine the sociotechnical conditions to understand how they shape complementarity, but we actively shape them to explore the design space of teacher training (WP4), AI tool and model design and implementation (WP3) as well as the design of the deployment conditions (WP3 and 4).

Figure 1: TAICo framework

1.1.1 The conceptual basis of the TAICo framework

From the perspective of the broader TAICo framework, complementarity is understood as emerging from within a socio-technical system that considers the determinants of teacher-AI complementarity and examines these determinants and their adaptation and development. We draw on a number of conceptualizations that have been applied to understand socio-technical systems in education. First, the use of intelligent technology in education has been considered from the perspective of models of distributed cognition (Cukurova et al., 2019; Ley et al, 2023) that consider the distribution of cognitive processing across human actors and artificial agents. It is assumed that a coupling of human and machine intelligence is achieved by a distribution of representations across internal cognitive states and external artefacts. The coupling creates a distributed cognitive system that can complete tasks by propagating cognitive states across these representations. In teaching tasks, knowledge representations include those pedagogical and psychological models of learning and instruction used both by the teacher as well as those used by the AI tool and that mediate interpretation and decision making in the cognitive system (Ley et al, 2023).

The way we have conceptualized the distributed cognitive system in this work assumes that the **interaction between teachers and AI** is initiated and embedded into a particular **pedagogical task** which provides the pedagogical goal. Interactions then lead to

complementarity configurations emerging on the task and skill level (see the inner circle of Figure 1). At the same time, these teacher-AI interactions do not happen in isolation but instead are embedded into a sociocultural context in which representations (internal cognitive states and external artefacts) act as cultural products and mediate human activity (Alaimo, 2024) and are therefore also key for understanding and supporting professional learning (Billett, 2021). The outer circles in Figure 1 present some of these important elements of the sociocultural context in line with conceptions of human activity systems. Besides the subject (the teacher), the tool (AI) and the object (the task) of the activity, the activity system is defined by the community, its rules and division of labour which we denote here as the deployment conditions.

The TAIco framework, depicted in Figure 1, bridges the cognitive and sociocultural spheres. While the cognitive level of analysis is covered by the complementarity analysis described in this report and developed in WP1, the elements of the sociotechnical system are examined and shaped through the co-design activities of the project (in WP3 and WP4). As such, the sociotechnical conditions do not only provide the context for analysis of complementarity but are themselves subject to negotiation and further development. The project actively contributes to these developments by suggesting how the sociotechnical conditions can be shaped to lead to meaningful integration of AI in education.

1.1.2 The evolution of the TAIco framework through engagement with TAIco Cases

The TAIco framework is a central result of the project that is being continuously updated based on project results across all workpackages. Specifically, the framework is updated through systematic engagement with the TAIco Cases and the empirical studies conducted in those cases (see project deliverable D2.1).

Figure 2: Evolution of the TAIco framework

The **evolution of the framework** is depicted in Figure 2. **Version 1** contained a first description of the different dimensions and a glossary of the terms (see D2.1). An illustration of the framework using illustrative examples from the observational studies was published in the

conference proceedings of the European Conference on Technology-enhanced Learning (Ley et al. 2025).

Version 2 was used to conduct a qualitative cross-case analysis of complementarity and their conditions across all 7 TAICo cases and submitted for publication to the *Journal of Computer-Assisted Learning (Exploring Complementarity in the interaction of teachers and Artificial Intelligence: A cross-case analysis*, see also Appendix C).

The current version (**Version 3**), depicted in Figure 1, is contained in the previous section. The main changes in this version were the conceptual integration of the cognitive and sociocultural levels of analysis, as well as the formal and operational specification of tasks, skills and knowledge on which the current complementarity analysis is based. In the present deliverable, we go further and provide an initial characterisation of teacher-AI complementarity by specifying how tasks, skills, and knowledge relate within AI-enhanced pedagogical tasks. The complementarity analysis suggested in the current deliverable is illustrated by one of the TAICo cases (see chapter 4) and will be used for a formal analysis of complementarity across all TAICo cases to be reported in D1.2 (January 2027).

1.2 The initial Teacher-AI-complementarity model (TAICo model)

As part of the project's work on the TAICo framework described above, WP1 develops an **initial conceptual model** that focuses on the interaction between teachers and AI within pedagogical tasks. While the framework captures the broader sociotechnical ecosystem in which complementarity unfolds, the **Teacher-AI Complementarity model (TAICo model)** specifies how complementarity becomes observable at the level of pedagogical tasks.

When AI-supported tools are introduced into teaching practice, pedagogical tasks change. Actions are redistributed between teacher and tool, new actions appear, and existing actions may take on a different character. At the same time, the skills and knowledge teachers need also change: some existing skills are activated differently, new skill demands emerge (for instance, interpreting AI-generated output or calibrating trust in algorithmic suggestions), and the knowledge base teachers draw on expands to include understanding of what AI tools can and cannot do. The TAICo project addresses this question through the concept of teacher-AI complementarity.

Here, the aspect of complementarity that we focus on are the **configurations of how teachers and AI interact** at the level of tasks and skills, each contributing distinct yet interdependent actions, skills, and knowledge within pedagogical tasks. Complementarity thus does not refer to a fixed property of a tool or a teacher, nor is it reducible to a single label. Rather, it emerges when we analyse, at sufficient granularity, what actions are executed within a pedagogical task, who executes them, what dependencies exist between actors, and what skills and knowledge are required to perform those actions.

Understanding complementarity at this level of detail requires a structured analytical model. Without such a model, descriptions of teacher-AI interaction remain general (e.g., "the tool supports the teacher") and cannot be compared systematically across tools, tasks, or educational contexts. The TAICo model therefore conceptualises complementarity as an interaction configuration centred on a shared pedagogical task.

Figure 3 visualises this conceptualisation and, thus, further specifies the center of Figure 1. Complementarity is represented as the interaction between a teacher and an AI-supported tool within a shared pedagogical task. The pedagogical task is the shared object in which complementarity is taking form. Teacher actions and AI actions together shape what happens for the learner. The curved arrows illustrate the reciprocal coupling between the teacher and the AI through interaction: the output generated by one actor can function as input for the other, and that their respective actions may be initiated, shaped, or limited through these exchanges. The dashed arrows to the learner represent task dependencies through learner-related information and outcomes (for example learner data used by teacher and tool, and outputs directed toward the learner). On the teacher side, skills and knowledge are required to enact teacher actions; on the tool side, capabilities and AI design features enable or constrain tool actions. In this deliverable, the analytic focus lies on teacher-AI interaction, while learners remain conceptually part of the interaction system.

Figure 3: Interaction triangle representing the conceptual complementarity model

To characterise the teacher-AI interaction, we operationalise complementarity by means of three analytical components: Hierarchical Task Analysis to capture task level changes, Skill and Knowledge Analysis to understand skill level changes, and Complementarity Analysis to typify different complementarity configurations, which are described in detail in subsequent chapters.

The development of this model draws on the work conducted in T1.1 and T1.2 during the first project year. T1.1 identified task-level changes when teachers work with AI-supported tools, while T1.2 examined changes in the skills and knowledge required for teaching with AI. T1.3 integrates these insights into a coherent conceptual model through a combination of literature-based framing and empirical analysis. The present deliverable introduces this initial model, aiming towards a systematic application across TAICo cases. The model is illustrated using one of the TAICo cases, more specifically, Radboud University's case (RU case), and will be further applied and refined in D1.2.

Components of the complementarity model

To operationalise the conceptual model introduced above, WP1 develops a model to describe teacher-AI complementarity that is grounded in analyses of the TAICo cases and expressed in a shared notation. These components make complementarity observable and comparable across cases by linking task structure, skill demands, and interaction patterns within pedagogical tasks.

The core idea is that teacher-AI complementarity becomes observable when we describe, at sufficient granularity:

- (a) what actions are performed within a pedagogical task,
- (b) who performs which actions and what dependencies exist between actors, and
- (c) what skills and knowledge are required to perform those actions.

We therefore pursue the following three analytical components:

Component 1. Task decomposition through Hierarchical Task Analysis (HTA)

We use HTA to decompose a pedagogical task into subtasks and actions, including plans that specify the order of actions and conditions. This results in two pedagogical task diagrams: one representing the baseline teacher-only task (before the AI supported tool is introduced) and one representing the AI-supported task (after introduction of the AI supported tool). The purpose is to visualise task (re)configuration, including which actions are performed by the teacher and which by the AI-supported tool, and where teacher and AI-supported tool interact within the same pedagogical task. At the action level, we code the action state (existing or new).

Component 2. Skill and Knowledge Analysis (SKA)

Building on the HTA actions, we conduct Skill and Knowledge Analysis (SKA) to identify the cognitive skills, metacognitive skills, and knowledge or system resources required to perform a given action in the pedagogical task. The purpose is to make explicit which teacher skills remain central, which shift, and which new skill and knowledge demands emerge when AI is introduced into a pedagogical task. We also code the state of skills and knowledge to capture whether the required skills or knowledge are existing or new, relative to the baseline task.

Component 3. Complementarity Analysis (CA)

We integrate the task analysis and the Skill and Knowledge Analysis into a Complementarity Analysis (CA) resulting in a complementarity configuration. The purpose is to characterise complementarity to observable patterns across a subtask, using (a) task level action codes, (b) skill and knowledge codes, and (c) combined codes that connect action structure with skill indicators. Complementarity is therefore not treated as a single label at the level of a tool, teacher, or job. Instead, it is specified as a description of how teacher and AI interact within pedagogical tasks, grounded in observable subtasks. Hence, because each task will have multiple subtasks, there can be various complementarity configurations per task.

This operationalisation is not presented as a finished theoretical position. Rather, it represents the current stage of an iterative development process through this project. We are building our conceptualisation of teacher-AI complementarity through systematic analysis of cases in which teachers work with AI-supported tools in authentic educational settings. The present deliverable (D1.1) reports the intermediate step in this process: an initial operationalisation

of complementarity and its illustrative first application to a single case. The analysis is however based on our experiences analysing the observation cases at the task and skill level. As such, the deliverable should be read as an intermediate version; one that presents our current analytical approach and demonstrates its feasibility, while acknowledging that the conceptualisation will continue to evolve as we apply it to additional cases and refine the model iteratively. The analytical categories and coding schemes presented here are not yet checked across cases; we treat them as working tools that will be refined as the analysis is extended to the remaining five TAICo cases and consolidated in subsequent deliverables (D1.2, D1.3).

1.3 Contributions to the TAICo project

The purpose of the TAICo complementarity model is to understand how the introduction of a specific AI-supported tool changes teachers' pedagogical practices at the level of tasks, subtasks and actions, with a focus on teacher-AI interaction configurations. This specification allows us to typify **complementarity configurations** by tracing where information flows, where handoffs occur, and where checks and decisions occur within a subtask.

The SKA is reported as a complementary layer that specifies what these teacher-AI interactions require from teachers and the AI-supported tool, respectively, and helps translate findings into implications for teacher professional development (WP4) and design specifications (WP3) for AI-supported tools. In this way, the task-, skill-, and complementarity analyses provide concrete inputs for the broader TAICo framework, by identifying where teacher competences need to be strengthened and where AI tools should be redesigned or better scaffolded to support ethical, effective, and usable teacher-AI interaction in practice.

D1.1 contributes to the evaluation framework in **WP2** by providing conceptual and measurement foundations for designing validation studies in authentic settings. For **WP3**, the task-level analysis makes visible where and how AI design affordances become relevant in teaching pedagogical tasks, informing the design of tools and interfaces that support teacher-AI complementarity. For **WP4**, the Skill and Knowledge Analysis identifies where new or changing demands arise for teachers, providing inputs for the design of professional learning trajectories.

In this way, the outputs of D1.1 feed into several strands of the TAICo project. Within WP1, the initial model and analytical approach provide the foundation for D1.2, which will extend the task and skill analysis to multiple cases and report on how AI changes teacher tasks and skills across different educational contexts. The Hierarchical Task Analysis templates, skill coding schemes, and complementarity labels developed here will be applied and refined in that deliverable.

2. Theoretical Background

In this chapter, we describe the theoretical background that informed the way we approach the development of the complementarity model in this deliverable. Our starting points are two complementary theoretical lenses. First, through an economic lens, we draw on debates about how the rise of (generative) AI may reshape the teaching profession. This lens motivates why we analyse change at the task and skill level, because shifts in task content and skill demands are expected to accumulate into job level changes. Second, an education lens emphasises the role of sound pedagogical practice, grounded in teachers' professional knowledge and enacted through cognitive and metacognitive skills. This lens therefore informs how we characterise the knowledge and skills required to perform the actions identified in the task analysis. We then bring these two lenses together in a Complementarity Analysis. Specifically, we combine information about the state of tasks, the responsible actors, the required skills and knowledge, and the type of teacher AI interaction to characterise different forms of teacher AI complementarity across the TAICo cases.

2.1 Economic lens – from job level questions to task and skill level analysis

Job-level, replacement-focused perspective

In economics, AI impacts are often framed at the level of occupations, using estimates of automatability and bottleneck tasks (Lassébie & Quintini, 2022). Teaching is typically characterised by relatively low automatability and many bottlenecks that still require human input (Lassébie & Quintini, 2022). Even with renewed debates prompted by generative AI, the need for human control in education remains evident. Hence, unlike domains such as construction or farming where automation can substitute substantial parts of the pedagogical task, human AI complementarity is expected to be comparatively high in education, because teaching involves context sensitive pedagogical judgment and relational work, and because accountability for educational decisions ultimately remains with teachers and schools.

At the same time, job level estimates about automation are not well suited to explain how this complementarity takes form in everyday practice. They treat tasks and technologies as relatively static and depend strongly on deployment conditions, which can obscure how teachers and AI supported tools interact in concrete pedagogical tasks and why seemingly similar deployments play out differently across settings. These limitations suggest that job level analyses can miss where change actually occurs, reinforcing the need to examine teacher AI complementarity at the task and skill level. In fact, qualitative economic work suggests that beyond displacement, AI can also induce complementation and reinstatement effects (Lassébie & Quintini, 2022; Milanez, 2023). In this economic framing, complementation effects refer to AI increasing the value or productivity of human work by supporting tasks that people still perform, while reinstatement effects refer to AI enabling new or renewed tasks and roles for humans, creating additional work rather than simply replacing it. Accordingly, the aim of Deliverable 1.1 is to operationalise this task and skill level focus by developing and applying an approach that makes changes in teacher tasks and associated skill and knowledge demands visible across diverse educational contexts.

Task-level perspective: reconfiguration of tasks

Task-based approaches to technological change already argue that the key question is not whether jobs are automated, but how (bundles of) tasks are reorganised and recombined when new technologies are introduced (Acemoglu & Autor, 2011). Building on this, recent work in AI and education distinguishes between tasks that are effectively replaced by AI, tasks where AI and humans work in tandem, and tasks where AI expands what professionals can do by enabling qualitatively new practices or higher quality at scale (Molenaar, 2024).

Evidence across sectors supports this task-level view: AI adoption seldom results in full automation of occupations, but more often leads to partial automation, task reorganisation, and new forms of coordination shaped by local implementation and worker training (Milanez, 2023). For example, in education, AI could analyse student data and inform teachers about students that struggle with certain learning goals, or AI could provide feedback on exams. In education, empirical studies often examine narrow task fragments and proximate outcomes, such as time spent on specific teaching activities (Van Leeuwen et al., 2019), quality of lesson plans (Pishtari et al., 2023), or cognitive load (Pozdniakov et al., 2023). These approaches provide useful insights into local effects of AI support on specific activities and outcomes, but they make it difficult to see how entire pedagogical tasks are reconfigured when an AI supported tool is introduced. To capture this pedagogical task level change, we need a more granular representation of pedagogical tasks and their action structure. We address this using Hierarchical Task Analysis.

Hierarchical Task Analysis

Hierarchical Task Analysis is a task decomposition method that originated in domains such as process control and aviation and has more recently been applied in healthcare to describe complex work for design, training, and risk analysis (Annett, 2004; O'Connor & O'Dea, 2025; Stanton, 2006). Its sustained popularity rests on two features. First, HTA is highly flexible and can be applied to virtually any system. Astley and Stammers (1987) note that it has been used to characterise successive generations of technological systems since its inception. Second, HTA is methodologically versatile, supporting purposes such as task specification, identification of training needs, error prediction, assessment of team performance, and system design.

In TAICo, we apply HTA to the educational domain to represent pedagogical tasks, subtasks, and actions at a granularity where teachers interact with an AI supported tool (including its user interface, UI) and with learners. This enables analysis of complete pedagogical tasks rather than isolated tool features. At the same time, teacher work differs from many traditional HTA settings because teaching is relational and adaptive. The same curricular goal can be achieved through different subtasks depending on learners' needs, classroom dynamics, and local constraints. AI supported tools may further reconfigure these pedagogical tasks, but their role depends on how teachers use the tool and how it is configured within a school. As a result, similar tools can play different roles across settings.

This difference matters for how we use HTA. In many standard applications, HTA aims to document a single representative or agreed task structure to support safe and efficient performance. In TAICo, our focus is instead on how a pedagogical task is reconfigured between teachers and AI supported tools, and which new professional actions and associated skill and

knowledge demands emerge. Standard HTA does not explicitly represent who performs each action, how outputs are interpreted and acted upon, or how responsibilities shift across actors. Therefore, to support the Complementarity Analysis in this deliverable, we extend HTA with task level codes that capture action state (existing versus new), actor roles, and interaction structure within subtasks, making patterns of teacher AI complementarity observable and comparable across cases.

Implications for TAICo WP1:

For WP1, the implication of using HTA is that we do not start from job-level automation estimates. Instead, we model teacher AI complementarity from the ground up by mapping how an AI supported tool changes the configuration of actions within concrete pedagogical tasks in context. This task level mapping then feeds directly into the next step in Deliverable 1.1, the SKA, which specifies what the reconfigured task requires from teachers and what may shift, expand, or newly emerge when AI support is introduced.

2.2 Education lens – teachers’ professional skills and knowledge

Complementing the economic lens, the education lens provides an elaboration on the effects of AI specifically for teaching practice. Rather than focusing on jobs or tasks automated by technologies, this lens foregrounds teaching as a professional practice that is shaped by pedagogical goals, instructional contexts, and teachers’ situated actions as supported by AI.

Across international and national teacher competence frameworks for digital and AI-enhanced teaching (e.g., UNESCO ICT Competency Framework for Teachers, 2022; UNESCO AI Competency Framework for Teachers, Miao & Cukurova, 2024; European DigCompEdu, Redecker & Punie 2017; OECD Teaching Compass, 2025) there is broad consensus that teaching with AI requires more than technical knowledge enabling teachers to work with AI. Across frameworks, emphasis is placed on the integration of pedagogical, ethical, and professional skills and knowledge that allow teachers to meaningfully and responsibly embed digital and AI technologies into instructional practice. Rather than engaging in a detailed comparison of these frameworks, we treat them as a shared background that motivates a closer examination of how such skills are enacted and how the related knowledge is applied in concrete teaching situations.

Teacher competence

When modelling teacher-AI complementarity, teacher competence frameworks must be taken into account, as these conceptualise the prerequisites needed to act professionally in complex instructional contexts. These frameworks form the theoretical basis for identifying skill and knowledge requirements and provide anchors for support mechanisms to inform the design of teacher professional development as well as AI design (relevant for WP3 and WP4) in AI-enhanced educational contexts.

Teacher competencies, defined as context-specific cognitive dispositions enabling individuals to successfully cope with domain-related demands (Klieme and Leutner, 2006), cannot be reduced to static knowledge elements. Across different frameworks, teacher competencies are commonly conceptualized as a multifaceted construct encompassing cognitive and motivational prerequisites as well as metacognitive and self-regulatory conditions (Lachner et al., 2024). In other words, competencies are a necessary prerequisite for teachers to carry out actions and complete tasks. The COACTIV competence model proposed by Baumert and

Kunter (2011), places an emphasis on professional knowledge, while motivational orientations, professional beliefs, and self-regulatory skills are acknowledged but receive less attention. While the COACTIV model primarily conceptualizes professional competence as a set of relatively stable teacher competencies, more recent models place a stronger emphasis on teachers' actual enactment in real teaching situations. For instance, Blömeke's competence as a continuum model (2015) takes into account the knowledge aspect, yet conceptualizes teacher professional competence as a continuum linking to cognitive situation-specific skills (noticing, interpreting, decision-making) and observable performance in practice. This aligns with our task-focused approach to describe how teacher and AI interact within pedagogical tasks, grounded in observable subtasks.

To clarify the relationship between competence, knowledge, and skill in the context of TAICo, we follow these established competence models that conceptualise the constructs of knowledge and skill as functionally interrelated within the umbrella term of competence. Professional knowledge represents a central cognitive resource for instructional action, while skills, in turn, describe the processes through which this knowledge is enacted in concrete situations. In this sense, knowledge constitutes an enabling condition, while skills operationalise knowledge in action.

In TAICo we follow this notion focusing on the specific goals and pedagogical tasks to examine the process tracing of enactment. Focusing on the process character of competence is particularly relevant to understand changing instructional situations due to the use of AI supported tools.

Professional knowledge as prerequisite

Within competence-oriented models, professional knowledge constitutes a central enabling resource for teachers' competent action, particularly in instructional contexts shaped by digitalisation and AI. While competence cannot be reduced to knowledge alone, knowledge provides the conceptual and informational basis that allows teachers to perceive situations meaningfully, interpret them in pedagogically relevant ways, and make informed decisions in practice. Particularly in teaching and learning environments influenced by digitalisation and AI, knowledge is an enabling resource for effective teaching. Knowledge frameworks, including Pedagogical Content Knowledge (Shulman, 1986), DPACK (Huer et al., 2019) and TPACK (Mishra & Koehler, 2006), as well as more recent AI-related extensions such as Intelligent-TPACK (Celik, 2023) and **AI-PACK** (Lorenz & Romeike, 2023), conceptualise professional knowledge as an integrated system linking content, pedagogy, and technology. These models underline that teaching with AI requires an understanding of both subject matter and pedagogy, as well as knowledge of how AI systems function and their respective affordances and limitations, and how they reshape instructional processes (e.g., Ning et al., 2024). These recent models stress that digitalisation involves qualitative transformations of teaching and learning processes. This shift from technology use to instructional transformation is particularly pertinent in AI-enhanced settings, where tools do not merely support existing practices but actively intervene in instructional decision-making, where it requires AI-specific technological knowledge to design, evaluate, and adapt digital learning environments in alignment with pedagogical goals and educational values. In line, a scoping review conducted by WP4 indicates that skills and knowledge related to pedagogical judgement, self-regulation, and context-sensitive decision-making are currently less addressed in many current professional development programmes (see D4.1, Training framework for AI implementation in professional settings).

For the TAICo model, these knowledge models serve as conceptual resources for identifying what teachers need to know in order to enact AI-supported pedagogical tasks. Knowledge becomes analytically relevant insofar as it is activated through applying cognitive and metacognitive skills in concrete task contexts. This perspective aligns with Blömeke's competence as continuum model (2015) and supports the task- and pedagogical task-based analysis of teacher-AI interaction.

Cognitive skills in teacher-AI interaction

Building on professional knowledge as an enabling resource, cognitive skills, understood as mental abilities that allow humans to process, understand, and use information, describe how this knowledge is enacted in concrete pedagogical tasks (Singley & Anderson, 1989). Competence models that emphasise performance converge on the view that knowledge becomes instructionally relevant through situation-specific processes of perception, interpretation, and decision-making, which are often discussed under the concept of professional vision or noticing (Goodwin, 1994; van Es & Sherin, 2002). These skills govern how teachers **perceive** and attend to relevant information or cues in instructional situations, **interpret** them aligning to pedagogical goals, and **decide** on appropriate actions. In AI-supported environments, these situation-specific skills shape how teachers engage with system outputs, such as analytics, recommendations or generated content. AI tools can amplify, redirect, or constrain what is perceived as salient, thereby reshaping processes of interpretation and decision-making within ongoing pedagogical tasks. Rather than constituting generic cognitive abilities, situation-specific skills are task- and context-specific and closely tied to concrete instructional actions (Kaiser et al., 2017). Therefore, we focus on perceive, interpret, and decide, and treat them as central analytical categories in the skill analysis. They capture how teachers connect professional knowledge with AI-mediated information to act within pedagogical tasks and provide a task-level basis for analysing teacher-AI interaction.

Self-regulatory and metacognitive skills

Complementing situation-specific cognitive skills, metacognitive skills regulate how teachers plan, monitor, and adapt these processes of perceiving, interpreting, and making decisions over time (Pintrich, 2000, 2004; Schraw & Dennison, 1994; Zimmerman, 2000, 2002). They are particularly relevant for conceptualising teacher-AI interaction as an iterative and adaptive process rather than a sequence of isolated actions. By enabling teachers to monitor their own cognitive processes and regulate their information processing and decision-making, these skills support continuous revision and reflection on their teaching (Peeters et al., 2014; Schraw et al., 2006). This becomes particularly salient in AI-supported classrooms, where AI may take over particular subtasks or actions while teachers engage with and integrate AI-generated information into ongoing decision-making within instructional pedagogical tasks.

Implications for TAICo WP1:

In D1.1, we adopt a practice-oriented understanding of competence and analyse teacher-AI interaction in relation to pedagogical goals and observable teaching practices in which teachers and AI systems jointly contribute to pedagogical tasks. By attending to teachers' practices, we can systematically link observed actions to the cognitive and metacognitive skills, and professional knowledge required to perform them, while acknowledging the complexity of teaching. To operationalise this perspective, WP1 combines HTA with SKA to

identify which actions are performed, how pedagogical tasks change when AI is introduced, and which new or shifting skill and knowledge requirements emerge for teachers. This focus on **new or changing requirements**, rather than on teacher competence in general, allows us to characterise teacher-AI interaction patterns at the level of subtasks and provides a foundation for subsequent analyses and design-oriented work in later work packages.

Skill and Knowledge Analysis

We use a Skill and Knowledge Analysis (SKA) as a preparatory step to analyze teacher-AI complementarity. In this analysis, we distinguish between the teachers' professional knowledge and cognitive and metacognitive skills, following the approach of Baumert & Kunter (2011) and Blömeke et al. (2015). This distinction is primarily analytical and serves to operationalise teacher-AI complementarity in a systematic and observable way. These skill and knowledge requirements will then be mapped onto the task structures identified in the Hierarchical Task Analysis. As we focus on teacher-AI complementarity in TAICo we consider not only teachers' cognitive and metacognitive skills, but also the respective functional capabilities of AI systems that contribute to the teacher-AI interaction. This does not imply that AI possesses skills in the human sense; rather, AI capabilities are conceptualised as system functions grounded in data processing, pattern recognition, and algorithmic procedures that enable the execution of specific task-related actions. From an AI-centric perspective, a taxonomy of AI tasks are broadly proposed as recognition/event detection, forecasting, intelligent user interfaces, goal-driven optimisation, and reasoning with knowledge structures (OECD, 2022), which can be operationalized in educational settings. To further specify this taxonomy, we draw on the detect-diagnose-act (DDA) framework proposed by Molenaar (2022). The DDA framework conceptualises AI capabilities in education as a sequence of (1) detecting relevant data from the learning environment, (2) diagnosing states or processes based on these data, and (3) acting upon this diagnosis through feedback, visualisations, or adaptive interventions.

By distinguishing between skills (on the teacher side), capabilities (on the AI side), and knowledge or system resources, we can specify the concrete prerequisites required to perform specific actions and whether these prerequisites reside on the human side, the AI side, or emerge through their interaction within a task. For instance, when the action involves evaluating AI-generated suggestions (e.g., dashboard recommendations), the teacher requires AI-specific knowledge to oversee the dashboard with the suggestions, perceive and interpret relevant information, as well as the ability to judge the information and decide on further actions. This approach allows us to analyse complementarity from the demands of the instructional activities in which teachers engage with AI tools in the TAICo Cases.

The differentiated coding of skills/capabilities and knowledge/system resources is not intended to directly determine the complementarity. For the description of complementarity itself, the decisive factor is how teacher and AI contributions are connected across a subtask, rather than whether an action relies on a specific skill, capability, knowledge element, or system resources. Accordingly, the distinction between skills/capabilities and knowledge/system resources mainly provides contextual information about who is able to perform which actions and under which conditions. However, this differentiation becomes essential in subsequent analytic steps we aim to perform in the next phases of the TAICo project. It enables later assessments of proficiency, validation of assumed complementarities, and evaluations of the quality of task execution by making transparent whether actors possess

the required skills, capabilities, knowledge, or system resources to perform their respective actions. In this sense, the SKA functions as a necessary preparatory layer that supports later validation and proficiency-oriented analyses, rather than as a direct determinant of the Complementarity Analysis performed as the third component of the TAICo model.

2.3 From tasks and skills to complementarity

The task and skill components provide the building blocks for a Complementarity Analysis. The goal of this analysis is not to evaluate tools in general, but to characterise patterns of teacher-AI interaction within pedagogical tasks in a way that can be traced back to observable pedagogical tasks and their skill and knowledge demands. Thus, we do not treat complementarity as a single label at the level of a job, task or skills. Instead, we assign labels at the level of subtasks within tasks.

HTA makes the pedagogical task explicit by specifying tasks, subtasks, and actions and by showing where the teacher and the AI supported tool are both involved. The SKA then specifies what is required to perform those actions. The Complementarity Analysis then integrates task level action codes with skill and knowledge indicators at the level of a subtask and describes what these elements mean together for different forms of teacher-AI complementarity in practice. Conceptually, we position this analysis using the categories replacement, complementarity, and augmentation, which distinguish different ways of integrating AI into educational practice (Molenaar, 2025; Cukurova, 2025).

Replacement

Replacement refers to configurations in which an AI supported tool substitutes a teacher task or skill, often associated with higher degrees of automation and reduced teacher involvement in the execution of that part of the pedagogical task (Cukurova, 2025). Molenaar (2025) further distinguishes between partial and full replacement. Partial replacement is more common and occurs when the tool automates specific actions without fundamentally changing the overall task. One example is automated feedback on task correctness, where the tool provides immediate feedback while the teacher remains responsible for pedagogical interpretation, such as diagnosing misconceptions or deciding on next steps. In these cases, the core teaching practice remains largely the same, but some actions are taken over by technological support. Full replacement refers to cases where the tool performs an entire pedagogical task with minimal substantive teacher involvement, such as providing instruction or generating and selecting learning materials. In education, full replacement appears to be relatively rare and is typically confined to narrowly defined contexts (Molenaar, 2025). For instance, intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) can replace a teacher when helping students practice without additional support from teachers (VanLehn, 2011).

Complementarity

Rather than by a clear division of tasks, complementarity is characterised by interdependence, where AI takes on actions that enrich teachers' work without fully automating it. This implies that the same instructional task is carried out, but in greater depth, enabled by AI-driven data processing and analysis (Molenaar, 2025). Similarly, Cukurova (2025) conceptualises complementarity as a configuration in which AI functions provide active support. This increases teachers' capacity while maintaining high teacher agency and a relatively low degree of automation. Teachers remain actively involved, using AI outputs to update their mental models of learners and learning processes. Within this configuration, Cukurova further distinguishes multiple levels of teacher-AI teaming (e.g., transactional, situational, operational and praxical), which specify how teachers and AI exchange information and coordinate actions, while describing the affordances of AI systems that can affect the boundaries of possible teacher-AI interaction. Across these levels, AI systems do not fully take over tasks but support teachers in perceiving, interpreting, and acting on complex classroom information.

From this perspective, complementarity refers to configurations in which the AI supported tool does not replace the teacher but contributes actions and outputs that the teacher must interpret, evaluate, or use to make progress in the pedagogical task. In this sense, complementarity is defined by bidirectionality of information flow between teacher and AI within a task. The teacher and the AI supported tool each contribute distinct actions to the same overarching pedagogical task, and task completion depends on how these contributions connect across a subtask. A common pattern is that the AI supported tool processes information at scale, for example by analysing learner data and producing indicators or suggestions, while the teacher remains responsible for sense making and pedagogical judgement, such as diagnosing needs, deciding next steps, and regulating the process (e.g., Yang et al., 2023). Complementarity is therefore not a single teacher-AI interaction type. It can take multiple forms within the same task, yet serve the same pedagogical goals, depending on where information flows, handoffs, output checks, and decision points across different subtasks.

Augmentation

Augmentation refers to configurations in which the introduction of an AI supported tool enables pedagogical work that was not previously feasible or scalable within the pedagogical task (Molenaar, 2025; Cukurova, 2025). In this configuration, teacher-AI interaction does not only support existing actions, but introduces new actions, new pathways, or new decision points in the pedagogical task. Molenaar (2025) describes augmentation as a configuration in which the combination of teacher and AI enables new forms of instruction or orchestration that neither could realise alone. Cukurova (2025) further emphasises that such configurations can be iterative and developmental over time, with teachers using tool outputs as evidence for refinement and the tool adapting to teacher goals and strategies. Cukurova refers to this configuration as synergistic teacher-AI teaming, characterised by mutual questioning, negotiation, and evidence-based reasoning. Here, outcomes emerge that go beyond the capabilities of either teachers or AI in isolation. Augmentation thus aligns most strongly with the concept of hybrid intelligence, in which human and artificial intelligence form a tightly coupled system aimed at achieving qualitatively new forms of educational practice. In WP1, augmentation is therefore treated as a specific subset of complementarity that is indicated by

observable pedagogical task change, such as new work demands and or iterative refinement cycles within a subtask.

In WP1, these categories serve as a theoretical lens for interpreting observed task (re)configurations in the attempt to characterize the teacher-AI interactions occurring in any given action sequence within a subtask by assigning a corresponding complementarity label to it. However, we do not assume that any single category applies to an entire tool or case. Instead, the categories are made operational through subtask level labels that are derived from coded pedagogical tasks and linked skill and knowledge indicators. The next chapter describes the method for each component of our TAICo model in order: first, how HTA is performed to represent tasks, subtasks, and actions, then how SKA is conducted per action, and finally how complementarity labels are assigned using explicit if-then rules at the level of subtasks.

3. Method

To formalise teacher-AI complementarity, WP1 developed a three-component analytical approach through an iterative, case-driven process. The approach was informed by existing literature on task analysis, teacher professional skills, and AI in education, and was progressively refined through empirical application to the TAICo cases. First, we model each pedagogical task using Hierarchical Task Analysis (HTA), producing both a teacher-only task configuration and an AI-supported task configuration. Second, building on the action level of the HTA, we code the cognitive skills, metacognitive skills, and knowledge requirements involved. Third, we combine task-level and skill-level codes at the level of subtasks to describe complementarity configurations. Each component was developed through cycles of literature review, empirical observation, initial coding, and revision based on expert teacher feedback. The following sections describe each component, its rationale, and the general procedure for applying the analysis. Throughout, we use a running example of a case study that we describe here first.

Description of the case used as running example: RU Curriculum adaptivity case

In the RU Curriculum Adaptivity case, primary school teachers use Snappet Copilot, an AI supported feature in the Snappet platform's teacher facing dashboard, to support lesson planning and differentiation. In mathematics, a single learning goal can be addressed through multiple lesson types: an instruction lesson, an independent practice lesson, a review lesson, and an enrichment lesson. A review lesson revisits an earlier learning goal when a student has not yet achieved the learning objectives for that goal. The HTA in this case focuses specifically on planning a differentiated review lesson and therefore covers the planning phase only.

During planning, the teacher uses the Snappet user interface to review the 'standard' current planning (Figure 4A), relate it to the annual curriculum planning (Figure 4B), and examine class and student progress toward relevant learning goals (Figure 4C), drawing on platform data, classroom observations, or both.

Copilot then generates suggestions for teachers, including lesson objectives and proposed student groupings for differentiation. For example, Copilot may assign some students to the review lesson, while others are assigned to independent practice or enrichment. Students assigned to independent practice can choose a learning goal that fits their progress level, reflecting curriculum adaptivity: students' progress through the curriculum at different rates, so some work on a prior learning goal (review), while others move ahead to a later learning

goal (new instruction, practice, or enrichment). The teacher reviews these student grouping suggestions and either accepts them directly or iteratively checks class or student status in the student and class dashboards, adjusts groupings where needed, and then finalises and schedules the differentiated lesson. Below, we show the relevant Snappet UI screens used to carry out this task and refer to these screens in the remainder of the text to support comprehension.

A) Screen 1: Overview of the four-week math planning, where each day is linked to a specific learning objective aligned with a broader learning goal. Blank days indicate built in flexibility for differentiation and therefore form the focus of our analysis.

B) Screen 2: Overview of the annual math curriculum, displaying the complete set of mathematics learning goals for the school year.

C) Screen 3: Student progress view for a specific learning goal, showing how individual learners are currently performing against that goal.

Figure 4: RU case Curriculum Adaptivity: Snappet tool interface.

Note: The student initials in screen 3 are fabricated for privacy purposes.

3.1 Hierarchical Task Analysis in Teaching Practice

The following chapter first outlines standard HTA concepts and procedures, then describes the adaptations we developed in WP1 to characterise pedagogical tasks in contexts where teachers work with AI-supported tools, and finally presents the task-level coding scheme used to make actor roles, task change, and interaction structure explicit and comparable across cases.

Core concepts in HTA

We use standard HTA terminology and apply it to teaching, as summarised in Table 1. A **task** is the top-level unit in the hierarchy and is formulated as a pedagogical or didactic outcome (e.g., "schedule a differentiated review lesson"). **Subtasks** denote intermediate outcomes that contribute directly to achieving the task; they break a pedagogical task into educationally meaningful steps (e.g., "analyse student performance" or "select a learning objective"). **Actions** are the smallest units of behaviour: what an actor actually does or observes, written as concrete steps in verb-object form. **Plans** specify the order in which subtasks or actions are carried out and include what happens under different conditions. **Conditions** are the situational cues, rules, or requirements that determine which branch of a plan is followed (e.g., "if large gaps between students are detected, return to the analysis step before proceeding"). Figure 5 illustrates the HTA task structure before the introduction of the AI in the tool (Panel A) and after the introduction of the AI in the tool (Panel B), including subtasks, actions, plans, and conditions.

Table 1. Terminology used in HTA

Term	Short definition	How we use it in TAICo
Task	Highest level of unit of work. A pedagogical task is a pedagogical-instructional teaching activity that consists of subtasks and actions that jointly achieve the task.	Describes a pedagogical task, for example "Prepare a differentiated math lesson". When we say "task analysis" we mean analysing how this task is realised.
Subtask	A subtask is a lower-level unit of work within a larger task.	Breaks a pedagogical task into educationally meaningful steps, for example "Select topic" or "Analyse student performance".
Action	An action is the lowest level unit of work within a larger task, written as a verb-object.	Concrete teacher, AI, or educational technology tool behaviours, for example "Open the dashboard" or "Suggest grouping".
Plan	A description that specifies the order in which subtasks or actions are carried out, including what happens under different conditions.	Describes pedagogical task logic, for example "Do 1, then 2, then 3. If large gaps between students are detected in 2, return to 1 before continuing."
Condition	A situational cue, rule, or requirement that determines which branch of a plan is followed.	The "If large gaps between students are detected in 2" part of the plan.

HTA procedure

There is no single agreed approach to performing HTA (Stanton, 2006). Here, we describe broad HTA heuristics described by Stanton (2006) and Annett (2004), applied within a structured seven-step format proposed by O'Connor and O'Dea (2025) for practical implementation. For each step, we first describe the general procedure and then illustrate it with a running example from the TAICo case on curriculum adaptivity (see the Radboud University's case (RU case) description in chapter 5).

Table 2.

Summary of the steps to conduct a HTA.

Step	Explanation
Step 1. Define the task and purpose	Identify the pedagogical task, user population and the intended end purpose of the HTA.
Step 2. Identify the boundaries of the HTA	The start point, end point and scope of the HTA should be established.
Step 3. Gather information from multiple sources	Source of information can include a combination of sources such as a literature review, observations, think alouds and interviews.
Step 4. Establish the level of detail and stopping point	Obtain consensus on the level of detail and granularity of the HTA.
Step 5. Specify plans and conditions	Outline the conditions under which subtasks and actions are executed, and guide the order and selection of subtasks and actions (i.e. the plan).
Step 6. Draft the diagrams with task structure and action list	Develop a hierarchy of subtasks and concrete actions that are required to complete the task.
Step 7. Refine the HTA with expert teachers and iterate	The HTA should be reviewed by independent experts to ensure the HTA represents "a correct" way, or ways, of performing a pedagogical practice.

Step 1: Define the purpose and task

The first step is to establish the **purpose** of the HTA and then to define the **task** that will be analysed. Both decisions shape every subsequent step, including the level of detail, the actors represented, and the type of comparison that the HTA will support.

Defining the purpose. The purpose specifies what the HTA will be used for. Different purposes lead to different analytical choices. Three elements should be considered when shaping the purpose:

(1) **The intended use of the analysis.** In education, an HTA can serve several functions: for example, supporting teacher learning about how to carry out a practice, supporting evaluation or assessment of a practice, or identifying how a practice is reconfigured when an AI-supported tool is introduced. In WP1, the purpose is to analyse how the introduction of an AI-supported tool reconfigures the distribution of actions between teachers and AI within a pedagogical task.

(2) **The type of comparison required.** The purpose determines whether a single HTA is sufficient or whether paired HTAs are needed. Because the D1.1 purpose requires visibility into task-changes, we construct paired HTAs: one for the teacher-only task (without the AI component) and one for the AI-supported task.

(3) **The intended end users.** It is important to consider from the beginning who will read and use the HTA (Stanton, 2006). In WP1, the primary end users are the researchers conducting the CA. However, the HTAs are also intended to be understandable to teachers and tool designers who participate in validation workshops and contribute to later project phases. Defining the end users early helps ensure a stable and appropriately detailed representation.

Defining the task. With the purpose established, the analyst defines the pedagogical task to be analysed. The following criteria guide this decision:

(1) **Recognisable unit of teacher work.** The task should correspond to a pedagogical or didactic outcome that teachers would recognise as a coherent unit of their professional practice (e.g., "schedule a differentiated review lesson," "design an assessment," "provide feedback on student writing").

(2) **Clear outcome formulation.** The task should be formulated as an outcome rather than an activity. "Analyse student data" is an activity that could be part of several tasks; "schedule a differentiated review lesson" is an outcome-oriented task that provides a clear endpoint.

(3) **AI relevance.** The task should be chosen at a level of granularity where the AI-supported tool plays a meaningful role, that is, where the introduction of the tool visibly changes how the teacher works. If the AI-supported tool only affects a small fragment of a much larger task, it may be more productive to define the task at a narrower scope. Conversely, if the tool affects an entire workflow, the task can be defined more broadly.

(4) **Scope.** The task should include all steps that the teacher and the AI-supported tool perform to achieve the stated outcome but should not extend into follow-up activities that serve a different pedagogical purpose (these are handled in Step 2, boundary setting).

Running example. In the RU curriculum adaptivity case, the **purpose** is to make visible where and how the AI-supported tool changes the action structure of this pedagogical task. The teacher-only version describes how teachers perform this task without the AI component; the AI-supported version describes the task as performed with the AI-supported dashboard. Comparing the two makes task changes explicit at the level of individual actions. The **task** is "schedule a differentiated review lesson". It is a recognisable unit of teacher work in primary mathematics education, formulated as an outcome, and the AI-supported dashboard (Snappet Copilot) plays a meaningful role throughout by providing suggestions for 1) learning goals, and 2) student groupings.

Step 2: Identify the boundaries of the HTA

Clear boundaries must be established by specifying where the task starts and ends, which actors and tools are included, and what falls outside the scope. In HTA, boundary setting is guided by three interrelated considerations drawn from standard task analysis methodology (Annett, 2004; Stanton, 2006).

First, the analyst defines the **system boundary**: what falls inside the analysis and what falls outside. The system boundary follows from the purpose and task definition. First, everything that contributes to achieving the stated task outcome is inside the boundary; activities that serve a different pedagogical purpose are outside it and may be analysed in a separate HTA. In WP1, the system boundary includes the teacher, the AI-supported tool (both its AI component and its user interface), and any artefacts or information sources that are directly used during the task. Contextual factors that influence the task (e.g., school policy, curriculum constraints) can be noted as background conditions but are not decomposed into actions within the HTA.

Second, the analyst specifies **trigger and terminal events** that mark where the task begins and ends (Annett, 2004; Stanton, 2006). In standard HTA, a trigger event is an identifiable cue or action that initiates the task, and a terminal event is an observable state or action that signals the task outcome has been achieved. In teaching, these should correspond to recognisable transitions in the teacher's workflow. A trigger event might be opening a tool, receiving a notification, or beginning a planning session. A terminal event might be saving a decision, completing a schedule, or handing off to instruction. Specifying these events prevents the HTA from expanding indefinitely and ensures that the analysis has a defined scope.

Third, the analyst determines the **actor scope**: which agents are represented in the HTA. In WP1, both the teacher and the AI-supported tool are always included, because the purpose of the analysis requires visibility into how actions are distributed between them. Other actors (e.g., students, co-teachers) are included only when they directly participate in the action subtask of the task being analysed.

Boundary decisions should be documented and treated as revisable. If subsequent data collection (Step 3) reveals that important actions fall outside the initial boundaries, for example because teachers consistently describe preparatory or follow-up steps as integral to the task, the boundaries can be adjusted in later iterations.

Running example. In the AI-supported version of the RU case, the trigger event is the teacher opening the AI-supported dashboard to begin lesson planning. The terminal event is the teacher scheduling the differentiated lesson and confirming the grouping. Follow-up work, such as preparing differentiated instructional materials and delivering the lesson, falls outside the system boundary and is treated as a separate task with its own HTA. The actor scope includes the teacher and the Snappet Copilot tool (both its AI component and its user interface).

Step 3: Gather information from multiple sources

To construct a robust HTA, it is recommended to use more than one information source (Diaper & Stanton, 2004; Stanton, 2006). For teaching practices, we typically combine: (1) literature review, (2) observations, and (3) interviews or think alouds with subject matter experts (teachers). Literature review can inform us of existing theoretical conceptualisations of the tasks and existing empirical insights about the execution. Observations of expert practice help to understand expert execution of the task that occurs in live classrooms, video records, or simulated sessions. When feasible, teachers are asked to think aloud while working with or without the AI tool, which makes visible not only what they do, but also the considerations that later can be translated into subtasks, plans, and conditions. Interviews

with experienced teachers or tool specialists can further clarify how the practice is performed and which contextual conditions shape decisions (e.g., time constraints). Including less experienced teachers can also be informative, because it helps identify task structures that may need attention in skill analysis.

Because different teachers may carry out the same pedagogical task in somewhat different ways, the information gathered across sources and informants is synthesised into a consolidated HTA that captures the common structure of the task while representing key decision points where variation occurs. Where teachers consistently describe different routes through the task (e.g., accepting an AI suggestion versus overriding it), these are represented as conditional branches in the plan rather than as separate HTAs. When differences are more fundamental, for instance when teachers use the AI features in a tool versus teachers who do not use AI at all, separate HTAs may be warranted.

Running example. In the RU case, the purpose is to make visible where and how the AI-supported tool changes the action structure of the task "schedule a differentiated math lesson." To inform both the teacher-only and the AI-supported HTA, we conducted interviews and think-alouds with 19 teachers using the Snappet Copilot tool, which served as the primary empirical basis for identifying the concrete task structure. This resulted in different task configurations. Yet, we report on one consolidated task configuration here for simplicity: the one with most teacher-AI interactions.

Step 4: Establish the level of detail and stopping point

Deciding how much detail is required is important and often difficult. A common guideline is the $P \times C$ stopping rule, which suggests stopping decomposition when the product of the probability (P) of failure and the cost (C) of failure is acceptably low, indicating negligible risk (Stanton, 2006). For example, in our example above (Figure 5B, subtask 2.2 "Evaluate differentiation suggestions") – If the teacher does not trust the AI fully, they may need to perform extra actions in order to check the data the AI is basing their decision on. In education, estimating probability and cost can be challenging. A pragmatic approach is therefore to present a draft HTA to intended users (teachers) and ask where they need more or less specification. End users are well positioned to judge appropriate granularity and to flag where detail is excessive or insufficient.

Step 5: Specify plans and conditions

Plans define the control structure of the HTA: plans describe sequence plus conditions. Plans are specified for subtasks where sequencing or branching needs to be made explicit (Stanton, 2006). A plan is specified for the overarching pedagogical task and for each subtask (unless the subtask only has one action). Plans guide the order and selection of subtasks and actions, and they articulate the conditions under which particular branches are triggered (Stanton, 2006).

Running example: In Table 13, we describe a plan for each task and subtask to make branching logic and decision points explicit. For example, if we look at plan 2; if the teacher is not happy with the AI suggestion (condition), they may perform extra actions until they are satisfied.

Step 6: Draft the diagrams: teacher-only and AI-supported

We use a standard HTA box-and-line diagram to represent the task hierarchy visually (Annett, 2004; Stanton, 2006). In this notation, each task, subtask, and action is represented as a labelled box. The top-level task appears at the top of the diagram and is connected by vertical lines to its subtasks, which in turn connect to lower-level subtasks or actions. The result is a tree structure that reads from top to bottom, with increasing levels of detail at each level. Numbered labels (e.g., 1, 1.1, 1.1.1) indicate the position of each element in the hierarchy.

We make two diagrams: one that visualizes the task configuration before the introduction of an AI tool (teacher-only), and one after the introduction of an AI supported tool. Because standard HTA diagrams do not natively encode who performs each action or the direction of information flow, **we add visual conventions to the diagram to represent TAICo-specific coding dimensions (see Table 3 for an overview) that are applied to the AI-supported diagrams only:**

(1) Colour coding for primary actor. Each action box is filled with a colour that indicates the primary actor: blue for Teacher, orange for AI. This makes the distribution of work visible at a glance across the diagram.

(2) Border coding for action state. The border style and colour of each action box encode an additional dimension. A dotted border indicates that the action is new (not present in the teacher-only HTA), while a solid border indicates an existing action.

(3) Directionality of interaction annotations. For actions involving a secondary actor, a short label (e.g., AI->T, T->AI) is added to indicate the direction of information flow. This keeps directionality traceable at the action level without altering the hierarchical structure of the diagram.

This approach retains the simplicity and readability of the classic HTA notation, which is familiar to researchers in human factors and ergonomics, while layering on the additional visual codes needed for the TAICo Complementarity Analysis.

Running example. In the RU case, the task "schedule a differentiated math lesson" was represented as a standard HTA box-and-line diagram (Figure 5). The top-level task was decomposed into two main subtasks: selecting and scheduling a math lesson and associated learning objective (subtask 1), and choosing a grouping (subtask 2). Each subtask was further decomposed into action boxes written in verb-object form, such as "open the block planning in tool," "Suggest a learning objective," and "Adjust AI differentiation suggestion." Action boxes were colour-filled to indicate the primary actor (blue for teacher, orange for AI). Plans were specified in the accompanying table that includes all tasks and actions (e.g., "Do 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4, 1.5 in order. At 1.4.4, do either 1.4.4a or 1.4.4b". Table 13). Both a teacher-only diagram (Figure 5A) and an AI-supported diagram (Figure 5B) were drafted to allow direct comparison.

Link to the Figure in high resolution: [Figure 5](#)

Figure 5: A) Teacher-only and B) AI-supported decomposition (HTA diagram) of the pedagogical task in RU case Curriculum Adaptivity.

Step 7. Refine the HTA with expert teachers and iterate

Each HTA should be reviewed with expert teachers who are experienced in the practice. The purpose of this review is to obtain feedback, correct inaccuracies, and ensure the HTA fits the local context, including curriculum, school policies, and the configuration of the AI-supported tool in use. The goal is not to enforce one canonical task structure, but to check that each HTA represents a reasonable, safe, and pedagogically sound way of carrying out the practice. Because different teachers may carry out the same pedagogical task in different ways, this approach naturally supports documenting diverse uses of the same AI-supported tool across tasks and contexts.

Iteration and versioning

HTA is a flexible, iterative method. In WP1, each analysis is revised across cycles as observations, teacher interviews, and evidence of actual AI use refine goals, subtasks, plans, and conditions. More complex practices involving multiple actors or multiple AI components typically require more iterations than simpler practices. We treat each HTA as a living document, sometimes maintaining multiple HTAs for the same task to represent different, pedagogically appropriate tool use. We log changes with dates, analysts, and data sources so the analyses remain comparable across cases and reusable as both research outputs and professional learning or design artefacts (Stanton, 2006; Annett, 2004).

Table 3. Overview of TAICo task-level coding dimensions.

Coding dimension	Codes	HTA level	Explanation
1. Action state	Existing, New	Action	By comparing the AI supported HTA to a baseline teacher only HTA, each action is coded as existing (already part of the practice) or new (introduced by AI supported work). We indicate this by either no border (existing) or a dotted border (new). <i>Note: only apply this to the AI-supported HTA.</i>
2. Primary actor (colored)	Teacher, AI, Student	Action	Each action is tagged with the primary actor in color. This makes the division of labor explicit. Blue represents the teacher as the primary actor while yellow represents the AI as primary actor and green represents the students.
3. Directionality of the interaction with a secondary actor	T→UI UI→T AI→T T→AI none	Action	It defines initiator versus output actor of the information flow. T = Teacher, AI = AI component of tool, UI = User interface. We distinguish between AI components of the tool and UI components of the tool. This distinction is important because AI-supported tools combine standard UI elements (e.g., navigation menus, input fields, static dashboards) with AI-driven features (e.g., algorithmically generated suggestions, automated analytics). Distinguishing the two makes visible where in the task the AI component actually reconfigures teacher work, rather than treating all tool use as equivalent.

3.2 Skill and Knowledge Analysis

As was already explained above, the HTA identifies the actions that teachers and AI perform within a task. Based on the new actions performed by a teacher or an AI system, we identify cognitive and metacognitive demands as well as knowledge requirements on the action level in the SKA. We code cognitive as well as metacognitive skills and regulatory capabilities, knowledge, and their state (existing or new), respectively, to distinguish skill-related and knowledge-related changes. In this analysis, we distinguish between human abilities, understood as cognitive and metacognitive skills, and professional knowledge grounded in situated judgment and experience, and AI abilities, conceptualised as system capabilities based on data processing, pattern recognition, and algorithmic decision procedures. Table 4 gives an overview of the coding dimensions of the SKA. The following table (Table 5) illustrates how the coding results are represented.

Table 4. Coding dimensions of Skill and Knowledge Analysis.

Step	For Teachers:	For AI:
Code 1:	Cognitive skills	Respective AI capabilities
Code 2:	Metacognitive skills	Regulatory capabilities
Code 3:	Knowledge	System resources
Code 4:	State	State

Table 5. Template for coding.

ID of the action	New Teacher/AI action	Cognitive skills	Respective AI capabilities	Metacognitive skills	Regulatory capabilities	Knowledge/system resources to perform an action	State Aggregation
		Teacher	AI	Teacher	AI		

Code 1: Teacher cognitive skills and AI capabilities

Based on the actor coding of the HTA, we code whether the teacher or the AI covers cognitive skills/capabilities at the action level. As we focus on teacher-AI complementarity in TAICo we consider not only teachers' cognitive skills, but also the respective capabilities on the AI side.

On the **teacher's** side, cognitive skills that relate to instructional actions involve - following the Blömeke model (2015) - situation-specific cognitive processes of perceiving, interpreting, and deciding (PID). **Perceive** refers to teachers' selective attention to relevant events in the instructional setting, **interpret** captures the process of making sense of these perceived classroom activities and **decide** either involves anticipating appropriate responses or considering alternative instructional strategies based on the situation (Kaiser et al., 2015). Additionally, we explicitly distinguish between cognitive processing and enactment. To capture performance-observable behaviours (Blömeke, 2015), we code teacher **act** when the teacher enacts an instructional or pedagogical action in the classroom or learning environment. This extension reflects that teaching does not end with decision-making but includes the execution of pedagogical actions, such as adapting, intervening or orchestrating. Table 6.1 provides an overview of the codes for teachers' cognitive skills.

Table 6.1. Overview of teacher cognitive skills coding.

Coding dimension: Cognitive skills			
Code	Definition	Explanation/ Example	Coding Rule
Perceive	Selective attention to relevant events, cues, or information in the instructional situation without explicit evaluation or inference.	The teacher notices that several students hesitate before responding or observes that a student repeatedly skips steps in a solution.	Code when the teacher attends to, observes, or becomes aware of relevant classroom information. Do not code if the teacher explains, evaluates, or infers meaning from the observation (→ Interpret).
Interpret	Sense-making process in which perceived classroom information is evaluated, explained, or linked to pedagogical, didactical, or content-related knowledge.	The teacher concludes that hesitation indicates conceptual misunderstanding and interprets skipped steps as a lack of procedural fluency.	Code when the teacher attributes meaning, evaluates significance, or connects observations to professional knowledge. Do not code if no evaluative inference is made (→ Perceive) or if a concrete response option is selected (→ Decide).
Decide	Selection or anticipation of an instructional course of action based on prior interpretation of the situation, without yet executing the action.	The teacher decides to revisit the concept using a visual representation and plans to form a small support group.	Code when the teacher selects or formulates a response strategy but has not yet enacted it. Do not code if the action is enacted (→ Act).
Act	Enactment of a pedagogical or didactical action that directly modifies the instructional or learning environment.	The teacher provides additional explanations and assigns differentiated tasks, as well as reorganises student groups.	Code when the teacher executes an instructional action that produces a concrete change in the learning environment. Do not code when the action remains planned or hypothetical (→ Decide).
If multiple cognitive skills occur, code all that directly characterizes the action's instructional function.			

On the **AI** side, corresponding capabilities are coded following the DDA framework (detect-diagnose-act) by Molenaar (Molenaar et al., 2021; Molenaar, 2022; Tabuenca et al., 2021). In this view, the DDA functions are seen as corresponding to teachers' situation-specific skills such as professional noticing (Van Es & Sherin, 2021) and decision-making, which guide teachers' navigation of classroom situations (König et al., 2022). **Detect** aligns with perceive, taking into account student data that AI systems use to observe learners and the learning context. For example, a system not only detects learning progression, but also attention parameters or affective states such as idleness or engagement. **Diagnose** refers to the algorithms that infer current states and likely development, similar to teachers' interpret. **Act** refers to the pedagogical-didactic responses based on those diagnoses, which could be seen as decide; either by informing users (for example, via dashboards) or by adapting tasks, feedback, or curriculum (Baker, 2021; Bodily et al., 2018; Jivet et al., 2018; VanLehn, 2011). Therefore, we propose extending the DDA framework to DDIA (detect-diagnose-inform-act) to further distinguish between **inform** (which may also mean that the AI suggests or recommends) and **act** in the sense of enacting. In this distinction, **inform** refers to cases in which the AI outputs information, feedback, or recommendations that require interpretation or further decision-making by the teacher, whereas **act** refers to cases in which the AI autonomously executes an instructional step or directly changes the learning environment without requiring an intermediate teacher decision (e.g., automatically assigning a new task or adapting task difficulty). This distinction mirrors the shift from decision-support to execution within the PID and DDA frameworks, and allows us to differentiate between AI contributions that inform cognition and decision-making, and those that constitute operative interventions in the workflow. Table 6.2 provides an overview of the respective capability coding for AI.

Table 6.2. Overview of AI capabilities coding.

Coding dimension: Respective AI capabilities			
Code	Definition	Explanation/ Example	Coding Rule
Detect	Computational identification or collection of learner- or context-related data used to register states, behaviours, or events within the learning environment.	The system records response accuracy, time-on-task, clickstream data, or engagement indicators.	Code when the AI system captures, registers, or monitors input data. Do not code when the system infers meaning from the data (→ Diagnose).
Diagnose	Algorithmic inference of learner states, performance levels, progress, or predicted development based on detected data.	The system infers that a learner has not mastered fraction comparison. The system predicts risk of failure based on performance patterns.	Code when the AI interprets detected data to generate an evaluative or predictive conclusion. Do not code when the system only displays raw data (→ Detect) or outputs recommendations (→ Inform).
Inform	System-generated communication of diagnostic results, feedback, or recommendations to an actor that requires interpretation or decision-making before action is taken.	The dashboard highlights students at risk and recommends reviewing a certain topic. The AI suggests assigning additional practice.	Code when the AI outputs information, feedback, or recommendations but does not autonomously modify the learning environment. Do not code if the system directly changes tasks, feedback, or sequencing (→ Act).
Act	Autonomous execution of an instructional or task-related modification that directly alters the learning environment without requiring an intermediate decision of the teacher	The system automatically assigns a new task and adapts task difficulty. The curriculum sequence is changed automatically.	Code when the AI independently implements an instructional change. Do not code when the change is only suggested to a teacher (→ Inform).

If multiple AI capabilities occur, code all that directly characterizes the action’s instructional function.

By explicitly coding teacher actions alongside perceive, interpret, and decide, and by differentiating inform and act on the AI side, the coding scheme allows us to distinguish between decision-making and enactment for both actors. Enactment describes a change in the instructional or learning environment, for instance, adaptations, interventions, or task modifications that directly affect learners or the learning process (e.g., adjusting tasks,

providing feedback, reorganising activities, or automatically adapting content), whereas act refers to pedagogical enactment of a decision in practice or system-initiated changes that are executed without requiring further human mediation. The use of comparable functional categories for humans and AI allows us to see how responsibilities for perceiving, interpreting, deciding and acting are redistributed in teacher-AI configurations. It additionally makes the DDA scheme easy to align with frameworks on teacher competence and professional development, including situation-specific skills and self-regulated learning that also distinguish between categories such as perceiving, sense-making, and responding.

Code 2: Teacher metacognitive skills and AI regulatory capabilities

Metacognitive skills are commonly defined as the capacity to monitor and regulate one's own cognitive processes, with oneself as the referent of cognition (Cox, 2005, Flavell, 1979). More specifically, they refer to the ability of regulating one's own tasks through planning, monitoring and evaluating (Kluwe, 1987; Jacobs & Paris, 1987). As we observe task completion, we look at how **teachers** regulate themselves in the process.

Planning includes selection of strategies such as goal setting and allocation of resources that affect the primary actor's task performance. Setting goals includes working towards a self-set standard and defining when the plan is reached. **Monitoring** refers to awareness of comprehension and task performance. It includes perceiving the progress on the plan and interpreting if it moves towards the self-set goals. **Evaluating** refers to appraising products including re-analysing one's goal and completion state (Schraw & Moshmann, 1995), for instance by checking if chosen actions were performed correctly and judging if they were helpful for reaching the plan.

Metacognitive skills draw on the availability, types and quality of the cognitive knowledge resources that an actor can access and apply, such as domain-related content knowledge (CK) as well as AI-specific technological knowledge (AI-TK). Teachers will have difficulties engaging in effective planning if only little CK is available. For instance, if a teacher wants to make a decision based on a teacher dashboard output, metacognitive planning requires the teacher to anticipate whether they possess sufficient understanding of the displayed indicators to interpret them meaningfully. A teacher may recognise uncertainty about how a specific visualisation is generated and deliberately decide to consult additional information. Metacognitive processing lies not in interpreting the dashboard itself, but in monitoring one's own understanding of the dashboard output and regulating subsequent action accordingly. Similarly, if for example an AI system lacks an adequate representation of pedagogical goals, it may generate suggestions that are poorly aligned with the instructional situation. Planning, monitoring, and evaluating are therefore constrained by the extent to which the actor can draw on knowledge or internal system resources to interpret the information it processes meaningfully. Table 7.1 provides an overview of the codes for teachers' metacognitive skills.

Table 7. 1. Overview of teacher metacognitive skills coding.

Coding dimension: Metacognitive skills			
Code	Definition	Explanation/ Example	Coding Rule
MC_ Planning	Anticipatory regulation of one’s own instructional or task-related cognitive processes through goal setting, strategy selection, and resource allocation prior to task execution.	The teacher sets a goal for how to use dashboard data in the lesson and allocates time to analyse the data before deciding on instructional steps. The teacher selects a strategy for integrating AI feedback.	Code when the teacher regulates their own upcoming task performance by setting goals, selecting strategies, or allocating cognitive or temporal resources. Do not code when the teacher selects an instructional response to students (→ Decide, cognitive level).
MC_ Monitoring	Ongoing awareness and tracking of one’s own comprehension, strategy use, performance progress, or alignment with self-set goals during task execution.	The teacher checks whether their own interpretation of dashboard data is correct and reflects on whether the chosen strategy is working. The teacher notices confusion in their own reasoning about AI output.	Code when the teacher attends to and tracks their own cognitive processes or progress toward self-set goals. Monitoring refers to regulating one’s own cognition. Do not code when the teacher observes AI or students (→ Perceive, cognitive level).
MC_ Evaluating	Reflective appraisal of one’s own decisions, strategies, performance outcomes, or goal attainment after or during task completion, potentially leading to adaptation.	The teacher evaluates whether their instructional adjustment based on AI output was effective and judges whether their interpretation of system feedback was accurate. The teacher reassesses whether their initial goal was appropriate.	Code when the teacher evaluates the quality, effectiveness, or correctness of their own cognitive or instructional processes. Do not code when evaluation refers to AI output or students’ performance only (→ Interpret, cognitive level).

Whereas teachers’ metacognitive processes are coded as such, AI-related adaptive loops are conceptualised as regulatory capabilities rather than metacognition. This avoids anthropomorphic attributions while still capturing dynamic feedback mechanisms within AI systems without prematurely attributing reflective capacities to AI. Unlike teachers, the **AI** system does not reflect on its own reasoning processes in a metacognitive sense. Instead, any adjustments occur at the level of algorithmic updating or parameter optimisation, for example when teacher feedback leads to recalibration of model weights or decision thresholds. These adaptive loops constitute forms of regulatory capabilities rather than metacognitive

reflection. It is yet an open question whether and to what extent a capability to reflect and regulate one's own reasoning processes exists in AI. While artificial systems may implement monitoring and control mechanisms, they do so without justifying their own reasoning processes, raising uncertainty on whether such regulatory capabilities constitute genuine metacognitive reflection (Cox, 2005; Dignum, 2019). However, AI-supported tools may exhibit regulation loops at the system level, for instance, teacher input can function as implicit or explicit feedback to the AI; for instance, when teachers adapt, confirm, reject, or override AI-generated suggestions. By doing so, such interactions may trigger adjustments in system parameters. There are examples with AI incorporating teachers' feedback preferences over time (e.g., Pereira et al., 2023). In our coding we denote these adaptive mechanisms as forms of regulatory capabilities. To reflect this distinction in the coding scheme, metacognitive codes are explicitly marked with the prefix "MC" and applied only to teacher actions. For AI actions, the same functional processes of planning, monitoring and evaluating are coded without a metacognitive designation.

Table 7. 2. Overview of AI regulatory capabilities coding.

Coding dimension: Regulatory capabilities			
Code	Definition	Explanation/ Example	Coding Rule
Planning	System-internal configuration of goals, thresholds, or control parameters that structures subsequent system operations.	The system sets thresholds for adaptivity based on predefined models.	Code when the AI establishes operational parameters guiding its subsequent processing.
Monitoring	Ongoing tracking of system performance, model accuracy, or user interaction data to adjust internal states.	The system tracks prediction error rates or logs teacher overrides.	Code when the AI continuously tracks internal or external variables for adjustment purposes.
Evaluating	System-level performance assessment resulting in parameter updating or model revision.	The system updates prediction weights based on feedback. The AI adjusts recommendation models after teacher corrections.	Code when the AI modifies internal parameters based on performance data. This constitutes algorithmic adaptation.

By introducing a distinct coding layer for metacognitive skills, the scheme extends the analysis of cognitive skills beyond instructional actions toward the regulation of those actions. While Code 1 captures how cognitive responsibilities for perceiving, interpreting, deciding, and acting are distributed between teachers and AI systems, Code 2 makes visible how teachers regulate their own cognition within these processes. In doing so, the coding of metacognitive skills differentiates between what actors do at the action level and how teachers regulate their engagement with these actions. Planning, monitoring, and evaluating are thus conceptualised as regulatory processes that operate on teachers' own understanding, strategy use, and goal

setting. This distinction is particularly relevant in AI-supported settings, where dashboard outputs, algorithmic suggestions, or automated adaptations may shape instructional decision-making. The coding scheme enables us to identify whether teachers merely interpret system information (cognitive processing) or whether they additionally monitor their own understanding of that information and regulate their subsequent actions accordingly (metacognitive processing).

Code 3: Required knowledge/system resources to perform an action

Apart from the required cognitive and metacognitive skills, knowledge as an enabling resource must be available to act adequately. We code which type of knowledge is needed for each specific action. Knowledge is conceptualized here as a prerequisite resource that enables an actor, teacher or AI, to execute an action, not as knowledge provided by the system or acquired as a consequence of interaction.

For **teachers**, knowledge codes refer to the AI-TPACK framework (Ning et al., 2024). This framework distinguishes between pedagogical, content-related, AI-specific-technological, and integrated forms of knowledge. The AI-specific knowledge aspects are only coded when the teacher's action explicitly involves interpreting, evaluating, selecting, or adapting AI-generated output. For example, when a teacher evaluates AI suggestions based on class status and curriculum objectives, they need an understanding of 1) how the AI generates the lesson objective suggestions and 2) how these relate to classroom data. Therefore, the corresponding teacher action requires both AI-specific technological understanding of the system (AI-TK) and judgment of its outputs (AI-TCK). If the action can be done independently of the AI, no AI-specific knowledge is coded, for example when a teacher chooses a lesson objective themselves from planning. Since the AI-TPACK encompasses knowledge aspects related to a concrete situation, we add contextual knowledge (XK) to capture what teachers consider when making meaningful decisions (Mishra, 2019). Table 8.1 provides an overview of the codes used to describe teachers' required knowledge to perform an action.

Table 8.1. Knowledge coding.

Coding dimension: Knowledge		
Code	Definition	Coding Rule
Content knowledge (CK)	Knowledge applied by teachers when delivering instruction in specific subject domains, such as mathematics or scientific knowledge.	Code when the action requires subject-matter expertise independent of pedagogy or AI functionality.
Pedagogical knowledge (PK)	Knowledge pertaining to the pedagogical process, methodologies, and practices comprised the formulation of instructional plans, the selection of teaching methods, classroom management strategies, assessment of student behavior, and academic performance, among other aspects.	Code when the action relies on general instructional strategies independent of specific subject content or AI-specific understanding.

Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK)	The knowledge required to select appropriate teaching methods and strategies designed to suit specific instructional content also includes the ability to reconfigure and present information to improve pedagogical outcomes.	Code when the action involves adapting specific content for instructional purposes.
AI-Technological Knowledge (AI-TK)	Teachers understanding and application of available AI technologies. This consists of the comprehension and familiarity of visible and tangible AI platforms, tools, products, and educational resources. It also includes adopting a pedagogical approach to using AI in educational contexts, such as fostering its literacy.	Code when the action requires understanding AI system functionality or output generation.
AI-Technological Content Knowledge (AI-TCK)	Teachers use AI to provide learners with highly immersive and interactive learning experiences that suit individual knowledge levels, cognitive states, and learning preferences.	Code when judgment is required regarding AI-generated content representations or adaptivity.
AI-Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (AI-TPK)	Dynamic understanding of how the use of AI transforms the teaching and learning processes. This understanding includes recognizing the mutual support, provisioning, and constraints between AI technologies and pedagogy, as well as being able to design effective teaching strategies and activities accordingly.	Code when the action and further pedagogical instruction depends on understanding AI affordances and constraints.
Contextual knowledge (XK)	Knowledge of contextual constraints and affordances, including institutional policies, infrastructural conditions, curricular standards, student demographics, and sociocultural factors shaping instructional action.	Code when the action requires contextual knowledge, including all information/ data a teacher takes into account.

For **AI**, codes describe system resources, implemented for instance via rules or models, that must be available in order to perform an action. Rather than referring to knowledge in a cognitive sense, these codes capture the technical and informational prerequisites that enable the AI to execute an action at a given point in time. This includes access to external resources (EXT), embedded models (M), explicitly encoded rules or decision logic (R), patterns learned from training data (T), and internal system representations of the current state (SR). These codes refer to internal system resources that enable the AI to detect, diagnose, or act, and are treated as functional equivalents to human knowledge without implying metacognition, understanding or awareness on the part of the system. Accordingly, AI knowledge coding does not describe how data is processed over time or how the system learns or updates but specifies which system resources must be available for the action to be possible.

For example, when an AI generates suggestions for student grouping, the action may require access to an embedded student model (M), predefined grouping rules (R), and internal representations of learners' current states (SR) to generate the suggestions. Table 8.2 provides an overview of the required system resources for AI.

Table 8.2. System resources coding.

Coding dimension: System resources		
Code	Definition	Coding Rule
Embedded models (M)	Internal computational models representing learners, content structures, or instructional goals and transforming inputs into classifications, predictions, or recommendations (e.g. student models or clustering models).	Code when action depends on internal model-based inference, transforming inputs into classifications, predictions, or recommendations (e.g. student models or clustering models).
Rules (R)	Programmed decision logic or rule-based mechanisms governing system behavior.	Code when action follows predefined rules, constraints, or decision logic.
Training data (T)	Statistical parameters or representations learned from training data enabling predictive or adaptive functions.	Code when action presupposes patterns learned from training data that are necessary for generating the output (e.g. language models, classifiers).
System representations (SR)	Internal representation of current learner, system, or environmental state.	Code when action depends on state tracking (e.g. learner states or task representations).
External resources (EXT)	External information that is not stored within the system's internal models or state representations.	Code when performing the action requires additional resources (e.g. teacher input or databases).

By coding knowledge/system resources the SKA moves beyond what actors do (cognitive skills) and how they regulate their actions (metacognitive skills) to specify which knowledge/system resources must be available for these actions to be performed. This addresses the requirements arising from the integration of AI and the associated changes in skills and knowledge. Linking actions systematically to their enabling knowledge or system resources provides a conceptual anchor for examining the epistemic and technical foundations of performance.

Code 4: State

The state coding captures whether the skills/capabilities and knowledge/system resources required to perform an action represent a change relative to the preceding task configuration.

The code is designed to be applicable across multiple time points (e.g., T0: without AI, T1: after AI introduction, T2: after 6 months of implementation). The reference point for determining whether something is existing (E) or new (N) is therefore not a fixed baseline (e.g., "pre-AI

practice”), but the preceding practice or functional capability of task enactment at a given point in time, respectively. Accordingly, what is coded as new at one point in time may become existing at a later point in time once it has been stabilized, become a routine, or be embedded in system functionality.

For each action, identified via HTA and analyzed in SKA, Codes 1-3 (skills/capabilities and knowledge/system resources of the primary actor) are first coded separately. This differentiation is necessary because AI integration may introduce new knowledge demands: actions may rely on established skills but require extended knowledge. For instance, teachers may already possess the skill of perceiving relevant cues from the classroom and interpreting them, but perceiving and interpreting AI-generated alerts may require new AI-specific knowledge to judge them and decide on further action. Coding both dimensions separately preserves this analytical distinction before assigning an aggregated action-level state that collapses across them.

The code **Existing (E)** is used, if the action relies on cognitive and metacognitive skills/capabilities as well as knowledge/system resources that were already part of the preceding HTA. For teachers, this means that existing cognitive or metacognitive skills (e.g., perceiving relevant cues, interpreting student understanding, deciding on next steps) can be applied without transformation in their mode of enactment. For AI, this means that previously implemented functional capabilities (e.g., rule-based grouping, scoring correctness) can operate without extension or restructuring.

The code **New (N)** is used, if the action requires skills/ capabilities and/or knowledge/system resources that emerge specifically through the teacher-AI interaction introducing a qualitative change relative to the preceding HTA. Such change may occur as an extension of an existing skill/capability (e.g., interpreting AI-mediated student data requiring additional AI-specific knowledge), as a transformation in how a skill is enacted (e.g., shifting from intuitive classroom perception to data-mediated interpretation), or as an introduction of a previously unnecessary skill/capability (e.g., new reflective and regulatory metacognitive skills regarding algorithmic input or deciding on automation boundaries). Table 9.1 provides an overview of the state coding for skills/capabilities and knowledge/system resources.

Table 9.1. Overview of skills/capabilities and knowledge/system resources state coding.

Coding dimension	Codes	Explanation
Skill / capability state	Existing (E)	Code E when the required skill/capability is enacted in a comparable form to the preceding HTA and does not involve a qualitative change in scope, coordination, or functional demand.
	New (N)	Code N when the action requires a qualitatively new form of cognitive, metacognitive, or functional capability (e.g., regulating AI outputs, meta-decisions about automation boundaries) relative to the preceding HTA.

Knowledge/ system resources state	Existing (E)	Code E when the required professional knowledge/system resources are used in a comparable way to the preceding HTA and do not involve expansion.
	New (N)	Code N when the action requires additional, extended, or qualitatively different knowledge/ system resources, for instance for understanding, interpreting, or operationalizing data.

In a second step, the dimension-level codes are aggregated to a single action-level state. Four aggregated state codes are distinguished. An action is coded as **Existing (E)** when it relies exclusively on existing skills/capabilities and existing knowledge/system resources. An action is coded as **New knowledge/system-resource-driven (N-K)** when the required skills/capabilities remain existing, but the action depends on new or extended knowledge or system resources. An action is coded as **New skill/capability-driven (N-S)** when at least one required skill/capability introduces a change, regardless of whether the underlying knowledge or system resources remain stable. Finally, an action is coded as **New combined (N-C)** when both skills/capabilities and knowledge/system resources combined include new elements. This aggregation ensures that each action can be characterized with one state code while still retaining information about where novelty is located. An action is coded as new whenever either skills/capabilities or knowledge/system resources introduce new requirements that are decisive for action execution. Only actions that rely exclusively on existing skills/capabilities and existing knowledge/system resources are coded as existing. Table 9.2. shows the codes for assigning an aggregated action-level state.

Table 9.2. Overview of aggregated action-level coding.

Skill/ capability	Knowledge/ data	Action-level state	Explanation
E	E	E	Code <i>existing</i> (E), when the action relies on existing skills/capabilities and existing knowledge/system resources only.
E	N	N-K	Code <i>new knowledge/system-resource-driven</i> (N-K), when the skills/capabilities are existing, but the action requires new or extended knowledge/system resources.
N	E	N-S	Code <i>new skill/ capability-driven</i> (N-S), when at least one new skill/capability is required for the action, together with the use of existing knowledge/system resources.
N	N	N-C	Code <i>new combined</i> (N-C), when both, new skills/capabilities and new knowledge/system resources, are required for the action.

3.3 Preliminary Complementarity Analysis (CA)

Our proposed Complementarity Analysis (CA) integrates the HTA action coding and the SKA coding at the level of **subtasks** defined as ordered sets of actions that jointly contribute to the completion of a specific task. We choose this approach, because complementarity between teachers and AI can't be inferred from isolated actions, but becomes visible through the distribution of actions, skills and knowledge within subtasks. In a subtask we can describe how actions are connected, how information flows between actors, and how cognitive and regulatory responsibilities are distributed. Therefore, we take these as the unit of analysis.

In our analysis, we derive a set of **subtask-level variables** from the underlying HTA and skill codes for each subtask in which AI is newly included as a primary or secondary actor (see in Table 10).

To capture changes in task execution and skill and knowledge distribution due to the use of AI-supported tools, two indicators are derived. **NEW_WORK_ACTION** is set to true when at least one action within a subtask is coded as new in the HTA, indicating a change in task structure and including AI as a primary actor for actions. **NEW_SKILL_KNOWLEDGE** is set to true when at least one action in the subtask requires new skills or knowledge. **NEW_WORK** is set to true only when both conditions are met within the same subtask. This indicates that AI involvement is accompanied by a skill and knowledge-related change rather than a purely structural redistribution of actions. This coding makes complementarity visible in the distribution of tasks and skills and allows various configurations of complementarity to be described.

Based on the SKA codes, we derive subtask indicators for teacher cognition and AI capabilities. For teachers, codes capture whether the subtasks involve perceive, interpret, decide, and act as well as metacognitive processes such as planning, monitoring, and evaluating. For the AI, corresponding codes capture detect, diagnose, inform, and act, as well as AI-internal planning, monitoring, and evaluating processes.

Table 10.1. Subtask level variables derived from HTA and skill codes.

HTA codes		
We analyze a subtask when AI is included as a primary or secondary actor.		
NEW_WORK_ACTION	=	TRUE
IF any action in the subtask has: Action state = New; Otherwise = FALSE		

Skill codes	
Skill codes combine the actor codes from the HTA with skill codes.	
NEW_SKILL_KNOWLEDGE = TRUE IF any action in the subtask has: Aggregated state = New; Otherwise = FALSE	
Teacher related codes	AI related codes
T_PERCEIVE = TRUE IF any Teacher-primary action in the subtask has Cognitive = Perceive; Otherwise = FALSE	AI_DETECT = TRUE IF any AI-primary action in the subtask has Cognitive = Detect; Otherwise = FALSE
T_INTERPRET = TRUE IF any Teacher-primary action in the subtask has Cognitive = Interpret; Otherwise = FALSE	AI_DIAGNOSE = TRUE IF any AI-primary action in the subtask has Cognitive = Diagnose; Otherwise = FALSE
T_DECIDE = TRUE IF any Teacher-primary action in the subtask has Cognitive = Decide; Otherwise = FALSE	AI_INFORM = TRUE IF any AI-primary action in the subtask has Cognitive = Inform; Otherwise = FALSE
T_ACT = TRUE IF any Teacher-primary action in the subtask has Cognitive = Act; Otherwise = FALSE	AI_ACT = TRUE IF any AI-primary action in the subtask has Cognitive = Act; Otherwise = FALSE
T_MC_PLANNING = TRUE IF any Teacher-primary action in the subtask has Metacognitive = Planning; Otherwise = FALSE	AI_PLANNING = TRUE IF any AI-primary action in the subtask has Metacognitive = Planning; Otherwise = FALSE
T_MC_MONITORING = TRUE IF any Teacher-primary action in the subtask has Metacognitive = Monitoring; Otherwise = FALSE	AI_MONITORING = TRUE IF any AI-primary action in the subtask has Metacognitive = Monitoring; Otherwise = FALSE
T_MC_EVALUATING = TRUE IF any Teacher-primary action in the subtask has Metacognitive = Evaluating; Otherwise = FALSE	AI_EVALUATING = TRUE IF any AI-primary action in the subtask has Metacognitive = Evaluating; Otherwise = FALSE

In addition, codes are derived to capture decision authority (which actor performs the final decision-related action) of the subtask (i.e. **T_DECISION_END** and **AI_DECISION_END**, respectively). **T_INPUT** and **AI_INPUT** indicate the direction of information flow, that is, which actor receives input to the other actor. **T_OUTPUT** and **AI_OUTPUT**, in contrast, indicate that an actor generates output that affects the subsequent actions of the other actor or is directed to the students.

While these codes describe each actor's contributions and exchanges, they do not yet capture how actions are functionally connected across the subtask. Therefore, based on these codes, preliminary combined codes are constructed to represent properties of coordination, such as regulation and interdependence. **Regulation** refers to the active adjustment of the joint teacher-AI interaction process. It describes subtasks in which one actor controls the unfolding interaction process across multiple steps, including cycles of perceiving and interpreting the other actor's output, monitoring and evaluating one's intermediate states, and deciding how to act on the other actors' contributions. Importantly, this notion of regulation goes beyond metacognitive self-regulation and regulatory capabilities (as captured by the codes in the SKA). Rather, regulation here concerns the control that one actor exerts over a process that involves the other actor's contributions. Therefore, **T_REGULATE** is set to true when the subtask contains teacher perception, interpretation, metacognitive evaluating, decision-making, and generating an output, indicating active regulation of the process by the teacher. While metacognitive codes reflect the teacher's monitoring and evaluation of their own cognition, **T_REGULATE** captures whether the teacher can actively engage with the AI output. In this sense, **T_REGULATE** indicates that the teacher does not merely respond to AI input but exerts control by shaping subsequent actions through decision and output. **AI_REGULATE** is defined analogously for AI systems, capturing cases in which the AI detects, diagnoses, evaluates, acts, and produces output within the same subtask. Therefore, both **REGULATE** codes refer to the other actor, not to self-directed/ system-regulatory processes.

Interdependence refers to configurations in a subtask, in which subsequent actions depend on reciprocal contributions from the teacher and AI, rather than on a unidirectional delegation or handoff. **BIDIRECTIONAL_EXCHANGE** is set to true when both teacher-to-AI and AI-to-teacher exchanges occur within the subtask, as conceptualising through the presence of teacher and AI inputs and outputs, indicating mutual dependence rather than a one-way handoff. **ITERATION** is used when the subtask contains repeated cycles of output and response, reflecting iterative coordination across actors.

These codes allow us to determine whether AI merely automates a subtask, provides informational support for teacher decisions, or participates in a genuinely reciprocal configuration of action.

Table 10.2. Combined codes derived from subtask level variables.

Combined codes (HTA + Skill) = subtask level variables	
Derived for CA	
<p>NEW_WORK = TRUE IF NEW_WORK_ACTION = TRUE AND NEW_SKILL_KNOWLEDGE = TRUE; Otherwise = FALSE</p>	
Teacher related codes	AI related codes
<p>T_DECISION_END = TRUE IF the teacher takes the final decision of the subtask: Primary actor = Teacher AND T_DECIDE = TRUE AND T_ACT = TRUE; Otherwise = FALSE</p> <p>T_INPUT = TRUE = teacher receives input IF any action in the subtask has: Primary actor = Teacher AND Directionality of the interaction = [any actor] → T AND T_PERCEIVE = TRUE AND T_INTERPRET = TRUE; Otherwise = FALSE</p> <p>T_OUTPUT = TRUE = teacher sends output IF any action in the subtask has: Primary actor = Teacher AND Directionality of the interaction = T → [any actor] AND T_ACT = TRUE; Otherwise = FALSE</p>	<p>AI_DECISION_END = TRUE IF the final action of the subtask has: Primary actor = AI AND T_DECIDE = FALSE AND T_OUTPUT = FALSE AND AI_ACT = TRUE; Otherwise = FALSE</p> <p>AI_INPUT = TRUE = AI receives input IF any action in the subtask has: Primary actor = AI AND Directionality of the interaction = [any actor] → AI AND AI_DETECT = TRUE AND AI_DIAGNOSE = TRUE; Otherwise = FALSE</p> <p>AI_OUTPUT = TRUE = AI sends output IF any action in the subtask has: Primary actor = AI AND Directionality of the interaction = AI → [any actor] AND AI_INFORM = TRUE or AI_ACT = TRUE; Otherwise = FALSE</p>
<p>T_REGULATE = TRUE IF AI_OUTPUT = TRUE AND T_PERCEIVE = TRUE AND T_INTERPRET = TRUE AND T_MC_MONITORING = TRUE AND T_MC_EVALUATING = TRUE AND T_DECIDE = TRUE AND T_OUTPUT = TRUE; Otherwise = FALSE</p>	<p>AI_REGULATE = TRUE IF T_OUTPUT = TRUE AND AI_DETECT = TRUE AND AI_DIAGNOSE = TRUE AND AI_MONITORING = TRUE AND AI_EVALUATING = TRUE AND AI_ACT = TRUE AND AI_OUTPUT = TRUE; Otherwise = FALSE</p>

BIDIRECTIONAL_EXCHANGE = **TRUE**

IF AI_OUTPUT = TRUE AND T_INPUT = TRUE AND T_OUTPUT = TRUE AND AI_INPUT = TRUE
[in any order]; Otherwise = FALSE

ITERATION = **TRUE**

Use ITERATION only when the subtask contains repeated cycles of output and response, as
indicated by repeated alternation of AI_OUTPUT and teacher response actions within the
same subtask; Otherwise = FALSE

This aggregated coding enables the concrete specification of **if-then rules** for complementarity conditions through the assignment of complementarity labels. Table 11 shows two examples, which are intended to illustrate how the procedure works and to clarify the underlying logic of our operationalization of complementarity. The focus is therefore on making transparent how complementarity can be systematically derived from the coded action subtasks, skills, and knowledge distributions. The specific labeling rules presented here should not be understood as fixed or exhaustive. Rather, they represent a current working version that remains open to refinement. As the coding scheme will be further refined and tested, additional labels may be introduced and existing rules may be specified in greater detail.

For instance, we assign the label replacement (example 1) when AI output is present but there is no observable teacher decision within that subtask. Complementarity (example 2) is assigned when there are repeated cycles of output and response between teacher and AI within the same subtask. The final decision can be made either by the teacher or by the AI. Iteration is assigned when bidirectional exchange is present, indicating interdependence rather than a one way handoff. Table 11 shows two examples for labeling complementarity.

Table 11. Examples for complementarity labeling.

Exam ples	Required inputs	IF conditions	THEN output LABEL	Notes
E 1	AI_DETECT, AI_DIAGNOSE, AI_ACT, AI_OUTPUT, T_DECIDE, T_OUTPUT, T_DECISION_END	AI_DETECT = TRUE AND AI_DIAGNOSE = TRUE AND AI_ACT = TRUE AND AI_OUTPUT = TRUE AND T_DECIDE = FALSE AND T_OUTPUT = FALSE AND T_DECISION_END = FALSE	REPLACEMENT	If the teacher only perceives or interprets, but there is neither teacher regulation nor teacher (final) decision within the subtask, it is replacement.
E 2	AI_OUTPUT, T_INPUT, T_REGULATE, T_DECISION_END	AI_OUTPUT = TRUE AND T_INPUT = TRUE AND T_REGULATE = TRUE AND T_DECISION_END = TRUE	COMPLEMENTARITY _TEACHER_LED	AI provides information that the teacher can work with. The teacher is observably engaged with the AI's output and captures decision authority.

In doing so, the codes allow to define how the AI is being part of the teaching and learning situation by describing different teacher-AI complementarity configurations. The applied coding scheme, both at the level of HTA and skill codes and through their explicit combination, yields a normative situational framing of teacher-AI interaction. By systematically applying the codes bottom-up across subtasks, the analysis produces a **fine-grained, situational description of teacher–AI interaction configurations** that allows for concrete interpretation of how pedagogical work is distributed, transformed, or newly constituted in hybrid teacher-AI environments. Rather than imposing superficial categories of human-AI collaboration, complementarity configurations emerge from observable patterns of how humans (teachers) and AI internalise skills and knowledge, exchange and execute tasks, leading to newly required skills and knowledge to achieve complementarity.

In this way, the analysis results in a structured description of configurations and changes. These configurations capture how tasks are performed by teachers and AI, while changes become visible through shifts in task structure, responsibility allocation, and required skills and knowledge. Importantly, the HTA provides a hierarchical representation of tasks, subtasks, and actions, which enables a differentiated understanding of **task change**. Task change can occur at multiple levels: at the overall task level, at the level of subtasks, or at the level of individual actions. The structure of the HTA is therefore essential for identifying whether task division choices between teacher and AI are made explicitly (e.g., through deliberate delegation) or implicitly (e.g., through automation embedded in system design). Observable changes can include (a) cases where a human task, subtask, or action becomes an

AI task, subtask, or action; (b) changes in the internal structure or sequencing of tasks; and (c) the emergence of new subtasks or actions, which subsequently drive the SKA.

Complementarity is further specified through the analysis of **skill change**. On the teacher's side, instructional action is conceptualized as involving situation-specific cognitive processes of perceiving, interpreting, and deciding (PID), which may be accompanied by metacognitive regulation such as planning, monitoring, and reflection and leads to further actions. On the AI side, corresponding functional capabilities are captured through detecting, diagnosing, and informing or acting (DDIA). Coding both sides within a shared functional logic allows the analysis to reveal how cognitive and regulatory responsibilities are redistributed across actors.

Compared with the baseline HTA's, analytically distinguishable types of **process change** can be identified. **Replacement** occurs when an existing human action is fully transferred from PIDA to DDIA, with the AI taking over the complete functional responsibility. **Partial replacement** describes cases in which elements of an existing human action are shifted to the AI, while other elements remain with the teacher. **Complementarity** captures configurations in which an existing action is performed jointly by teacher and AI, combining PID and DDIA across different steps. In such complementary configurations, bidirectional exchange and iteration may occur, and regulation can be enacted by teachers and/or by AI systems (in the form of informed, system-led decisions), with final decision authority residing either with the teacher or the AI.

4. Case study result

In this chapter we present a detailed description of applying all three components of the TAICo model to the Radboud University's case (RU case).

4.1 Applying Hierarchical Task Analysis to the RU Case: Curriculum Adaptivity

Summary of teacher-only task configuration

Before describing the AI-supported task configuration, it is important to characterize the baseline task configuration. In the baseline configuration (Figure 5A), teachers already interact with the non-AI components of the Snappet platform to carry out the task "schedule a differentiated math lesson." Specifically, teachers use the platform's user interface to review the current weekly planning (Figure 4A), consult the annual curriculum planning (screen 2), and examine class and student progress data in the dashboard (screen 3). These are interactions with standard UI elements — navigation, data display, and input fields — that do not involve AI processing. As shown in Table 13.1, all actions in the baseline configuration (1.1–1.6, 2.1–2.2) are teacher-executed in interaction with the UI (T→UI), with no AI involvement at any level of the hierarchy. The teacher is the sole cognitive agent throughout: retrieving, interpreting, and integrating information, while the platform serves as an information display and data entry surface. The baseline task configuration (Figure 5A) therefore represents the task as performed with the platform's conventional UI, and it is against this configuration that we compare the AI-supported task configuration (Figure 5B) to identify where the introduction of the AI component (Snappet Copilot) reconfigures the task. This distinction between UI interaction and AI interaction carries through into the task-level coding, where teacher actions are tagged accordingly.

Next, we describe the stepwise approach we took to analyse the RU case about curriculum adaptivity, resulting in the HTA diagram (Figure 5).

Link to the Figure in high resolution: [Figure 5](#)

Figure 5: A) Teacher-only and B) AI-supported decomposition (HTA diagram) of the pedagogical task in RU case Curriculum Adaptivity.

Step 1. Defined the task and purpose

We defined the task as “Schedule a differentiated math lesson” shown as the top level task in Figure 5. The broader purpose of the HTA is to compare the situation before (Figure 5A) and after the introduction of the AI feature (called Copilot) (Figure 5B) to identify how the task distribution changes.

Step 2. Identified the boundaries of the HTA

We defined the boundaries of the analysis following the three considerations described in the method: system boundary, trigger and terminal events, and actor scope.

The system boundary encompasses everything that contributes to the lesson-planning task: the teacher, the Snappet Copilot tool (both its AI component and its user interface), and the information sources consulted during planning. Activities that serve a different pedagogical purpose, such as preparing instructional materials or delivering the lesson, fall outside this boundary and would require a separate HTA.

The trigger event is the teacher opening the planning overview to begin planning mathematics lessons for a given week. The terminal event is the teacher confirming the student grouping and scheduling the differentiated lesson. These events correspond to recognisable transitions in the teacher's workflow: the task begins when the teacher initiates a planning session and ends when the planning decisions have been finalised. In Figure 4, these events map onto specific interactions in the tool (opening the planning overview in Screen 1 and scheduling the lesson in Screen 1, respectively), but the boundary itself is defined by the pedagogical transition, not by the interface.

The actor scope includes the teacher and the Snappet Copilot tool. No other actors (e.g., students or co-teachers) directly participate in this planning task.

Step 3. Gathered information from multiple sources

We compiled evidence on how the task is performed through interviews and think-alouds with 19 teachers using the Snappet platform. These sessions made visible the concrete sequence of actions teachers perform when planning a differentiated math lesson, including how they navigate the interface, which information sources they consult, where they make key instructional decisions, and how they interact with the AI-generated suggestions. The information gathered across informants was synthesised into a consolidated HTA that captures the common structure of the task while representing key decision points where teacher behaviour varies. This resulted in three different task configurations; we report on one here for conciseness, specifically the one with the most teacher-AI interactions.

Step 4. Drafted the diagrams with (sub)goal structure and action list

We translated the gathered information into an initial hierarchy: one top level task, a small set of subtasks, and action statements written in verb-object form. In Figure 5 this produced two main subtasks, one focused on selecting and scheduling a lesson and learning goal (subtask 1) and another focused on choosing a grouping (subtask 2), each decomposed into concrete actions.

Step 5. Established the level of detail and stopping point

Using the interview and think aloud data, we decomposed actions further when teachers described bringing in distinct information sources or making judgements that could influence later choices. For example, teachers did not describe “analyze class progress” (subtask 1.3) as a single step. Rather, they reported moving between their own knowledge, class level tool information, student level tool information, and classroom observations. We therefore specified 1.3 into four actions (1.3.1 to 1.3.4) to reflect the recurring components that teachers verbalised and enacted. This level of detail was needed because it clarifies what information is brought into two key decision points in the task: selecting a lesson objective (1.4) and evaluating the AI supported grouping (2.2).

In contrast, we avoided decomposing additional actions when the interviews and think alouds indicated that extra clicks of actions were merely navigational and did not add additional judgement or did not relate to any pedagogical goals. For instance, “Teacher looks at AI’s selected students per group” (2.2.2) is represented as a single action, even though some teachers described performing extra checks (for example opening underlying performance information) when they did not fully trust the AI suggestion. We treated these as plausible, optional verification actions and did not report them as standard steps unless they were consistently described across teachers or reliably changed the decision path.

Finally, we represented revisits explicitly only when they appeared in the think alouds as a meaningful return to earlier information that could alter the outcome. This is why Figure 5B includes actions that repeat earlier analysis, such as 1.4.3 and 2.2.3 (both repeating 1.3). Overall, we stopped decomposing when each action in the diagram could be grounded in what teachers actually reported doing, and was specific enough to support consistent coding of teacher and tool contributions, without turning the HTA into a button by button procedure.

Step 6. Specified plans and conditions

We specified plans and conditions to capture the control logic of the task: the order in which actions typically occur, and the points where the process can legitimately diverge. Based on the interviews and think alouds, we translated teachers' "if-then" reasoning into explicit sequences and branches, so the HTA reflects not only **what** actions occur but also **when** and **under which conditions** they occur (Table 12).

Table 12.2 shows two types of control logic we encoded. First, we represented the standard sequencing within subtasks. For example, within subtask 1 (select and schedule a math lesson and associated learning objective), teachers typically analyse progress information (1.3), consult the curriculum-level objectives (1.4.1), review the AI suggestion when available (1.4.2), and then choose a lesson objective (1.4.4) that is saved into planning (1.5) before scheduling the lesson (1.6). Second, we represented conditional branches where teachers described different routes. A clear example is the branch at 1.4.4 between (a) choosing an AI-suggested objective (1.4.4a) and (b) selecting an objective independently (1.4.4b). In the think-alouds, some teachers indicated that they follow route (a) when the AI suggestion fits their intended weekly plan and matches the observed class status, whereas they switch to route (b) when they want to prioritise a different learning goal (for example due to curriculum pacing, classroom observations, or other planning constraints).

We also used plans and conditions to model when teachers return to earlier steps. In Figure 5B, the repeat actions (for example 1.4.3 and 2.2.3 repeating 1.3) indicate that teachers may re-consult progress information after reviewing an AI suggestion, particularly when they are uncertain or when the suggestion conflicts with their expectations.

Step 7. Refined the HTA with expert teachers and iterate

We reviewed the draft diagram during a workshop with 24 experts (i.e., teachers) and revised the hierarchy and wording so that the HTA reflects a plausible and pedagogically sound way of working with the tool. We treat the HTA as a living document and log changes across iterations.

Task-level coding:

To make task change explicit, we compared the AI supported version (Figure 5B) against a teacher-only baseline (Figure 5A). See the beginning of the results chapter for a description of the teacher-only baseline version. Each action was then coded according to the dimensions described in the method, and repeated here for completeness:

1. **Action state (border type):** we tagged actions as 'existing' or 'new' (dotted border).
2. **Primary actor tag (fill colour):** Teacher in blue, AI part of the tool in yellow, student in green.
3. **Directionality of interaction with secondary actor (below action):** For each action, we looked whether this happens in interaction with a secondary actor and if so, we code the directionality of the interaction below that action.

What the resulting diagram shows.

The final Figure 5 is therefore the combination of (a) a validated hierarchy of task, subtasks, and actions, and (b) layered coding that makes division of labour and tool involvement visible at the action level. It becomes immediately legible where the AI contributes actions directly

(orange actions such as generating suggestions) and where the teacher’s work is supported by the tool’s UI or by the AI component (indicated below each respective action).

Table 12 shows all (sub)goals and actions together with a plan.

Table 12.1.

Table of teacher actions for Panel A: Pedagogical task before introduction of AI. The task and subtasks are in bold. Each subtask requires a plan (sequence and conditions).

Task, subtasks and actions	Plan (Sequence and conditions)
0.Schedule a differentiated math lesson	First 1, then 2.
1.Select and schedule a lesson and associated learning objective	Carry out 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4, 1.5 and 1.6 in numerical order.
1.1.Teacher opens the month planning in the tool	
1.2.Teacher creates an overview by reviewing the planning	
1.3.Teacher retrieves insights about class progress and curriculum knowledge	
1.4.Teacher opens screen with curriculum objectives	
1.5.Teacher selects learning objective	
1.6.Teacher schedules the lesson	
2.Choose a student grouping	Carry out 2.1 and 2.2 in numerical order.
2.1.Teacher reviews student performance and classroom knowledge	
2.2.Teacher makes a grouping and saves it in the tool	

Table 12.2.

Table of teacher actions for Panel B: Pedagogical task after introduction of AI. The task and subtasks are in bold. Each subtask requires a plan (sequence and conditions).

Task, subtasks and actions	Plan (Sequence and conditions)
0.Schedule a differentiated math lesson	First 1, then 2.
1.Select and schedule a math lesson and associated learning objective	Carry out 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4, 1.5 and 1.6 in numerical order.
1.1.Teacher opens the month planning in the tool	
1.2.Teacher creates an overview by reviewing the planning	
1.3.Analyze class progress on the learning goals	Carry out 1.3.1, 1.3.2, 1.3.3 and 1.3.4 in numerical order. Repeat this sequence whenever updated information about class status is needed.
1.3.1.Teacher retrieves their own insights about class progress and curriculum knowledge	
1.3.2.Teacher looks at progress on learning goals at class level in tool	

1.3.3. Teacher looks at progress on learning goals at student level in tool

1.3.4. Teacher integrates tool data with their own classroom observations

1.4. Select a lesson objective at curriculum level

Carry out 1.4.1, 1.4.2, 1.4.3 and 1.4.4 in numerical order.

1.4.1. Teacher opens screen with curriculum objectives

1.4.2. AI suggests lesson objectives

1.4.3. Teacher evaluates AI suggestions based on class status and class planning (repeat 1.3)

1.4.4. Choose a lesson objective

Do either 1.4.4a or 1.4.4b.

1.4.4a. Teacher chooses a suggestion from the AI

1.4.4b. Teacher chooses a lesson objective from the planning themselves

1.5. Teacher saves lesson objective in planning

1.6. Teacher schedules the lesson

2. Choose a grouping

Carry out 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4 in numerical order.

2.1. AI suggests student grouping for differentiation

2.2. Evaluate differentiation suggestions

Carry out 2.2.1, 2.2.2 and 2.2.3 in numerical order. If the teacher wants to adjust the AI suggestion, potentially also carry out 2.2.4. Then proceed to 2.3.

2.2.1. Teacher retrieves their own insights about students and curriculum knowledge

2.2.2. Teacher looks at AI's selected students

2.2.3. Teacher re-analyses class status (repeats 1.3)

2.2.4. Teacher adjusts AI differentiation suggestion

2.3. Teacher accepts the (final) differentiation suggestion

2.4. Teacher schedules the differentiated lesson

4.2 Applying Skill and Knowledge Analysis to the RU Case

Using the results of the HTA, we focus on new teacher-AI actions indicated by the action state coding of the HTA. The table below presents the results of the SKA for the RU case, organized at the action level and structured along the coding dimensions introduced in the method chapter. Each row represents one newly identified teacher or AI actions derived from the HTA and analyzed in terms of skills, knowledge, and state.

Each subtask is represented by its own table (Table 13.1 & Table 13.2.). The columns highlighted in grey contain information from the HTA, including the ID, a short description of the new action, the actor tag, and the directionality of the interaction. Together, these columns specify who is the primary actor, whether a secondary actor is involved, and how

information flows between teacher and AI (e.g., AI → Teacher via a dashboard or Teacher → AI via an adjustment). It should be emphasized that the codes of the coding dimensions can be assigned multiple times within a subgoal and independently to all subgoals. Thus, there is no dependency between multiple subgoals and the codes that can be assigned to them.

As described in the methods chapter, teacher cognitive skills or AI capabilities, respectively, teacher metacognitive skills or regulatory capabilities, respectively, as well as the teacher knowledge or system resources necessary for performing the action, respectively, are analyzed and listed in the subsequent columns.

Rows (new action identified in the HTA): Each row corresponds to a new action performed by either the teacher or the AI system within a specific subtask. The ID column allows tracing the action back to the HTA structure.

Skill/capability columns: The columns cognitive skills/capabilities and metacognitive skills/regulatory capabilities indicate which skills are required by the primary actor to perform an action.

Cognitive skills and capabilities distinguish between

- teachers' situation-specific skills (perceive, interpret, decide, act) and
- functionally equivalent AI capabilities (detect, diagnose, inform, act).

Metacognitive skills and capabilities capture planning, monitoring, and evaluating when implied by the action. Even if using the same terminology, as described above, there is an important distinction between

- teachers' metacognitive skills and
- corresponding AI regulatory capabilities.

Knowledge/system resources column: This column specifies the knowledge resources required to perform an action, not the knowledge generated by the action.

- For teachers, knowledge codes follow the AI-TPACK framework (e.g., PK, AI-TK, AI-TPK).
- For AI systems, codes refer to internal representations such as models, rules, or training data.

Action-level state column: Additionally, the state of the required skills/ capabilities and knowledge/system resources is coded (E = existing, N = new). Based on the combination of existing and new skills and knowledge, an aggregated action-level state is assigned to each action, indicating whether the action relies on established practice or introduces new skill-related, knowledge-related, or connected demands.

Interpretation column: Finally, the Interpretation column explains the rationale behind the coding decisions. It links the coded skills, knowledge, and state to the instructional meaning of the action and clarifies how AI integration reshapes responsibilities, cognition, or control in this step.

Taken together, the table allows readers to move from left to right: from identifying who acts and how, through which skills and knowledge are required, to whether these requirements change due to teacher-AI interaction. Below we describe the results of the skill and knowledge analyses for the RU case about curriculum adaptivity.

Table 13.1. Coding of skill dimensions for the RU case; subtask 1.4

Subtask 1.4: Select a lesson objective at curriculum level											
ID	New teacher/AI action	Actor tag		Directionality of the interaction	Cognitive skills	Respective AI capabilities	Metacognitive skills	Regulatory capabilities	Knowledge/ system resources to perform an action	State Aggregation	Interpretation
		primary	secondary		Teacher	AI	Teacher	AI			
1.4.2	AI suggests lesson objectives	AI	-		-	Detect and diagnose students' performance (E); inform by providing suggestions (N)	-	Planning of lesson objectives (E)	M: Expert and student model (ITS); R: aligning student performance with curriculum objectives; SR: representation of the current instructional context (class level, progress status) (N)	N-C (New, combined)	AI (Snappet Copilot) externalizes established monitoring of students. AI has new capabilities as it optimizes between class and individual goals instead of only optimizing on the individual level.
1.4.3	Teacher evaluates AI suggestions based on class status and class planning (repeat 1.3)	Teacher	AI	AI→T	Perceive dashboard data (E); Interpret AI suggestions (N)	-	MC_Monitoring (ongoing assessment of whether the AI-suggested objectives align with teachers' goals and plan) (N) and MC_Evaluating (reflective appraisal of whether the AI-generated objective supports intended goals) (N)	-	AI-TK (understanding what Copilot does) (N); AI-TCK (judging AI-generated suggestions) (N)	N-C (New, combined)	The action introduces new skill demands, which require new knowledge to enable the teacher to oversee and evaluate the AI output and align with their own curriculum and class knowledge and current development of students in the class.
1.4.4.a	Teacher chooses a suggestion from the A	Teacher	AI	T→AI	Decide (N) and act (E)	-	-	-	AI-TPK (knowing how AI suggestions affect pedagogy) (N); XK (curriculum and curriculum pacing) (N)	N-C (New, combined)	The action requires new regulatory skill enactment. Decision-making itself is not new, but AI-supported decision-making is, as it requires judging if AI-suggested objectives are acceptable or should be rejected/changed is new.

Table 13.2. Coding of skill dimensions for the RU case; subtask 2

Subtask 2: Choose a grouping											
ID	New teacher/AI action	Actor tag		Directionality of the interaction	Cognitive skills	Respective AI capabilities	Metacognitive skills	Regulatory capabilities	Knowledge/ system resources to perform an action	State Aggregation	Interpretation
		primary	secondary		Teacher	AI	Teacher	AI			
2.2.1	AI gives suggestions for grouping	AI	-		-	Detect (E) and diagnose students' performance (E); inform by providing suggestions (N)	-	Planning of grouping (N)	M: for mapping student performance data to grouping rules; R: Grouping rules; SR: representation of students' current states (N)	N-C (New, combined)	The capability to provide suggestions for grouping represents a new AI function, even though the data and rules themselves are established.
2.2.2	Teacher looks at AI's selected students per group	Teacher	AI	AI→T	Perceive dashboard data (E); Interpret AI suggestions (N)	-	MC_Monitoring (ongoing assessment of whether the AI-suggested objectives align with teachers' goals and plan) (N)	-	PK (grouping strategies and differentiation principles) (E); AI-TK (understanding how Copilot generates and visualizes grouping suggestions) (N)	N-C (New, combined)	Although evaluating dashboard data are existing skills, interpreting AI-based suggestions requires new AI-specific technological knowledge, e.g., how the AI suggests on groupings, as well as new metacognitive monitoring to decide whether to continue versus to adapt the suggestion.
2.2.3	Teacher reanalyses class status (repeats 1.3)	Teacher	UI	UI→T	Perceive (E) and interpret additional dashboard data (E)	-	MC_Evaluating (assessment of one's own level of knowledge to determine whether additional information is needed to judge the AI's suggestion) (N)	-	AI-TK (understanding how to navigate and interpret dashboard data) (E)	N-S (New, skill-driven)	Although perceiving and interpreting dashboard data are existing skills, teachers must apply it to new epistemic objects and reflect on themselves in order to reach a decision. applied to established practice.
2.2.4	Teacher adjusts AI differentiation suggestion	Teacher	AI	T→AI	Decide (N)	-	MC_Planning (further goal setting and allocating resources) (N)	-	AI-TK (understanding the AI grouping logic and system functionality) (E); AI-TPK (understanding how AI-generated groupings interact with pedagogical goals and classroom management decisions) (N)	N-C (New, combined)	To judge on AI suggestions, teachers need an understanding of AI grouping logic and adapt/integrate it to pedagogical and social considerations. So the action requires new regulatory skill enactment by deciding how to adjust AI suggestions.
2.3	Teacher finally accepts the differentiation suggestion	Teacher	AI	T→AI	Decide (N) and act (E)	-	-	-	AI-TPK (understanding how AI suggestions affect pedagogy) (N)	N-C (New, combined)	Final commitment decisions in AI-supported actions are not equivalent to routine instructional decisions, as they involve responsibility for algorithmically mediated outcomes. Therefore, teachers need a comprehensive understanding of AI to judge when AI-supported groupings are acceptable and how much to rely on them.

Across both subtasks - selecting a lesson objective and choosing a grouping - the SKA reveals that AI integration in the RU case does not primarily replace teacher cognition but redistributes and extends it.

The AI largely builds on existing detection and diagnostic capabilities but introduces new capabilities as it optimizes between class and individual goals instead of only optimizing on the individual level. AI externalises performance monitoring and translates student data into actionable suggestions, by informing the teacher. In particular, AI-generated lesson objectives and grouping proposals shift part of the analytic work from implicit teacher reasoning to explicit algorithmic output. The AI, therefore, assumes an expanded role in structuring the informational basis for instructional decision-making.

For the teacher, the most salient changes occur in interpretation, decision-making, and metacognitive regulation. Perceiving dashboard data largely remains part of the established practice and baseline HTA. However, interpreting AI-generated suggestions requires new AI-specific technological knowledge (AI-TK) and AI-technological pedagogical knowledge (AI-TPK) to judge how algorithmic outputs relate to pedagogical goals, curriculum pacing, and classroom situations. Teachers must therefore understand not only what the system displays but also how and why suggestions are generated.

Additionally, teachers need to monitor their own level of knowledge to determine whether AI suggestions align with their own goals and plan and whether they need additional information. In Subtask 2, the re-analysis of class status (2.2.3) illustrates this: while perceive and interpret dashboard data remain existing (E), the action becomes skill-driven new (N-S) because teachers must engage in additional evaluation before committing to or adjusting AI suggestions.

All other aggregated action-level states indicate that new actions in both subtasks are coded as new combined (N-C), meaning they require both new/extended skills and new knowledge. Although deciding itself is an established pedagogical skill, AI-mediated decision-making involves judging the appropriateness of algorithmic recommendations and assuming responsibility for AI-generated outcomes. This introduces new regulatory enactment and requires extended AI-related knowledge.

Overall, the SKA demonstrates that, in the RU curriculum adaptivity case, AI serves as decision support for lesson planning. Using Snippet Copilot, teachers stay responsible for interpretation, contextualization, and regulatory oversight. Teacher expertise remains central and becomes even more important because they need to judge AI suggestions. As this process is increasingly mediated by AI-generated recommendations, this leads to a configuration in which algorithmic suggestions and pedagogical judgment are tightly coupled within subtasks.

4.3 Applying the Complementarity Analysis to the RU Case

Building on the HTA and SKA, the CA integrates structural task change and skill distribution at the level of subtasks, as proposed in chapter 3.3. Complementarity is not derived from isolated actions, but from the configuration of teacher and AI contributions within each subtask, leading to teacher-AI interaction. Complementarity labels are derived by combining HTA and skill codes.

Subtask 1.4: Select a Lesson Objective

In Subtask 1.4, AI is introduced as a primary actor by generating lesson objective suggestions. Since at least one action in the subtask is structurally new (HTA) and requires new skills and knowledge (SKA), NEW_WORK is coded as TRUE.

At the level of functional contribution, the AI detects, diagnoses, and informs, producing output in the form of suggested learning objectives. However, it does not autonomously execute instructional decisions or includes teachers feedback in further actions.

The teacher perceives and interprets the AI-generated suggestions, engages in metacognitive monitoring and evaluating, decides whether to accept or adjust the suggestions, and executes the final action. Because AI output is present and the teacher observably regulates the process - indicated by repeated sequences of actions to gain additional information - accompanied by interpretation, evaluation, decision-making, and acting, T_REGULATE is coded as TRUE. The teacher performs the final decision-related action, resulting in T_DECISION_END = TRUE.

Although information flows in both directions (AI → teacher via suggestion; teacher → AI via selection), there is no repeated alternation of output and response within the same subtask. Therefore, BIDIRECTIONAL_EXCHANGE = TRUE and ITERATION = FALSE.

According to the examples for labeling complementarity in chapter 3.3, this configuration is assigned the **label: COMPLEMENTARITY_TEACHER_LED**

Here, AI structures the interaction by generating decision-relevant options, while the teacher retains interpretive authority, regulatory control, and final decision-making responsibility.

Table 14.1 provides an overview of HTA, SKA, and combined codes set to true for the analyzed subtask 1.

Table 14.1. Subtask-Level Complementarity Table for Subtask 1.4 (RU Case).

Subtask	Combined codes
<p>1. Select and schedule a math lesson and associated learning objective</p>	<p>NEW_WORK_ACTION = TRUE because the subtask contains at least one action with Action state = New, namely the Copilot suggestion action.</p> <p>NEW_SKILL_KNOWLEDGE = TRUE because the state coding logic indicates that interpreting AI suggestions and regulating acceptance or rejection requires new knowledge and new metacognitive skills for the teacher (Aggregated state = New).</p> <p>NEW_WORK = TRUE because both NEW_WORK_ACTION and NEW_SKILL_KNOWLEDGE are true.</p> <p>AI_OUTPUT = TRUE because the subtask contains an AI primary action that provides output to the teacher (Copilot suggests lesson objectives).</p> <p>T_PERCEIVE = TRUE and T_INTERPRET = TRUE because after AI output the teacher engages in sensemaking actions, operationalised as the teacher interpreting the AI suggestions.</p> <p>T_DECIDE = TRUE because the teacher selects a lesson objective.</p> <p>T_OUTPUT = TRUE and T_DECISION_END = TRUE because the subtask ends with a teacher decision, operationalised as choosing and saving the lesson objective.</p> <p>T_REGULATE = TRUE because AI_OUTPUT, T_PERCEIVE, T_INTERPRET, T_MC_MONITORING, T_MC_EVALUATING, T_DECIDE, and T_OUTPUT are all true within the subtask.</p>
<p>Complementarity Label</p>	<p>LABEL_COMPLEMENTARITY_TEACHER_LED, because the AI provides information to the teacher, who is observably engaged with the output. The teacher decides to accept, adapt, or reject the AI suggestion (AI_OUTPUT = TRUE AND T_REGULATE = TRUE). At the end, the teacher captures the final decision (T_DECISION_END = TRUE).</p> <p>It's not replacement, because although the AI detects and diagnoses, its output informs the teacher, and the AI is not acting independently.</p>

Subtask 2: Choose a Grouping

In subtask 2, AI provides grouping suggestions based on student data. As in Subtask 1.4, structural change and new skill/knowledge demands are present; thus, `NEW_WORK = TRUE`.

Functionally, AI again performs detect, diagnose, and inform and generates grouping suggestions. The teacher responds by perceiving and interpreting the suggestions, engaging in monitoring and evaluating, and re-analysing class data when necessary, and adjusting groupings if required. Teacher regulation is therefore observable, satisfying the condition for `T_REGULATE = TRUE`. Final decision authority remains with the teacher (`T_DECISION_END = TRUE`).

The interaction is bidirectional: AI produces output that the teacher works with, and the teacher's adjustments are directed back into the system. However, the repeated re-analysis of class data does not constitute iterative AI-teacher interaction. There are no alternating cycles of AI output and system-updated response within the same subtask. Therefore, `BIDIRECTIONAL_EXCHANGE = TRUE` and `ITERATION = FALSE`.

This subtask is thus also classified as: **COMPLEMENTARITY_TEACHER_LED**

Table 14.2 provides an overview of HTA, SKA, and combined codes set to true for the analyzed subtask 1.

Table 14.2. Subtask-Level Complementarity Table for Subtask 2 (RU Case).

Subtask	Combined codes
<p>2.Choosing a grouping for differentiation (subtask 2)</p>	<p>NEW_WORK_ACTION = TRUE because the subtask contains at least one action with Action state = New, namely the Copilot suggestion action for grouping.</p> <p>NEW_SKILL_KNOWLEDGE = TRUE because the state coding logic indicates that interpreting AI suggestions and regulating acceptance or rejection requires new knowledge and new metacognitive skills for the teacher (Aggregated state = New).</p> <p>NEW_WORK = TRUE because both NEW_WORK_ACTION and NEW_SKILL_KNOWLEDGE are true.</p> <p>AI_OUTPUT = TRUE because the subtask contains an AI primary action that provides output to the teacher (Copilot suggests groupings).</p> <p>T_PERCEIVE = TRUE and T_INTERPRET = TRUE because after AI output the teacher engages in sensemaking actions, operationalised as the teacher interpreting the AI suggestions.</p> <p>T_DECIDE = TRUE because the teacher makes a choice about grouping.</p> <p>T_OUTPUT = TRUE and T_DECISION_END = TRUE because the subtask ends with a teacher decision, operationalised as accepting, rejecting, or adjusting the grouping and committing that choice in the pedagogical task.</p> <p>T_REGULATE = TRUE because AI_OUTPUT, T_PERCEIVE, T_INTERPRET, T_MC_MONITORING, T_MC_EVALUATING, T_DECIDE, and T_OUTPUT are all true within the subtask.</p>
<p>Complementarity Label</p>	<p>LABEL_COMPLEMENTARITY_TEACHER_LED, because the AI provides information to the teacher, who is observably engaged with the output. The teacher decides to accept, adapt, or reject the AI suggestion (AI_OUTPUT = TRUE AND T_REGULATE = TRUE). At the end, the teacher captures the final decision (T_DECISION_END = TRUE).</p> <p>It's not replacement, because although the AI detects and diagnoses, its output informs the teacher, and the AI is not acting independently.</p>

Summary of case study results

In the initial RU curriculum adaptivity case, the AI system mostly structures and reconfigures the existing pedagogical task at the level of subtasks and the related actions. Typical patterns are that AI takes over and supports monitoring students' learning and first pass interpretation, while teachers retain or even intensify student data interpretation and pedagogical decision-making. The Skill and Knowledge Analysis translates these task changes into concrete competence demands: (1) interpreting AI outputs, (2) deciding when to accept, adapt or reject AI suggestions, and (3) integrating AI-informed decisions with contextual knowledge. These demands draw on AI-specific professional knowledge (AI-TK, AI-TCK, AI-TPK), on cognitive situation-specific skills of perceive, interpret and decide, and on metacognitive skills for planning, monitoring and evaluating, including the regulation of AI use within one's own teaching practice.

Across both analyzed subtasks, this results in a consistent pattern of teacher-led complementarity. That is, the configuration does not constitute replacement or partial replacement, as core pedagogical judgment and decision authority are not transferred to the AI. Nor does it reflect iterative teacher-AI interaction. Instead, it exemplifies structured decision support in which AI expands the informational basis of planning, while teachers regulate and authorise instructional action.

5. Discussion

Evaluation of and reflection on first application of the method

In this deliverable we provide a detailed description of applying the three-component method (1. Hierarchical Task Analysis, 2. Skill and Knowledge Analysis, 3. Complementarity Analysis) of our initial TAICo model to the RU case. Below we summarize our reflections on the application of our model to the RU case, before discussing our initial conclusions.

This exemplary application suggests that the approach is feasible and that the three components add distinct value. The method works as intended as an integrated chain. HTA makes the pedagogical task explicit by decomposing the focal pedagogical task into subtasks, actions, and plans. The SKA then specifies what teachers do at the points where AI enters the pedagogical task, making visible which skills are enacted, changed or newly demanded, and which knowledge teachers need to perform the actions. The CA provides a transparent way to describe the observed subtasks using explicit rules, without treating complementarity as a vague label. In this way, the application example presented in this deliverable shows that the three components support traceability from observed task changes to skill and knowledge demands and interaction patterns. Complementarity is realised through dependencies between actions (one actor's output is the input for the other), rather than through separate "AI tasks" and "teacher tasks". This supports the decision to code at action and subtask level. It also implies that future case level reporting should summarise profiles and distributions across subtasks to describe complementarity more thoroughly.

However, this application of our method also highlights where information from other TAICo cases are needed in order to further refine our model. The RU case application identifies methodological choices that will need to be stabilised when scaling up. Subtask boundaries and the representation of the deciding actor matter. Relatedly, a teacher can be actively

involved in a subtask by interpreting an AI output, even when the HTA does not capture a separate, explicit decision action such as accepting, rejecting, or saving a choice in the tool. Our current choice is to treat subtasks without observable interaction and teacher decision evidence as replacement, and to assign complementarity only when interaction and decision evidence is visible. This operational choice does not aim to fix complementarity categories; rather, it allows the analysis to differentiate and compare distinct complementarity configurations across subtasks in a transparent and rule-based manner. As additional cases are analysed, these configurations can be systematically contrasted, enabling a more fine-grained understanding of their variation and of the consequences they entail for teacher-AI interaction, responsibility distribution, and instructional decision-making.

6. Conclusions

In this deliverable we present an initial version of the TAIco teacher-AI complementarity model, which is embedded in the broader TAIco framework (see Figure 2). The TAIco model connects three perspectives: economic task-based views of technological change, educational perspectives on teacher competence and skill development, and the idea of hybrid intelligence. By analysing concrete pedagogical tasks, we move beyond job level automation toward a task and skill level account of how teachers and AI actually share work in classrooms. The discussion reflects on the first application of the model components and situates the observed patterns in relation to complementarity, task change, and skill demands.

Overall, the RU case illustrates that AI integration leads less to replacement than to complementarity, shown by a reconfiguration of actions, resulting in shifted responsibilities and expanded skill and knowledge demands for teachers. Beyond introducing new skill demands, AI also redistributes the load on existing skills and may create risks of erosion, raising the question of whether and under which conditions such shifts are problematic or not. In the present case we capture these changes only at a single point in time and do not yet address how such redistributions may unfold or accumulate over time. Nevertheless, dynamic implications over time are conceivable. For instance, when AI partially takes over teachers' cognitive situation-specific skills, such as perceive and interpret student data, these skills may be activated less often, while interpretive and decision-making skills become more central and more frequent. For novice teachers in particular, there is a risk that some skills do not fully develop if AI structures too much of the process. These findings provide concrete anchors for professional development in WP4 in developing training formats that both expand teachers' knowledge base through explicit conceptual and factual input and provide structured opportunities for practice, ensuring that the use of AI supports, rather than replaces, the development of core perceptual, interpretive, and decision-making skills, particularly among novice teachers. At the same time, the findings provide a basis for the design, development, and deployment of AI features in WP3, for example around transparency, explanation and interface design that support teacher agency rather than undermining it.

These changes in task structure and skill demands become particularly visible when focusing on complementarity configurations within subtasks, emerging through handoffs: AI produces a suggestion or analysis that teachers then interpret and decide to accept, adapt, or override. Rather than reducing teacher work, these configurations often expand the scope of tasks and introduce new demands. In such subtasks, different forms of interaction can occur around

PIDA and DDIA processes, for example, AI-based detection and diagnosis triggering teacher interpretation and decision-making, or teacher decisions feeding back into AI actions. The specific pattern of these interactions determines the resulting complementarity configuration and allows different configurations to be systematically compared across subtasks and cases. At the same time complementarity is highly local and context dependent. The same AI tool can support very different task structures depending on how teachers configure it, their beliefs and experience, and organisational constraints. Some configurations approximate a replacement for specific decisions, whereas others keep teachers central and use AI outputs as one input among several decision points. This confirms that complementarity cannot be read off from AI affordances alone but must be understood as interaction in a socio-technical configuration of actions, roles and conditions. At the same time, the present analysis is deliberately static. It captures complementarity configurations at the level of subtasks but does not yet represent dynamic transitions between configurations. Processes such as handoffs, dependencies, and temporal coordination across actions and subtasks are therefore not modelled explicitly. Addressing these dynamics constitutes a next analytical step, focusing on interaction processes through which complementarity unfolds over time.

Taken together, the initial TAICo model enables the identification and comparison of complementarity configurations, providing an analytical conceptual lens and serving as a systematic basis for theory-driven assumptions and the generation of hypotheses for subsequent field studies. The complementarity configurations allow to formulate assumptions and hypotheses about expected changes in teacher tasks, teacher skills, and thus professional demands, related to specific configurations of teacher-AI interaction. The three-step approach (HTA, SKA and CA), together with the shared notation for tasks, roles and skills offers a common language across TAICo work packages. This supports the systematic linkage of observed configurations to teacher characteristics, AI system properties and deployment conditions, and will inform validation studies in the next project phase.

7. Next steps

The current deliverable presents **four** main outcomes:

- A first version of the TAICo model and shared terminology, integrating economic, educational and hybrid intelligence lenses.
- An HTA based task analysis approach with TAICo specific coding for actors, roles, and interaction directionality.
- A skill and knowledge coding scheme that maps teacher cognitive and metacognitive skills, professional knowledge and respective AI capabilities and system resources onto newly emerging actions in the HTAs.
- An initial set of combined codes that describe how task structures, skills, and responsibilities are distributed between teachers and AI at the level of subtasks, allowing further the description and labeling of various complementarity configurations.

Building on these outcomes, the overarching ambition is to move towards cross-case patterns of complementarity configurations, with a particular focus on how complementarity configurations are enacted and transformed in practice.

In the next phase of TAICo, WP1 will focus on **four directions**.

7.1 Extend and stabilise the complementarity model in WP1

We will refine the model based on the HTAs and skill and knowledge coding for all TAICo cases. This includes refining the combined codes and developing a set of complementarity configuration labels to describe actions and skills within tasks, and clarifying how tasks requiring cognitive and metacognitive skills as well as knowledge are reconfigured when AI is introduced. This enables systematic comparison across cases and support subsequent validation and hypothesis development.

7.2 Analyse interaction processes

Building on the identification of complementarity configurations, WP1 will extend the analysis towards interaction processes within subtasks. While the current approach captures how tasks and skills are distributed between teacher and AI at a given point in time, the next step is to examine how teacher-AI interaction unfolds within subtasks. As responsibilities, information, and decision-making are distributed across teachers and AI, the quality of complementarity depends not only on which actions are performed by whom but also on how information is communicated, interpreted, and acted upon, and how coordination and regulation take place.

To address this, WP1 will work towards action- and skill-focused analyses with an examination of interaction, regulation and coordination processes. Analysing these processes will allow us to move beyond static descriptions of complementarity configurations towards a more process-oriented understanding of teacher-AI interaction.

7.3 Provide inputs for WP2, WP3 and WP4

- **Towards WP2 (validation studies)**

WP2 validates the complementarity model through the TAICo case studies and synthesizes findings across cases to build a robust knowledge base. WP1 will (together with WP2) distil a small set of testable assumptions from the cross-case complementarity configurations, for example about where replacement is likely to occur and which skills are most affected. These assumptions, together with the HTA and skill and knowledge coding templates and the complementarity codes, will be used by WP2 to design and carry out validation studies in authentic settings. WP1's role is to provide the conceptual and measurement backbone; WP2 leads the empirical testing.

- **Towards WP3 (AI affordances and teaming levels)**

WP3 analyzes existing AI tools and develops future-oriented, human-centered design scenarios to formulate evidence-informed guidelines for AI development and deployment. They conceptualise teaming levels as descriptions of AI system affordances and technical constraints that define the space of possible teacher-AI interaction. WP1 contributes by grounding these affordance-based teaming levels in analyses of complementarity configurations. In the current deliverable, WP1 has analysed how AI systems enter pedagogical tasks at the level of subtasks and actions, how responsibilities for perceive, interpret, and decide are distributed, and which skills and knowledge are required. These analyses make visible where and how AI affordances become relevant, and which forms of interaction they enable or constrain. In the next phase, WP1 will extend this analysis to interaction processes within subtasks, providing comparable evidence on how AI affordances shape observed complementarity configurations in concrete instructional contexts, which WP3 can use to refine the teaming level taxonomy.

- **Towards WP4 (professional development)**

WP4 investigates teacher professional learning and the impact of AI on the teaching profession to derive policy recommendations and best practices for teacher training. Using the SKA, WP1 will specify where new or changing skill and knowledge demands arise (for example interpreting AI outputs, calibrating trust, deciding when to override suggestions) and where existing skills risk erosion. These patterns will be translated into preliminary PD anchors: candidate learning goals, critical incidents that can be used in PD, and examples of HTA and skill tables that can function as PD artefacts. Insights into interaction and coordination processes will further inform WP4 about where reflective engagement, sensemaking, and timing of decisions should be targeted in professional development trajectories. WP4 can then build PD trajectories and interventions on this task and skill-based foundation.

7.4 Prepare a shared validation and measurement framework

Finally, WP1 will collaborate with WP2, WP3 and WP4 to assemble a shared inventory of measures and coding instruments that can be used across validation studies. This will include HTA-based codes, core skill codes/indicators (for instance situation specific perception-interpretation-decision skills and metacognitive skills) and teacher reported outcomes, for instance perceived agency and workload. This shared framework will support cumulative evidence building across work packages and ensure that findings can be interpreted within one coherent complementarity model.

Appendices

Appendix A: Overview of TAIco cases

Table A1: Overview of analysed cases and data sources for observation studies used for HTA development.

Partner and case	AI tool	Main task	Teacher participants	Main data sources for HTA
OULU, MAI agent	MAI metacognitive AI agent that supports students' regulation during collaborative tasks	Guide collaborative learning exercise during class	Basic school teachers working with student groups using MAI	Transcribed classroom video recordings of MAI supported activities, focusing on how MAI and teachers jointly support (socially shared) regulation of learning
UWK, GenAI for activity design	Generative AI tools used for co designing learning activities	Design a learning activity	Teachers and learning designers participating in a design workshop	Observational workshop data: field notes, audio or video recordings, and collected artefacts (AI supported activity designs)
TLU, GenAI for lesson planning	Generative AI tools for lesson planning (prompt based assistants)	Monitor and coregulate collaborative learning during class	Secondary and vocational school teachers from different subjects	Think aloud lesson planning sessions with GenAI, screen and voice recordings, transcribed protocols, short reflective comments
RU, Curriculum adaptivity (Co-pilot)	Snappet Co-pilot for curriculum adaptive maths practice in primary education	Schedule a differentiated math lesson	Primary school teachers using Snappet in planning their mathematics lessons (N = 23)	Teacher interviews, think aloud planning or walkthroughs with the dashboard, classroom observations, and system generated data from Snappet Co-pilot

RU, GenAI feedback	Generative AI assistant that helps teachers plan or draft personalised feedback on project based assignments	Plan personalised feedback for a project based assignment	Secondary school teachers who experimented with the GenAI feedback pedagogical task	Screen and audio recordings of feedback planning with GenAI, collected prompts and AI outputs, follow up interviews or evaluation on how the tool fits feedback practice
RUB, Calcularis	Calcularis intelligent tutoring system for basic maths skills	Decide on (individual) support measures for students for math	Primary and secondary teachers supporting students' work with the ITS	Screen recordings of teachers' interactions with Calcularis, teacher questionnaires (for example AI related beliefs and experience), and interview and think aloud data from pilot participants
UCL, Collaboration analytics dashboard	Collaboration analytics dashboard that provides monitoring of collaboration indicators and offering personalised feedback for students	Plan the next collaborative learning lesson	Higher education teachers (teaching assistants and module leader) using the dashboard to monitor and distribute feedback for student groups	Data from authentic classroom use of the dashboard, system logs and analytics reports, and teacher interviews or evaluations on monitoring, interpretation, and intervention strategies

Appendix B: Core definitions

The field is characterised by a proliferation of terms, often used inconsistently or even synonymously. This heterogeneity complicates conceptual clarity and the comparability of research findings. To ensure coherence within this project, we establish a shared terminology. The following table provides an overview of the key concepts and terms used in this deliverable.

Table A2. List of terminology.

Term	Description
Task	In our context a task is a pedagogical-instructional teaching activity that consists of subtasks and actions that jointly achieve the pedagogical task.
Subtask	A subtask is a lower level unit of work within a larger task
Action	An action is the lowest level unit of work within a larger task, written as verb-object.
Task configuration	How actions within a task are arranged and distributed between agents = the result of HTA before introduction of AI supported tool.
Task reconfiguration	A change in task configuration over time: actions are rearranged and redistributed across actors = result of HTA after introduction of AI supported tool.
Competence	Context specific interplay of knowledge, skills, motivational dispositions, and self regulatory dispositions enabling performance and adaptation to professional demands.
Knowledge	Knowledge is a task-related, multidimensional construct, consisting of distinct types that vary in qualitative characteristics and together enable effective performance. Teacher professional knowledge includes a context sensitive understanding of content, pedagogy, and technology and their interaction, enabling effective and pedagogically meaningful teaching strategies.
Skill	Skill is procedural knowledge (knowing how) applied to perform tasks or to solve problems in context, including AI impacted cognitive and metacognitive skills for working with and around AI systems.
Cognitive skill	Cognitive skills allow humans to process, understand, and use information, describing how knowledge is enacted in concrete pedagogical tasks. It involves encoding, memorising, and recalling information.
Metacognitive skill	Metacognitive skills are commonly defined as the capacity to monitor and regulate one's own cognitive processes, with the self as the referent of cognition.
TAICo specific terminology	
TAICo framework	Description of relationships between parts of the ecosystem (teacher characteristics, AI affordances, deployment conditions) affecting complementarity. (see Figure 1)
Teacher-AI complementarity model (TAICo model)	WP1 conceptual model for describing teacher-AI interactions within pedagogical tasks. In the main text, it is operationalised in an analytical approach utilizing three components (Hierarchical Task Analysis, Skill and Knowledge Analysis, Complementarity Analysis) within the larger sociotechnical system.
Complementarity	Configurations of how teachers and AI interact at the level of tasks and skills, each contributing distinct yet interdependent actions, skills/capabilities, and knowledge/ system resources within pedagogical tasks.

Appendix C: Qualitative Cross Case Analysis of Complementarity and its sociotechnical conditions in the TAICo cases

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Exploring Complementarity in the interaction of teachers and Artificial Intelligence: A cross-case analysis

Tobias Ley^{1,6}, Mutlu Cukurova², Justin Edwards³, Ann-Christin Falhs⁵, Sanna Järvelä³, Reet Kasepalu⁶, Anne-Wil Kramer⁴, Inge Molenaar⁴, Gerti Pishtari¹, Nikol Rummel⁵, Jörgen Sikk⁶, Wannapon Suraworachet², Kairit Tammets⁶, Paraskevi Topali⁴, Qi Zhou²

¹ Center for Digitalisation in Lifelong Learning, University for Continuing Education Krems, Austria

² UCL Knowledge Lab, University College London, UK

³ Learning and Educational Technology Research Lab (LET), University of Oulu, Finland

⁴ National Education Lab AI (NOLAI), Radboud University, The Netherlands

⁵ University of Bochum and Center for Advanced Internet Studies (CAIS), Germany

⁶ School of Digital Technologies, Tallinn University, Estonia

Abstract

Background: Rather than considering Artificial Intelligence as a technology for automating teaching tasks and replacing teachers, it is necessary to acknowledge the transformatory role technologies can have on work, teaching and learning practices in education.

Objective: Through the lens of recent models of hybrid intelligent systems and distributed cognition, we explore the impact that AI could have on the teaching profession.

Methods: We first propose a framework on the complementarity of teachers and AI that considers complementarity to emerge on the task, the skill and the job level when AI is meaningfully integrated into teaching and learning. The framework proposes a number of sociotechnical conditions that influence complementarity, such as how the AI tool is designed and deployed and how teachers are prepared. We then report results of a cross-case analysis of seven

cases involving over 150 teachers in a range of authentic applications of AI for the creation of educational strategies and materials, diagnosis of student learning and regulation of classroom activities.

Results and Conclusions: By applying the framework, we show how AI automates, complements and augments teaching tasks and thereby affects professional knowledge, skills and attitudes of teachers. Complementarity emerges as a result of a redistribution of tasks, knowledge and skills across the distributed cognitive system. By analysing characteristics of the AI tools used in the cases, characteristics of the teachers interacting with these and the specific deployment conditions, we derive a potential design space for future hybrid intelligent systems in education.

Practitioner Notes

- The use of AI in education often emphasises automation of teaching and learning tasks
- We propose a framework on how teachers and AI can complement each other
- Across seven authentic applications of AI, we show how complementarity emerges
- Complementarity is observable in cases where integration of AI is meaningful
- We propose some guidelines for hybrid intelligent systems that enhance complementarity

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, hybrid intelligent system, teacher

Introduction

Recent advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI), encompassing a range of data-driven and deep learning–based systems (including large language models based on pretrained transformers), have expanded the repertoire of tools available to students and teachers and have been rapidly integrated into classrooms across schools and universities. This development has intensified the discussion around the use of AI in education, despite the fact that various AI technologies have long been part of the educational toolset, such as intelligent tutoring systems, learning analytics platforms, and other data-driven technologies. Because these earlier AI technologies were typically embedded within educational platforms, they were usually aligned with pedagogical principles and explicitly designed to support learning and instruction. Despite this alignment, their adoption and classroom integration have remained a persistent challenge (e.g., Cukurova, Miao & Brooker, 2023).

In contrast, many contemporary AI tools, particularly conversational agents based on large language models (LLMs), have achieved broad uptake among both learners and teachers. However, because these systems are general-purpose technologies rather than education-specific tools, there is considerable uncertainty about how they should best be used to support teaching and learning in meaningful and responsible ways. The question of their educational use and impact is therefore far from trivial. LLMs can automate a range of cognitive tasks, including those typically classified as “higher-order thinking” (Fan et al., 2025). In the educational domain, for instance, they have demonstrated the capability to solve assessment tasks typically used at schools, such as those from the PISA for large-scale assessment. Similarly, they can automate the process of creating educational materials for particular student groups including assessment tasks and items (Li, Cukurova & Bulathwela, 2025).

The automatization of higher order cognitive tasks has raised concerns about the long-term effects of such automatization, especially for teaching and learning processes and outcomes (Dinsmore & Fryer, 2026). Research has raised concerns about effects on critical thinking (Lee et al, 2025), on metacognitive abilities, and cognitive engagement (Kosmyrna et al, 2025). In this paper, our primary focus is on teachers and how the growing use of AI shapes their professional roles, skills, and responsibilities. There is an agreement that in the age of AI, teacher roles would possibly grow in importance rather than decline. This is because of the important role that teachers play for the development of learners, which requires strong pedagogical and didactical knowledge as well as situated classroom expertise and the need to instruct learners in the productive use of AI in their lives. There is now a concern that because of the potential of automatization that AI possesses, responsibility for these critical developments may shift from the teacher to the AI. There is also a concern that by relying increasingly on AI, teachers may experience a decline in some of the skills that are critically important for making decisions about their learners’ development.

Although these questions about the effects of automatization have recently been raised because of the large-scale adoption of LLMs in education, it is important to note the questions

around automatization are not new. Reviewing of the large body of research on AI tools in education (mostly prior to LLMs), Ley et al. (2023) show that in many intelligent learning systems used in classroom instructions, the role of teachers and how they interact with the system is not explicitly considered. For example, intelligent tutoring systems have traditionally left teachers out of the loop, and only recently have been enhanced through approaches like open learner models or human-centered or model-based Learning Analytics to be more open towards educators.

In this paper we pose broader questions about automatization in teaching and learning that are not tied to any specific current AI technology but instead consider a future in which AI is increasingly integrated into diverse educational tools and practices. Our central assumption is that, as in other domains, the focus will shift from AI as replacement for human functions toward the complementarity of teachers and AI within what is often called “hybrid intelligent systems” in education. Because of their advanced cognitive capabilities, AI technologies are likely to have a more fundamental impact on education, which calls for a more systemic perspective that needs go beyond task-level support and considers the evolving roles, relationships, and responsibilities of teachers and learners in technology-enhanced learning environments.

Our aim with this research was therefore to identify complementarities of teachers and AI when interacting with intelligent learning technology and derive possible determinants for these complementarities. We explored the following research questions:

- RQ1: What are some of the complementarities on the task level that can be observed in authentic educational settings?
- RQ2: What are some of the complementarities on the skill level when AI is used in authentic educational settings?
- RQ3: What are some of the sociotechnical conditions of complementarity that originate in the characteristics of the teacher, the AI, or the deployment of AI?

Complementarity of teachers and AI in the hybrid intelligent system

Towards Hybrid Intelligent Systems in Education

The use of AI in educational settings has been proliferating for some years. Learner-focused AI has found its way into classrooms (e.g., intelligent tutoring systems (Du Boulay, 2016), universities (Bond et al, 2024) and training institutions (Ley, 2020). Only more recently has the role of teaching staff in an AI-supported learning environment come into greater focus. Most available AI aims - intentionally or unintentionally - to replace certain tasks of teachers rather than providing explicit design and deployment affordances that would complement teachers' everyday practice and allow them to complete tasks more efficiently and effectively. A recent review identified deficits in addressing the role of teaching staff in the application of AI across all educational domains (Ley et al., 2023). These trends point to a structural imbalance in

current AI-in-education research and practice: while AI systems are increasingly embedded in learning environments, their alignment with teachers' professional reasoning and decision-making remains underdeveloped.

Emerging evidence indicates that AI tools can, for instance, foster teachers' situation-specific skills, which leads to positive outcomes for student learning. For instance, Aslan et al. (2019) found that a real-time student engagement dashboard improved classroom management, leading to increased teacher support and reduced student boredom compared to non-AI classrooms. Similarly, Holstein et al. (2018) observed positive learning outcomes using an adaptive tutoring system and a mixed-reality dashboard that helped teachers understand student progress.

These examples, in which teachers dynamically share tasks and decisions with an AI-based system, and the AI augments teachers' skills, have been termed Hybrid Intelligent Systems (Cukurova et al, 2019; Holstein, Alevan & Rummel, 2020; Molenaar, 2022a). However, while there are examples of hybrid intelligent systems that focus on AI-student complementarity (Molenaar, 2022b), evidence on the effects of AI on teachers is limited, especially in authentic classroom settings (Kasepalu et al, 2024; Ley et al, 2023).

Complementarity of teachers and AI in the Hybrid Intelligent System

Teaching is increasingly recognized as a multi-layered professional practice that comprises interrelated elements shaping how educators design, enact and adapt instruction (Darling-Hammond & Bransford, 2005). This professional practice encompasses tasks, skills, and underlying dispositions. Teaching involves core instructional tasks such as planning lessons, facilitating learning activities, assessing students' understanding, and reflecting outcomes. These tasks are supported by a diverse set of professional skills and knowledge, including domain knowledge, pedagogical reasoning, and technological fluency, as outlined in the TPACK framework (Mishra & Koehler, 2006). Teachers draw on situation-specific skills, such as perceiving cues in classroom interactions, interpreting them based on pedagogical knowledge, and making adaptive decisions (Blömeke & Kaiser, 2017) At a more implicit level, attitudes and beliefs, such as trust in technology, sense of agency and conceptions of student learning, shape how teachers enact their professional judgement.

Complementarity of teachers and AI has been studied from three perspectives: a job-level, task-level, and skill-based perspective. The *job-level perspective* has examined occupational databases (O*NET) to classify tasks within various professions as being either irreplaceable (bottleneck) or automatable (Lassébie, & Quintini, 2022). In these studies, teachers are considered to have a low to intermediate risk of automation, given a lower proportion of highly automatable tasks. However, the recent emergence of Generative AI challenges this assessment (Lassébie, & Quintini, 2022). The fact that a task *can* be automated does not necessarily mean that it *should* be automated. Instead, a job-level perspective needs to consider the long-term implications, aligning with education's goal of fostering positive human

development. While the job-level perspective recognises the complementarity of humans and AI in the teaching profession, it has certain limitations: It treats tasks and technology as static, overlooks worker-technology interaction, and depends on specific deployment conditions (Milanez, 2023), thus potentially underestimating the transformative potential of AI in teaching.

The *task-level perspective* therefore focuses on the transformation of tasks. Complementarity of human and AI agents on the task level is defined as a situation where a task is performed more successfully by the two agents working together, rather than by each one separately. To achieve complementarity, there needs to be a sharing of certain aspects of the task. An example is the “6 layers of automation” model as proposed by Molenaar et al (2022a), which specifies the division of control between teachers and AI and is used to describe how AI technologies replace, complement, and augment teachers' roles. Replacement occurs when tasks are taken over by the AI,

i.e. highly automatable items; complementarity occurs when teachers' tasks and those of AI are aligned, resulting in reciprocal interaction with each executing specific tasks; and augmented tasks are those in which teachers' skills are enriched by AI to enact new tasks to transform teaching and learning. This model has also been used to describe how teachers use the same AI technology differently, with some replacing and others choosing to complement or even augment. Hence, task-level models offer the possibility to differentiate between different AI tools or deployment conditions. At the same time, these have been tested in narrow tasks (such as implementing personalised learning in classroom instruction), and mainly focusing on task-level impact such as time spent on different teaching tasks (van Leeuwen et al, 2021), the quality of teaching plans (Pishtari et al, 2024), or teachers' cognitive load (Pozdniakov et al, 2022). However, the reasons for these differences need to be understood on the level of skills and knowledge.

Besides shaping what teachers *do*, the use of AI also has implications for teachers' knowledge, skills, and attitudes. As such, AI-enhanced systems, such as teacher dashboards (Tammets & Ley, 2023; van Leeuwen et al, 2021) can enhance teachers' ability to perceive and interpret classroom dynamics and through that support the development of situation-specific reasoning. Additionally, tools like intelligent tutoring systems or adaptive learning platforms can impact teachers' knowledge, requiring new forms of technological integration into subject-specific pedagogy. Research by Celik (2023) for instance has suggested that a higher level of familiarity with AI tools contributes to a better understanding of the pedagogical functions of AI tools. Beyond technical fluency, however, the integration of AI requires teachers to develop new ways of thinking and feeling about their role as teachers which encompasses motivational and affective dimensions. This enables us to explain why some teachers may embrace AI in some contexts and resist in others, and how AI design can align with it to foster teaching expertise. These aspects can be summarized under a *skill-based perspective* on teacher-AI complementarity that explains the long-term consequences of offloading certain tasks to AI, rather than others.

Taken together, all three perspectives (job-level, task- and skill-based) need to be taken into

account to gain a comprehensive understanding of the effects of AI on the teaching profession. Moreover, decisions about automating teaching tasks reflect more fundamental beliefs about what aspects of education should remain human-led (Karumbaiah et al, 2023), and therefore questions of a societal and ethical concern also need to be addressed.

A Sociotechnical view on Teacher-AI Complementarity

A more comprehensive and systemic view on the role of AI in teaching and learning acknowledges that introducing AI may lead to a redistribution of tasks, knowledge, skills and responsibilities between teachers and AI. Because education is highly sensitive societal domain with long-term consequences for young people, this redistribution raises significant ethical and societal concerns. This is reflected in the recent European AI Act that flags many uses of AI in education as high-risk.

To address these aspects, we propose to a view complementarity as emerging from within a socio-technical system that considers the determinants of teacher-AI complementarity and examines these determinants and their adaptation and development in authentic educational settings. We draw on a number of conceptualizations that have been applied to understand socio-technical systems in education. First, the use of intelligent technology in education has been considered from the perspective of models of distributed cognition (Cukurova & Luckin, 2019) that consider the distribution of cognitive processing across human actors and artificial agents. It is assumed that a coupling of human and machine intelligence is achieved by a distribution of representations across internal cognitive states and external artefacts. The coupling creates a distributed cognitive system that can complete tasks by propagating cognitive states across these representations. A recent concept suggested in the intelligent learning systems research is that of “model-based learning analytics” which assumes that those representations are formed by pedagogical and psychological models of learning and instruction that mediate interpretation and decision making in the cognitive system (Ley, 2020; Ley et al, 2023).

The view of a distributed cognitive system foregrounds the *interaction of teachers and AI* in authentic situations that will then lead to complementarity emerging on different levels (see the inner box of Figure 1). At the same time, these interactions do not happen in isolation, but instead are embedded into a *sociocultural context* in which cognitive representations act as cultural products and mediate human activity (Alaimo, 2024) and are also key for understanding and supporting professional learning (Billett, 2021). The outer boxes in Figure 1 present some of the important elements of this sociocultural context which, according to conceptions of human activity systems, encompass aspects of the subject (the teacher), the tool (AI) and the community, its rules and division of labour which we denote here as the deployment conditions. The framework depicted in Figure 1 bridges the cognitive and sociocultural spheres and has provided the basis for our analysis of complementarity. Its elements will therefore be described in more detail next. The framework has been previously presented in [BLINDED], and is being continuously updated based on empirical studies and literature reviews.

Figure 1: A Sociotechnical perspective on Teacher-AI Complementarity in the Hybrid Intelligent System

Key dimensions of complementarity: re-distribution of tasks, skills and job demands

Core aspects of the complementarity in the hybrid intelligent system are listed in the middle box. First, AI integration can influence certain *teaching tasks* are performed. Repetitive tasks may be *automated*, such as correcting math exercises, where AI can take over, and a teacher can rely on AI for instant, accurate results. Complex tasks, on the other hand, will be complemented or augmented, rather than replaced. For example, when managing group work in the classroom, AI tools can *complement* the teacher in monitoring each group’s progress in real time, alerting the teacher when a group seems to be off-track or a student is not engaged, and suggesting pedagogical interventions. Such recommendations can show *augmentation* of a task, if both the teacher’s view and input provided by the AI-tool are considered. AI can also provide inspiration for tasks that deal with the production of materials, tasks, or lesson plans. For example, AI provides feedback about a lesson plan or suggests elements to add to it and learn from evidence-based models, thereby *augmenting* the learning design process.

As knowledge-based technology, AI also has profound implications for our understanding of teaching and learning and thus the *knowledge, skills, beliefs, and attitudes* of teachers. We therefore examine teachers' technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge, situation-

specific skills, and beliefs and attitudes. Central to our exploration of teacher knowledge is the TPACK framework, which guides analysis of how AI intersects with content, pedagogical, and technological knowledge to foster teaching effectiveness. Teachers may develop knowledge on what effective feedback is, on the role of metacognition in collaborative learning, or on how to prepare engaging lessons. For cognitive skills, it is helpful to draw upon framework proposed by Blömeke & Kaiser (2017) to incorporate teachers' situation-specific skills, such as perceiving cues in the classroom and drawing on them to interpret and make situation-specific decisions. These interact with the capabilities of AI when used in the classroom, for example when teacher dashboards make student learning transparent or suggest actions to be taken. AI can enhance teachers' awareness by aiding in monitoring and understanding students' thought processes. This integration of insights can improve instructional practices, as teachers with advanced metacognitive skills are better equipped to manage their cognitive processes, resulting in more effective teaching and efficient student learning (Duffy et al, 2009).

Finally, on the *job level*, there may also be profound changes. As the teaching profession evolves, with changes in workload, decreasing job satisfaction, and a decline in the perceived attractiveness of the profession, it is essential to explore how AI can complement these shifting dynamics. From analysing the impact of AI on the evolving demands on teachers through these authentic cases, the need for teacher upskilling and changes in their role are visible, such as a stronger focus on supporting their students learning. Likewise, the potential for new job profiles can be considered (such as learning designers) and role of AI in contributing to career sustainability (Kong et al, 2023).

The sociocultural context of complementarity: determinants in the socio-technical system

While complementarity can be described in terms of how AI supports or reshapes tasks, skills and job roles, the framework also identifies a set of contextual and systemic factors that explains how this complementarity plays out in practice: a) The properties of the AIED system; b) The characteristics of the teacher and c) The conditions of deployment (see Figure 1).

The *design and functionality of an AI system* – what it observes, how it processes data, and the feedback it provides – play a crucial role in shaping its complementarity with teaching practices. Transparent, interpretable models aligned with established educational constructs (e.g., the ICAP model or domain-specific models) enable teachers to make informed decisions. In contrast, decontextualised systems risk disrupting instructional flow and undermining trust. What task the AI performs and how it communicates with the teacher determines whether it serves to replace, augment, or complement specific teaching tasks.

Complementarity also depends on *what teachers bring into the interaction* – their pedagogical beliefs, professional experience and experience to engage with TEL tools and willingness to engage with system recommendations. For instance, teachers with strong interpretive and reflective capacities may use AI outputs to improve their instruction, whereas others may reject AI guidance depending on their trust in the system or perceived threat to autonomy. As

some of the studies suggest [14], individual differences in cognitive, emotional and motivational aspects toward AI are rather important to how appropriate it is in practice.

Finally, *the way AI is introduced and embedded* in the learning environment also influences its effectiveness and integration. Alignment with instructional goals, training and support, organizational environment and the granularity of AI feedback, all affect how teachers interact with the system. Complementarity is more likely when AI is part of coherent instructional design, rather than an add-on feature. Professional learning and co-design processes can act as enabling conditions that help teachers develop the judgement and skills needed to navigate hybrid systems. Technological deployment conditions such as the technological readiness or support play a major role.

Methods

We conducted a cross-case synthesis of seven case studies that examined teachers' use of AI tools in authentic educational settings. Taking the framework of Teacher-AI Complementarity as a guiding lens into the cases, the goal was to collect initial insights into task level, skill-level complementarity and the effect of deployment conditions. We did not focus on job-level complementarity in this study.

Selection of cases

Cases were selected to maximize the variation across **teaching tasks** (creation, regulation, diagnosis), **pedagogical approaches** (e.g. tutoring, project- and problem-based learning collaborative learning, metacognition), **educational levels** (primary, secondary, higher and continuing education) and **AI tool types** (e.g., dashboards, intelligent tutoring, conversational/GenAI agents). All cases reported empirical data on teacher-AI interaction, enabling analysis of complementarity as enacted in practice. Inclusion required that the case reported observed interaction (e.g., classroom observation, think-aloud, interviews, or interaction logs) and provided detail to identify task division and teacher reasoning around AI outputs.

Table 1: Cases Selected for the Cross-case Analysis

Case 1: Lesson design with GenAI (TLU)	Context: Secondary Education Task Type: Creation
<p>Teaching context: This case focused on in-service teachers using a generative AI tool to support lesson design in several subject areas. Teachers engaged in design activities, using AI to generate lesson structures, activity ideas, contextual examples, and draft instructional materials. The design task required alignment with curriculum standards, learner characteristics, and pedagogical principles such as engagement, inclusion, and alignment with the curriculum.</p>	
<p>AI tool: Commercially available generative AI tools (e.g., ChatGPT, Gemini, Copilot, Canva AI) were used. These systems generated lesson structures, contextual examples, and draft materials in response to prompts. However, they did not include built-in pedagogical validation, curricular alignment checks, or reflective scaffolding. Outputs were opportunistic and dependent on prompt quality.</p>	
<p>Role of Teachers: Teachers functioned as critical instructional designers. They monitored coherence, pacing, and learner fit; interpreted outputs through pedagogical and content knowledge; and frequently modified or rejected suggestions. AI supported idea generation and drafting, while pedagogical alignment, contextual adaptation, and ethical responsibility remained teacher-driven.</p>	
Case 2: Diagnostic decision making in an intelligent Math tutor (RUB)	Context: Primary Education Task Type: Diagnosis
<p>Teaching Context: An intelligent tutoring system (ITS) designed to enhance mathematical competencies in primary and lower secondary education is used to adaptively support mathematics learning. The ITSs adaptive algorithm continuously assesses students' progress and adjusts the difficulty of tasks according to students' needs. Students receive just-in-time feedback on their work along with additional scaffolding and hints.</p>	
<p>AI Tool: The ITS adjusts task difficulty and provides just-in-time feedback to students. A teacher-facing dashboard visualized performance patterns, progress trajectories, and alerts for struggling students. The system provided structured summaries but required interpretation.</p>	
<p>Role of Teachers: Teacher's role shifts from direct observation of students to interpreting student-AI interaction data. The dashboard augmented perception and supported interpretation of student needs. However, teachers differed in how deeply they engaged with the data: some validated their own observations, while others relied more heavily on alerts. Diagnostic decision-making remained teacher-led.</p>	
Case 3: Giving feedback in project-based learning (RU-GenAI)	Context: Secondary Education Task Type: Creation

Teaching Context: In secondary schools, teachers often use project-based teaching to help students understand complex topics in diverse topics such as STEM, history, or geography. Instead of just memorizing and repeating facts, the students research a topic, plan and design a solution, and write a report. These types of assignments boost student creativity, and assess the new knowledge learned applied into realistic scenarios.

AI system characteristics: The AI chatbot guided teachers through a structured dialogue to develop feedback plans to develop project-based teaching (Topali et al, 2025). It suggests feedback interventions based on contextual inputs such as student skill level, task complexity, and learning objectives. The system embedded theoretical feedback principles but relied on teacher-provided context.

Role of Teachers: Teachers will use this tool mostly in the lesson preparation by contributing with contextual, content and pedagogical knowledge. The AI expands the range of feedback options and structured reflection, prompting teachers to reconsider habitual feedback strategies. Teachers evaluate and select appropriate feedback interventions, retaining final decision authority.

Case 4: Supporting socially shared regulation in higher education (UCL)	Context: Higher Education Task Type: Regulation
Teaching Context: This case study focuses on the context of postgraduate collaborative learning classrooms with multiple student groups. It aims to enhance students' collaboration and regulatory skills by providing post-hoc insights into group interactions and their challenges along with the regulation of learning detected during group activities.	
AI system characteristics: A collaboration analytics dashboard analyzed verbal and non-verbal interaction data using machine learning and rule-based models. It visualized group challenges, regulatory processes, and engagement indicators and generated feedback suggestions. Teachers could adjust thresholds and personalize feedback.	
Role of Teachers: The developed AI system aims to complement teachers' ability to perceive, interpret and strategically adapt their interventions and learning design in supporting collaboration skills and socially shared regulations of learning.	
Case 5: Inviting metacognitive awareness in collaborative science learning (OULU)	Context: Secondary Education Task Type: Regulation
Teaching Context: MAI is a Metacognitive AI agent designed to detect disruptions in collaborative learning which require regulation and to invite metacognitive awareness through spoken prompts. MAI was implemented in secondary school science classrooms across multiple sessions [10].	
AI system characteristics: The Metacognitive AI (MAI) agent used speech recognition and rule-based detection of regulatory triggers (Järvelä, & Hadwin, 2024). It delivered pre-scripted spoken prompts to encourage reflection and regulation. The system did not provide answers or content-level feedback.	
Role of Teachers: Designed for classroom environments with multiple small groups, MAI eases teacher oversight while promoting student-driven regulation. MAI does not provide answers but aims to strengthen students' metacognitive skills while easing the teacher's role in overseeing multiple groups during collaborative tasks and understanding group learning processes letting teacher to focus more on pedagogical expertise.	
Case 6: Practicing learning Design in Continuing Education (UWK)	Context: Continuing Education Task Type: Creation
Teaching Context: The case focuses on trainers and learning designers who create courses for continuing education and training settings, for example courses on learning analytics for educational professionals. These trainers create learning designs for engaging courses, need to consider the varying background of learners and the newest developments in the field and ensure alignment of learning designs with pedagogical goals of the curriculum.	
AI system characteristics: The AI system analyzed lesson plans, checked alignment	

between goals and activities, and generated structured feedback. It used semantic analysis and automated classification to evaluate pedagogical coherence.

Role of Teachers: The tool mainly seeks to augment the learning design process by enhancing the teachers' ability to plan and design meaningful learning activities. It is expected that by providing direct feedback, learning design skills will be enhanced and practiced.

Case 7: Planning a Differentiated, Curriculum Adaptive Math Lesson (RU)

Context: Primary
School Task Type:
Diagnosis

Teaching Context: Teachers review students' progress in mathematics lessons, select learning objectives, differentiate the learning experience and decide how to group students who need additional instruction or practice on a given learning goal.

AI system characteristics: Snappet Copilot used predictive analytics to suggest learning goals and student groupings within a teacher-facing dashboard. Teachers could inspect, adjust, accept, or override suggestions.

Role of Teachers: The tool supports data driven differentiation, but teachers remain responsible for pedagogical decisions. Teachers interpret and evaluate AI recommendations using their curriculum knowledge and knowledge of students, cross check suggestions against class status and progress information, and decide whether to accept or revise the proposed lesson objectives and student groupings. The tool therefore aims to complement yet could also augment (depending on the teacher's experience) teacher's practice of scheduling differentiated math lessons.

Data collection

Across all cases, primary data was collected, and focus was placed on the interactions of teachers with AI tools. In all cases, interactive group-based or individual sessions were organized in which teachers interacted with the tools. The sessions were guided and observed by researchers. In the individual sessions, teachers interacted with the tools and a think aloud protocol was followed in which teachers were asked to state for each step in the use process of their reasoning. These sessions were audio recorded, and synchronized screen recordings were taken. At the same time, researchers took observational field notes. In the group sessions, teachers were guided through particular tasks using the tool at their individual computers. In all cases, interviews and questionnaires were also used after the interaction.

In some cases, data was complemented by the analysis of the artefacts created (e.g. the resulting lesson plans created) or by the interaction logs or chat protocols resulting from the interaction. In all cases, the tasks in which teachers were observed were guided by researchers, but it was ensured that the tasks were meaningful for teachers and aligned with their usual expectations. Table 2 gives an overview of all cases, data collection methods used and number of teachers involved. Across all cases, over 150 teachers were involved in the study.

There was a need in this study to define observable evidence for when an episode was identified as involving *complementarity in teacher-AI interactions*. In prior work on human-AI complementarity (e.g. Riedl & Weidmann, 2025), successful complementarity was primarily defined in terms of performance or outcomes, whether human and AI together perform better than either could alone. While valuable, this perspective tends to treat the interaction itself as a “black box.” Our approach focuses on the quality of the interaction process between teachers and AI. By drawing on observations, think-aloud protocols, interviews in the cases, we were able to examine how complementarity was enacted, supported, or hindered in real educational settings. In this study, the following indicators of high levels of (successful) complementarity were used and triangulated across data sources:

- *Integration into instructional flow:* AI outputs were incorporated into teaching decisions or lesson design (e.g., adapting tasks, targeting feedback), or explicitly evaluated as useful by teachers.
- *Teacher sensemaking and critical engagement:* Teachers actively interpreted AI outputs (e.g., checking rationale, contextualizing with knowledge of students or curriculum, modifying or rejecting recommendations with justification).
- *Reciprocal or shared use of contextual information:* AI tools appropriately incorporated teacher-provided

contextual information (e.g., prompts, student characteristics, task constraints) into their recommendations.

The following indicators of lower (limited or unsuccessful) complementarity were used:

- *Disruption or non-use*: AI outputs disrupted instructional flow, were ignored, or were judged inappropriate or irrelevant.
- *Uncritical delegation*: Teachers accepted AI recommendations without evidence of evaluation or contextualization, suggesting limited added value of teacher involvement at the task level.
- *Context misalignment*: AI tools misused or failed to incorporate teacher-provided contextual information, leading to recommendations misaligned with classroom realities

We interpret uncritical delegation and context misalignment as indicators of reduced task-level complementarity, as they signal weak coordination between human and AI representations within a distributed cognitive system. Importantly, these indicators capture interaction processes rather than learning outcomes, enabling analytic comparison across heterogeneous cases.

Based on the collected materials and identified episode of complementarity, researchers involved in each of the cases prepared short descriptions of teacher-AI interaction episodes. Each episode was described in terms of the task division between teachers and AI, teacher reasoning and decision-making processes shaping AI use and the specific deployment conditions that shaped the complementarity. For each of these categories, researchers were given prompts extracted from the framework to guide writing of the episodes (e.g. “*What is the knowledge and the skills brought in by teacher and AI to complete the task and how do they interact*” for skill-level complementarity). Researchers also added specific evidence (such as quotes from interviews or observations) to these descriptions.

Table 2: Data collection methods and teachers involvement across cases

Case	Data collection methods	Number of teachers involved
1	Structured think-aloud lesson-planning sessions with generative AI (45–75 min); audio recordings and synchronized screen recordings.	8 teachers (primary & secondary)
2	Online think-aloud with a tutoring system; audio and screen recordings; followed by semi-structured interview and questionnaire.	9 teachers (primary & secondary)
3	Teacher think-alouds, questionnaires, observations; focus group and co-design workshop.	16 teachers (8 in focus group + 8 in co-design; secondary)
4	Three workshops with prototypes; open-ended questionnaires and observations; thematic analysis.	49 participants in total across three workshops; mostly university staff/PG students
5	5 week in-classroom intervention study in 12 classrooms followed by individual interviews with teachers	3 secondary school teachers, approximately 150 students
6	Workshops, content and thematic analysis of chatbot interactions; quantitative questionnaire analysis; analysis of digital traces; observations/interviews.	28 workshop participants (13 Austria + 15 Mexico) incl. 7 interviewed/observed
7	Think-aloud lesson-planning sessions with AI; interviews and observations; hierarchical task analysis and workflow diagrams	42 teachers total (19 in think-alouds + 23 in validation workshop; primary)

Cross-case analysis

For the cross-case analysis, the case level descriptions were then subjected to a qualitative content analysis by the main author and cross-checked by the other authors. The teacher-AI complementarity framework was used as an analytical lens. Each teacher-AI interaction episode was coded along three dimensions: *task-level complementarity* (how well human and AI coordinated to complete specific instructional tasks), *skill-level complementarity* (how AI use related to the exercise, development or decline of teachers' professional skills, as well as conditions under which human–AI complementarity was strengthened or weakened across contexts. For each dimension, we looked for recurring patterns and assigned sub-categories along the categories proposed by the framework, or created new categories.

Results

RQ1: Task-level complementarity: sharing of task responsibility

Types of teaching tasks covered in the cases

Prior work on human-AI complementarity distinguishes between creation-oriented tasks and decision-making tasks (e.g. Vaccaro et al., 2024). However, in our cases decision-making tasks differed substantially in temporality (when the decisions are made in the instructional process) and epistemic demands (what kind of knowledge and reasoning is required), we split the decision-making tasks into *regulation tasks*, which involve real-time classroom orchestration

and *diagnosis tasks*, which involve interpreting evidence about student learning. Regulation tasks align with the research on classroom management (e.g. Wolff, et al. 2021), whereas the diagnosis task related to the area of educational assessment (e.g. Gardner et al. 2021).

We identified three primary task types:

- *Creation Tasks*: involved designing lesson plans and learning materials for specific topics and learner groups within curricular constraints (Cases 1, 3, 6). These tasks required integrating general pedagogical and content knowledge with highly contextual knowledge about students and institutional conditions. The generation and refinement of feedback constituted a subset of creation tasks, as it mediates student learning and requires the integration of pedagogical, content, and contextual knowledge.
- *Regulation Tasks*: The monitoring of instructional situations in real time and making of minute-to-minute decisions to adapt to the learning environment and optimize student learning. Examples were the guiding of group work in secondary (case 5) and higher education (case 4), as well as the decisions about individual student support (case 2).
- *Diagnosis Tasks*: The diagnosis of student learning progress and potential barriers to suggest corrective actions. Examples were the monitoring of student learning progress in adaptive learning systems to suggest hints, adapt the task difficulty (case 2) or differentiate students into different groups (case 7).

These task types were not mutually exclusive; for instance, diagnostic insights in Case 7 informed subsequent lesson design decisions, illustrating interdependencies between diagnosis and creation.

Observed Complementarities: shared task responsibility

Across cases, we did not observe extensive full automation of teaching tasks. Instead, complementarity primarily took the form of distributed task responsibility, with AI systems performing information-intensive or routine sub- tasks and teachers retaining responsibility for contextual judgment and pedagogical decision making.

In *creation tasks*, AI systems primarily supported generative drafting and large-scale idea generation, such as proposing lesson structures (Case 1). AI also structured tasks according to good practices in instructional design (Case 6¹) and feedback provision (3) and differentiation (7). AI also detected and flagged inconsistencies with these good practices. Teachers' roles were around critical oversight, quality assurance, judging suitability to the context, and final decision making. This oversight was visible when teachers explicitly rejected AI suggestions that did not align with their pedagogical values: “*Completing a worksheet is one of the most boring tasks... so I won't do it*” (Case 1, Teacher 2). Similarly, teachers treated AI-generated differentiation suggestions as provisional: “*Sometimes there are children suggested [by the AI]*”

of whom I think, yeah, they should be there... Or sometimes there is someone there that shouldn't be there" (Case 7, Teacher 4).

In *regulation tasks*, AI was tasked with monitoring individual students (2) or learner groups (4, 5) in real-time. AI also provides standard interventions directly to students, such as suggesting certain metacognitive regulation strategies to groups of students (5). Teachers are free to make decisions about more complex interventions or content level support. As one teacher explained, the AI helped manage distributed attention demands: *"It helps guide the students' collaboration, especially in those moments I don't have time to be everywhere"* (Case 5, Teacher 1). Teachers described how AI prompts maintained focus without replacing their role: *"It kind of acts as a helper, a guide... something that could help keep the rhythm and maintain focus on the task"* (Case 5, Teacher 2). In other cases, teachers can review the feedback suggestion, to be sent to students, and adapt it before it is given to students (4).

Diagnosis tasks were mainly related to diagnosing student learning from their task performance (2) and historical patterns (7). The *diagnosis* was a precursor for decisions, either on the class level (e.g. planning of differentiated lessons) (7) or on the individual student level (e.g. suggesting corrective feedback, hints or task progression) (2). AI gathers data on task performance and on a bigger *variety* of other data. AI then performs summaries of this data to *suggest* a diagnosis, or a prediction, and suggests grouping (7). Teachers oversee the suggestions and make final decisions. Many teachers use *the* information provided as a complement to their own understanding about the students (2). Teachers emphasized that the dashboard expanded their perceptual access: *"I wouldn't have this overview, and secondly, I wouldn't be able to discuss with the students because I wouldn't know where they stand"*

¹ Numbers in brackets denote the case in Table 1.

(Case 2, Teacher 5). However, this complementary use was moderated by time constraints: *“When I do not trust the AI’s suggestions, I go and review the student data again. However, when I’m out of time, I more often accept the AI’s suggestions”* (Case 7, Teacher 1)

Together, these findings suggest that task-level complementarity in education is not only structured by task type (creation vs decision-making), but also when decisions are made in the teaching process and by the complexity of pedagogical reasoning needed, with AI mainly supporting large-scale data processing and teachers keeping the responsibility for context-sensitive pedagogical judgement.

RQ2: Skill-level Complementarity: interaction of knowledge and skills

The distribution of tasks in the cases we examined was accompanied by a redistribution of professional knowledge and skills across teachers and AI systems. We analysed teacher-AI interactions in terms of how pedagogical, content, and technological knowledge (TPACK), including AI-specific technological knowledge (AI-TPACK), and situation-specific skills were represented and coordinated across human and artificial agents.

Technological, Pedagogical and Content knowledge (TPACK and AI-TPACK)

Teachers deployed **pedagogical knowledge** when interacting with AI tools, particularly in instructional design (1, 6), differentiation (7), feedback (3), and metacognitive support (3). Teachers reasoned about the lesson coherence, pacing and instructional strategies when reviewing AI-generated lesson plans and recommendations and some reported adopting AI-suggested pedagogical strategies in their practice. For example, one teacher described incorporating AI-generated metacognitive prompts in classroom practice: *“I try to give my students prompts like the ones [the AI tool] said, like, read the assignment again, or ‘look, let’s see if we can find some help in the book’, because I’m sure they were just confused, and they didn’t follow the instructions. I give prompts like that too.”* [Case 5, Teacher 1]

Content knowledge and curriculum knowledge were central in **creation and diagnostic tasks**. Teachers explicated subject-matter and curricular knowledge when interacting with AI systems, which attempted to integrate these inputs with formal domain models and student performance data to generate instructional recommendations (Cases 1, 3, 6, 7). Teachers critically evaluated these AI-generated suggestions using their contextual knowledge of students’ prior knowledge and classroom dynamics. For example, a teacher explained how student background knowledge shaped instructional decisions: *“I have to base my decisions on whether I have students with narrow or broad mathematics”,* Case 1, Teacher 3).

In **diagnostic and regulation tasks**, teachers also evaluated AI-generated grouping and intervention suggestions using their knowledge of individual students: *“I press the plus button [...] it is practice for the children who need extra practice, and [the AI] has this figured out for*

me. I'll take a look. Sometimes there are children suggested [by the AI] of whom I think, yeah, they should be there [the practice].

Technological knowledge, including AI-specific knowledge related to system functioning and interpretability, was required to understand and appropriately use AI outputs. Interaction with AI-specific technological knowledge was uneven; in one case, teachers adjusted criteria used by the AI to generate alerts or feedback, illustrating emerging AI-TPACK practices (Case 4).

Situation Specific Skills

Situation Specific Skills explain how knowledge that teachers or the AI possess is used in specific contextual creation, regulation or diagnosis tasks. In those situations, AI is not only a passive source of information but increasingly participates in perceiving cues, structuring interpretations, and shaping decision processes.

In our cases, dashboards supported perception by alerting teachers to struggling students (Case 2) or identifying challenging moments in collaborative work (Case 4), thereby complementing teachers' own classroom awareness. Teachers described how this enhanced overview enabled more targeted pedagogical action: *"I wouldn't have this overview, and secondly, I wouldn't be able to discuss with the students because I wouldn't know where they stand"* (Case 2, Teacher 5).

Importantly, situation-specific skills were also enacted during pedagogical design, not only during classroom orchestration. In the lesson design case (Case 1), teachers monitored AI-generated lesson structures for coherence, pacing, learner relevance, and curricular alignment, interpreted AI outputs through pedagogical and content knowledge, and iteratively refined prompts and lesson plans. For example, teachers rejected AI generated worksheets and requested alternative contexts when activities lacked relevance for students, demonstrating perception–interpretation–decision cycles during design-time interaction with AI.

In creation tasks, the AI tools aided especially interpretation and reasoning, as teachers were observed to apply pedagogical reasoning about suitability of certain student tasks. They critically reviewed AI suggested activities (7, 6, 1). Teachers reported heightened need for pedagogical judgment, but they also reported better understanding of pedagogical strategies, such as differentiation (7).

Together, these findings indicate that AI systems in hybrid educational settings do not only support task execution but also support core cognitive processes of teaching. Professional knowledge and situation-specific skills are distributed across human and artificial agents, with AI contributing to perception and (data-informed) interpretation and teachers maintain responsibility for contextual pedagogical judgement and decision-making.

RQ3: Conditions for Complementarity

The level of complementarity that we observed in these cases was dependent on several sociotechnical conditions. Our analysis gives first evidence about some of those conditions. Following our framework, we looked at the characteristics of the teachers, characteristics of the AI tool and model, and characteristics of the deployment conditions (Table 3).

Table 3: Deployment conditions with a potential impact on complementarity

Teacher Characteristics	
Professional knowledge and reasoning capacity	Level of TPACK, curriculum knowledge, pedagogical reasoning skills and knowledge about students shaped how deeply teachers engaged with AI outputs (1,4,7). Teachers with stronger pedagogical reasoning more actively evaluated, modified and contextualized AI suggestions
Technical AI knowledge	Interest in underlying system functioning and understanding of AI mechanisms supported more deliberate engagement (2), Data literacy and AI literacy were relevant mainly in dashboard-based systems (4,7).
Attitude and trust towards AI	Attitudes ranges from openness to caution: <i>"I wouldn't mind at all if I actually had some kind of AI agents in the classroom"</i> (Case 5, Teacher)

	1), while others remained skeptical about the adequacy of AI-detected features for pedagogical decision-making (Case 4).
Prior experience and representational expectations	Prior experiences with AI shaped expectations about system behavior (2,5,6). E.g. Teachers were seen to adapt the use of the tool to fit their pre-existing practice, e.g. focusing on whole class vs. focusing on struggling students only (2) Or in Case 5, some expected answer-providing systems (e.g., Siri-like behavior), which misaligned with regulation-oriented prompts (<i>"I guess the impression was that even though it was said that MAI doesn't give answers, It was assumed that it was a bit like Siri or Alexa, that when you asked a question, it would give you an answer. But MAI didn't respond"</i> (Case 5, teacher 2). In Case 6, teachers expected open-ended interaction but later expressed preference for more structured dialogue.
Characteristics of the AI System	
Complexity of the output / interface	In case 2, information became harder to interpret with larger groups, interface complexity influences usability and depth of engagement. As one teacher noted, usability decreased with scale: <i>"The group was just quite large... That makes it easier to keep track of things, of course"</i> (Case 2, Teacher 4).
Pedagogical alignment of the AI output	The alignment of output was a strong factor: When it was missing (1) or too broad and lacking detail (4) or lacking transparency (7), it led to less complementarity. In other cases, it guided the teacher better to give feedback on metacognition (5), or when guiding their instructional design process (6). Moreover, AI tools were observed to lose context from one interaction to the next (1,5), which led to interruptions in the pedagogical flow.
Transparency	Loss of contextual continuity across interactions (1,5) interrupted pedagogical flow. Teachers reported fragmented system behavior: <i>"Somehow prompts remained quite isolated... even though it follows the conversation, it doesn't fully understand it"</i> (Case 5, Teacher 3). One teacher explained: <i>"When the algorithm is not transparent, I am checking all the data, so it adds to the workload"</i> (Case 7).

Characteristics of the Deployment Conditions

Organisational and policy conditions

Licensing and access structures	In case 2, access to the AI-supported tutoring system depended on licensing fees, limiting universal availability. Deployment was therefore dependent on institutional support and resource allocation.
Integration into professional development	Complementarity was more visible when AI tools were embedded in professional development initiatives (Cases 4, 6, 7). Training supported teachers in developing AI literacy, improving prompt strategies, and

	interpreting dashboards or predictive analytics. In the absence of such scaffolding, teachers struggled to interpret features (4) or relied on habitual, narrow usage patterns (2)
Shared norms and ethical use	In case 1, teachers relied on pedagogical and ethical values to judge AI outputs, as the system itself did not scaffold pedagogical alignment.
<i>Work-practice conditions</i>	
Time pressure	Time pressure emerged as a critical moderating factor. Under constrained conditions, teachers were more likely to accept AI suggestions without deeper verification (Case 7,1). In case 7, teachers explicitly reported re-viewing suggestions more thoroughly when trust was low but defaulting to quicker acceptance when under time constraints (<i>When I do not trust the AI's suggestions, I go and review the student data again. However, when I'm out of time, I more often accept the AI's suggestions</i>) (Case 7, Teacher 1).
Fit with existing routines	AI integration depended on its compatibility with existing instructional and planning routines (7). When embedded into regular workflow cycles, such as weekly differentiation planning, the tool became part of teachers' established practice (<i>"Now [with the AI] it is much easier to switch between the different levels within my class"</i>) (Case 7, Teacher 3). In contrast, when the system required additional coordination or diverged from routine practice, engagement was more limited (Case 2, particularly larger groups)
Support and interaction scaffolding	Across cases, teachers expressed the need for structured guidance in interacting with AI systems. Participants in Case 6 explicitly preferred more guided interaction, describing open-ended chat as <i>"providing little structure in the interaction,"</i> and indicating preference for interfaces that scaffold lesson design more explicitly. Teachers in Case 4 highlighted the need for support in interpreting analytic features before confidently using them for pedagogical decisions.

<p>Autonomy of teacher decision making</p>	<p>Interaction patterns depended on whether final decision authority re-mained clearly situated with the teacher (1,7). Teachers commonly treated AI suggestions as provisional recommendations that require contextual validation (<i>"Sometimes there are children suggested [by the AI] of whom I think, yeah, they should be there... Or sometimes there is someone there that shouldn't be there"</i> (Case 7, Teacher 4)</p>
<p><i>Adoption</i></p>	
<p>Initial adoption</p>	<p>Teachers reported engaging with the AI system when it was experienced as supporting idea generation and improving instructional design, even if it did not necessarily reduce workload. As one participant noted, <i>"The tool does not necessarily reduce my workload, but it provides additional support in preparing lessons. It proposes helpful suggestions regarding different ways to provide feedback to the students"</i> (Case 6).</p>

Sustained use	Sustained engagement depended on alignment with professional needs, instructional goals and established routines (7,2). Case 7 integration into weekly differentiation planning cycles supported continued use, as the AI tool became embedded within existing workflow structures. Teachers described how this integration improved their practice: <i>“Now [with the AI] it is much easier to switch between the different levels within my class... differentiation has gotten much better and more organised”</i> (Case 7, Teacher 3). By contrast, in Case 2, usability challenges in larger groups and limited fit with regular classroom organization constrained deeper engagement. As one teacher explained, the dashboard became harder to manage at scale: <i>“The group was just quite large... That makes it easier to keep track of things, of course”</i> (Case 2, Teacher 4).
Risks of offloading critical tasks to AI	In cases 6 and 7, there was evidence of potential long-term offloading of diagnostic and decision-making work to AI systems, particularly under time pressure or increased familiarity. <i>“When I do not trust the AI’s suggestions, I go and review the student data again. However, when I’m out of time, I more often accept the AI’s suggestions”</i> (Case 7, Teacher 1.)

Across cases, several deployment conditions were observed to shape how teachers engaged with AI systems. These included organizational factors such as licensing structures and integration into professional development, work-practice conditions such as time pressure and alignment with existing routines, and teacher-level characteristics including professional knowledge, prior experience, and attitudes toward AI. In addition, characteristics of the AI tools themselves, such as transparency, pedagogical alignment, interface complexity, and availability of interaction scaffolding, were associated with differences in how AI outputs were interpreted and used in practice.

Discussion

Complementarities in the Hybrid Intelligent System

We approached this analysis from a distributed cognitive system perspective, conceptualizing teacher-AI complementarity as emerging within a hybrid intelligent system in which human and artificial agents coordinate to accomplish educational tasks. Complementarity makes interaction between human and AI necessary. Rather than viewing AI as replacing isolated

teacher functions, our findings show how educational work is redistributed across agents. Across cases, we identified three different types of educational tasks with distinct AI-human interaction patterns:

1. *Creation Tasks*: refer to pedagogical design activities such as planning lessons, designing learning activities, and developing feedback strategies. In these tasks, AI primarily contributed generative and information-processing capabilities, such as proposing lesson structures, activity ideas, or draft instructional materials. Teachers contributed contextual pedagogical, curricular, and learner knowledge and retained responsibility for evaluating, adapting, and approving AI-generated content. Complementarity in creation tasks therefore involved AI-supported idea generation and drafting combined with teacher-led pedagogical judgment and instructional decision-making.
2. *Regulation Tasks*: refer to real-time classroom orchestration, such as monitoring group work, detecting disengagement, and supporting students during learning activities. In these tasks, AI systems contributed to the perception of classroom events by detecting patterns in interaction, engagement, or collaboration data. Teachers interpreted these AI-generated cues considering their pedagogical knowledge and classroom context and enacted pedagogical interventions. Complementarity in regulation tasks was thus characterized by AI-supported perception and teacher-led interpretation and action.
3. *Diagnostics Tasks*: refer to analytic activities that involve interpreting student learning data to inform instructional decisions, such as grouping students, adapting task difficulty, or planning differentiated instruction. In these tasks, AI systems aggregated and analysed large-scale performance data and generated diagnostic suggestions. Teachers contextualized and validated these AI-generated diagnoses using their knowledge of students, curriculum, and classroom dynamics, and made final pedagogical decisions. Complementarity in diagnosis tasks reflected AI handling data analysis and teachers providing contextual pedagogical judgment.

The distributed cognition perspective that we have taken here assumes that agents interact by coordinating internal and external representations used to understand current classroom situations, make decisions and take actions. Internal representations are the knowledge and the skills that teachers are using, as well as the models that AI tools are using to process data. Coordination is enabled by external representations through which teachers externalize their knowledge (e.g. writing prompts) or by which AI tools communicate to the teacher (e.g. by dashboards). Our findings extend distributed cognition accounts by showing that coordination between human and artificial representations is not automatic but contingent on epistemic alignment. Complementarity emerged when AI-generated representations (e.g., dashboards, draft plans, predictive groupings) were interpretable within teachers' existing pedagogical frameworks. Where this alignment was weak, teachers either disengaged or increased verification effort, sometimes reducing efficiency gains. Complementarity in hybrid intelligent systems therefore depends not only on task division, but on representational compatibility.

For complementarity to emerge, there needs to be an interaction between these representations. This is because teachers and AI models hold complementary knowledge. In several of the cases discussed above, AI outputs required teacher-held context knowledge to interpret and use AI outputs appropriately. Teachers contribute classroom observations and knowledge about students that are not captured by the tool, and this contextualisation is explicitly noted in the cross-case synthesis (Cases 1, 2) and in the workflow logic of dashboard-supported cases (Cases 4, 7).

Across cases, pedagogical and curriculum knowledge did not diminish but became a coordination mechanism within the hybrid system. Teachers acted as epistemic gatekeepers who evaluated, validated, and contextualized AI outputs before instructional enactment. In our cases, TPACK knowledge was represented both in humans and AI, and situation specific skills were likewise enacted by the teacher, as well as the AI tool. Teachers were observed in many occasions to adjust their understanding to information displayed by the tool. In the case of contextual knowledge, it was provided by teachers in the form of prompts or example documents to the AI (6) which then made use of it to adjust its behaviour. In one case, the teacher was enabled to adjust the algorithm used by the tool (4).

This also has related design implication: support inspection and traceability/transparency of AI suggestions as it may increase workload otherwise. A recurring teacher action is inspection/checking why a suggestion is made and whether it fits the classroom reality (case 1, 4, 6, 7). It might help to state explicitly that tools should make the rationale behind recommendations easy to inspect (for example which evidence or criteria drove the suggestion), so teachers can verify and adjust more efficiently.

The socio-technical conditions of complementarity

A second assumption that we started from was that the hybrid intelligent system should be understood as a socio-technical system in which several conditions determine to what degree complementarity can be observed or not. Our cross-case analysis has brought out a broad number of factors that influence complementarity, including characteristics of the teacher, of the AI tool, and of the deployment conditions. Figure 1 synthesizes these multi-level dynamics and illustrates how complementarity emerges at their intersection within a hybrid intelligent system.

As already alluded to in the previous section, the teacher plays a central role in the hybrid intelligent system. For this reason, a number of factors were identified in the cases that relate to teacher knowledge and competence. Only if sufficient levels of pedagogical knowledge, technical skills and content knowledge were available, did this lead to meaningful interaction. Attitudes towards AI was another factor that determined the readiness to use AI in a meaningful way, as well as how the tool fit their prior practices with AI tools. Beyond task redistribution, hybrid systems introduce new forms of coordination work, including inspecting algorithmic outputs, calibrating trust, and translating between system representations and

classroom realities. From a distributed cognition perspective, this coordination work becomes a core professional activity in itself. Professional competence in AI-supported environments therefore increasingly includes meta-level coordination skills, which may reshape role expectations and workload structures over time.

While teacher characteristics featured very strongly, the role of the AI tool was less pronounced in our study. A reason may have been that while multiple teachers were observed (leading to variety of interaction patterns), the AI tool was stable in each case. This may have led to an underrepresentation of tool characteristics influencing complementarity. The dominating aspect that we evidenced was the degree to which AI outputs were aligned with pedagogical models, curricular structures, and classroom realities. Misalignment increased verification effort and reduced perceived complementarity, underscoring the importance of representational alignment within distributed cognitive systems. Transparency of AI outputs and underlying decisions and suggestions was another important factor. Across cases, AI systems varied in modality (dashboards vs chatbots), degree of autonomy (suggestive vs semi-automated), and interaction structure (open-ended vs guided dialogue). These differences influenced how representations were externalized and interpreted, suggesting that complementarity is also shaped by interface design and the epistemic opacity of underlying models.

Finally, a number of deployment conditions were observed to influence complementarity. These were related to the alignment with existing work practices or routines, the level of teacher autonomy, time pressure, or the amount of support that was provided, either in the tool itself, during introduction or by embedding into teacher development programs. These conditions are most likely only a snapshot of some of the factors that play a role, and further research is required to extend this list, but they highlight that complementarity is not a fixed property of a tool, but an emergent phenomenon shaped by the interaction between human expertise, system design, and institutional and social context.

Conclusions: Towards the future of Hybrid Intelligent Systems in Education

An emerging design space

In this paper we have proposed a framework on teacher-AI complementarity that bridges cognitive and sociocultural perspective. Based on seven cases of the use of AI in authentic settings, we have extracted evidence for emerging complementarity on the task and the skill level, and we have proposed a number of socio-technical deployment conditions that would seem to have an impact on complementarity. Our analysis does not prescribe specific technical solutions, but it opens a design and research space for hybrid intelligent systems in education. Rather than framing AI in education as a question of automation versus replacement, our findings suggest that the future lies in carefully structured complementarity, where task redistribution, knowledge coordination and professional judgment are balanced. To realize this vision, we identify following research and development priorities:

Teacher Agency

At the heart of this transformation is the role and agency of the teacher. Are we designing AI systems that empower educators as reflective professionals, or ones that gradually displace essential aspects of their pedagogical judgment? We argue for a future where teacher agency is not diminished, but redefined, not through automation, but through the reshaping of the context in which teachers perceive, interpret and act. In this vision, AI functions as a partner in cognition, providing real-time insights, surface learning patterns and enabling responsive support that would otherwise remain inaccessible. Teachers are not replaced but repositioned as orchestrators of hybrid systems in which human and machine intelligence co-evolve.

Preventing Overreliance on AI

Our findings also indicate potential risks of offloading diagnostic and decision-making work, particularly under time pressure, in case of lack of knowledge or increasing familiarity with AI tools. Over-reliance on AI can lead to deskilling, particularly in teachers' perceptual and interpretive abilities - skills essential for responsive and context-sensitive teaching. When low-level tasks that traditionally support the development of instructional expertise (such as noticing classroom dynamics) are mindlessly offloaded, we risk undermining the cognitive processes that enable adaptive teaching.

Contextualizing AI systems

Additionally, AI systems that are decontextualized or lack pedagogical grounding may generate misleading recommendations. For instance, systems may flag disengagement based on inactivity, without considering teaching goals, task design, collaborative dynamics, thereby undermining teachers' trust and instructional consistency. AI models have shown to exhibit biases with regards to underrepresented populations. Their use in predictive modelling in education (e.g. predicting student dropout or disengagement based on early warning signs) might reinforce teachers' biases towards underrepresented groups, rather than question them.

Allow co-evolution

We believe that in a possible future of hybrid intelligent systems that would allow co-evolution between humans and AI, AI models and tools would need to be "aware" of their limitations and communicate these to their users: During design-time, biases or the limited amount of training data would need to be uncovered. During run-time, model evolution should not happen autonomously but put the human in the loop. In this way, AI tools could incorporate good teaching practices or learn from feedback about their recommendations from teachers or students.

Co-designing of AI tools that involves stakeholder

As we move from seeing AI tools as technical add-ons to imagining them as pedagogically embedded and reflecting complexities of classroom practice, we need to integrate educational stakeholders, educators, students, parents, school leaders and the EdTech sector into co-designing systems, to ensure that AI solutions are shaped by and responsive to teachers' expertise, instructional intentions and contextual constraints.

Limitations and future research directions

The current study is necessarily limited in several regards. While the framework was useful to analyse these cases, it certainly needs to be extended in breadth and depth and validated through other means and in other settings. We acknowledge that the current analysis is constrained by the focus of the seven cases. For example, our cases did not cover uses of AI specifically for grading or particular administrative tasks that teachers have (e.g. reporting). Below are some of the directions we are currently undertaking to advance this research agenda.

Understanding complementarity in practice

The current analysis was constrained by the use of qualitative methods which needs to be enhanced by a more formal approach to evidence specific complementarity patterns. This includes developing frameworks and instruments that examine how AI augments, complements or replaces specific teaching tasks, and how these shifts influence teacher cognition, decision-making and expertise development. In our current work, we analyse task-level and skill-level changes resulting from the introduction of AI in the classroom by operationalising this with a three step approach. First, we use Hierarchical Task Analysis (Stanton, 2006) to decompose a pedagogical task into smaller subtasks and actions, allowing researchers to compare a baseline workflow (before the introduction of AI) with an AI supported workflow and to pinpoint where work is redistributed between teachers and AI, and where new actions emerge. Second, a skill and knowledge analysis links those (new) actions to the professional skills and knowledge required to perform them (Blömeke et al., 2015), and corresponding AI capabilities (Molenaar, 2022b). Third, a complementarity analysis integrates task and skill information to characterise whether AI use reflects replacement, complementarity, or augmentation in practice, acknowledging that different configurations of complementarity within the same pedagogical task can exist. This approach then allows a more systematic description of complementarity configurations which in the current paper we gave only in qualitative sense.

AI affordances and design of interactions for education

In our future development efforts we will prioritise AI models and interaction interfaces that strengthen teacher- AI complementarity. This direction aligns with Cukurova et al. (2026), who

call for advancing AI towards praxical and synergistic forms of teaming, where collaboration evolves from tool use to learning partnerships. Along this continuum, teacher-AI interaction moves beyond transactional request-response exchanges and situational information support towards operational integrations in which AI executes pedagogically aligned goals. More advanced configurations involve AI systems that dynamically adapt to teacher feedback and instructional intent, and ultimately proactively engage in negotiation and co-reasoning that challenge and extend teachers' thinking. Progressing towards these praxical and synergistic teaming requires AI systems that are pedagogically grounded, equipped with adaptive learning capabilities, and supported by explainable models. The design of interaction structures are also important to enable teachers to iteratively interrogate, negotiate, and refine AI behaviour in alignment with pedagogical goals. Such socio-technical configurations are essential for strengthening teacher agency, fostering calibrated trust and ethical use, and supporting teachers' ongoing professional development. Advancing these conditions will be central to achieving sustained human-AI complementarity in educational practice.

Professional learning for hybrid systems

Future research on teacher professional learning for AI-enhanced teaching should be grounded in core constructs of the learning sciences, particularly how teachers make sense of cognition, learning processes, and motivation in real time within hybrid human-AI classroom systems. Professional learning should support teachers in reasoning pedagogically with data and AI outputs, using them to inform decisions that align with their instructional goals and their understanding of students as learners.

We argue that professional learning should be designed around teacher-AI co-activity, in which teachers and AI systems jointly participate in pedagogical tasks and teacher competence is demonstrated in how educators perceive, interpret and decide within these hybrid configurations. Research is needed to investigate how different forms of professional learning, such as co-design with AI tools, situated classroom experimentation, structured reflection using perception-interpretation-decision frameworks and knowledge creation in communities of practice, can foster instructionally meaningful and theory-informed reasoning in context.

In particular, future studies should examine how professional learning can support teachers' development along

situated trajectories of teacher-AI complementarity, recognizing that teachers may operate at different levels of expertise and human-AI teaming depending on task, tool, and context. We also call for research that links professional learning design more closely to AI system characteristics (e.g., transparency, autonomy, explainability). Higher levels of AI autonomy may require deeper pedagogical reasoning, ethical awareness and professional vision, suggesting that professional learning must be differentiated and aligned with both teacher competence and AI design features.

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